

Dialectics of Liberation Congress: Creating a Digital Archive

This is the proofread version of my master's thesis, submitted to the Faculty of Cultural Studies, Digital Humanities, at Paderborn University in September 2022

Natascha Naumann
nnaumann@posteo.de

Table of Contents

List of Tables and Figures.....	iii
List of Acronyms	iv
1. Introduction.....	1
2. Congress on the Dialectics of Liberation.....	3
3. Archives and Digital Technology	7
3.1 Archives - General Introduction	7
3.2 Archives and Digital Technologies.....	10
3.3 Archives under the Scrutiny of Academics.....	12
3.4 Archives and Digitalization - the First Digital Archives	13
3.5 Archives in the 21 st Century.....	16
3.6 Archives and Access	18
4. Practical Project, Methodology.....	20
4.1 List of Tools, Software, and Websites	20
4.2 List of Data	21
4.3 Analysis of Inventory Lists of Berke’s Estate at the PET Archives	21
4.3.1 Documentation of the Analysis.....	22
4.4 TEI XML Encoding of Information about the Congress	26
4.4.1 TEI XML	26
4.4.2 ODD.....	27
4.4.3 Roma ODD Customization Tool.....	27
4.4.4 Schematron	28
4.4.5 OxGarage Conversion.....	28
4.4.6 Oxygen XML Editor	28
4.4.7 Transcription of Audio Files	28
4.4.8 Process of TEI Encoding.....	29
5. Results.....	30
5.1 Results Analysis of Inventory Lists	30
5.2 Results TEI XML Project	36

5.2.1 List of Persons.....	37
5.2.2 List of Places.....	41
5.2.3 List of Organizations.....	43
5.2.4 List of Terms.....	46
5.2.5 List of Audio Recordings.....	48
5.2.6 List of Events.....	50
5.2.7 Transcript.....	52
5.2.8 TEI header.....	56
5.2.9 Audio Recordings, Milestone Element.....	58
5.2.10 Constraint Specifications.....	61
6. Discussion.....	61
6.1 Discussion Analysis of Inventory Lists.....	61
6.2 Discussion TEI XML Project.....	62
6.3 Discussion of the Term Digital Archive in Relation to this Project.....	67
7. Conclusion.....	69
8. Reference List.....	71
9. Annex.....	77
Annex A.....	77
Annex B.....	81
Annex C.....	87

List of Tables and Figures

<i>Table 1: Examples for Entries in Reel-to-Reel Tape Recordings, Initial List; PP-JB-IPS-tapes.doc...</i>	22
<i>Table 2: Audio Recordings 18 July 1967, morning.....</i>	31
<i>Table 3: Audio Recordings 18 July 1967, afternoon.....</i>	32
<i>Table 4: Audio recordings 22 July 1967, 8 pm</i>	33
<i>Table 5: Audio recordings 23 July 1967</i>	35
<i>Table 6: Elements and Attributes allowed in Element <listPerson> in the List of Persons</i>	38
<i>Table 7: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <person> in the List of Persons</i>	39
<i>Table 8: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the <listPlace> Element in the List of Places</i>	41
<i>Table 9: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <place> in the List of Places</i>	42
<i>Table 10: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the <listOrg> Element in List Organizations</i>	44
<i>Table 11: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <org> in List Organizations</i>	45
<i>Table 12: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the <listTerm> Element in List Terms.....</i>	47
<i>Table 13: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <term> in List Terms</i>	47
<i>Table 14: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <audio> and Example of Encoding for the Element in the List of Audio Recordings</i>	49
<i>Table 15: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <event> and Examples of Encoding for the Element in the List of Events</i>	51
<i>Table 16: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <div>in the XML Document for Transcripts</i>	54
<i>Table 17: Examples of Encoding, Transcript.....</i>	55
<i>Table 18: Required Elements TEI header List of Audio Recordings</i>	56
<i>Table 19: Truncated Examples of TEI header List of Audio Recordings.....</i>	57
<i>Table 20: Equivalents of the xml:id of the Audio Recordings and the Digital File Number.....</i>	58
<i>Table 21: Milestones Sorted by Audio Files.....</i>	58
<i>Table 22: Milestones Sorted by their Chronological Order in the Transcript.....</i>	59
<i>Figure 1: Overlap of the Audio Files related to the Event on 23 July 1967, Public Address to the Black Community, Questions and Answers</i>	60
<i>Figure 2: Relation of XML Documents</i>	66

The shortlink to the digital data referenced in this thesis may be requested from the author for personal research purposes only, due to copyright restrictions on the audio recordings and transcripts.

List of Acronyms

ADHO	Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations
AGI	Archivo General de Indias
CMS	Content Management System
IATH	Institute for Advanced Technology in the Humanities
IBM	International Business Machines Corporation
ICA	International Council on Archives
IDC	International Data Cooperation
ISAD(G)	General International Standard Archival Description
NARA	The U.S. National Archives and Records Administration
PET	Planned Environment Therapy (Archives and Special Collections)
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WWW	World Wide Web
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

The Congress on the Dialectics of Liberation took place from 15 to 30 July 1967 at the Roundhouse in London, United Kingdom (UK), a former railway roundhouse turned into an arts venue in 1966¹. It was organized by a group of so-called anti-psychiatrists and advertised as „a unique gathering to demystify human violence in all its forms, the social systems from which it emanates, and to explore new forms of action“ (Berke, 1969, p. 410). Announced as a major counterculture event, speeches by well-known intellectuals from different countries like Allen Ginsberg, Ronald D. Laing, and Herbert Marcuse were attended by up to 3000 people daily.

Many of the problems addressed at the congress, such as war, racial inequity, climate change, and their relation to capitalism persist, despite changes in the political-social setting. Others were inherent and are obvious from a contemporary perspective, like the blatant bias in the selection of the speakers featuring only one nonwhite main speaker, the Black Power activist Stokely Carmichael. The only female contributor featured in the program was the artist Carolee Schneemann who oversaw a performance of kinetic theater.

The main source of reference for most of the little research that is available on the congress is a book with transcripts of audio recordings that were made of the speeches held at the congress. The magnetic tapes and other material related to the congress in the estate of one of the main organizers, Joseph Berke, are held at an English community archive. A collection-level description of the estate has only recently been put online, and access to most of the material is only possible on-site.

What does the term *digital archive* refer to? The first part, *digital*, could be summarized as binary data that can be accessed by computerized technology. The second part, *archive*, was formerly understood as certain records kept for preservation in a specific physical space. Today, a wide range of collections is labeled *archives*. Next to governmental, organizational, or private archives created to meet compliance requirements for recordkeeping, there are archives curated or accumulated by individuals, groups, or organizations, made up of every imaginable kind of material or media, conceived for long-term preservation or contemporary usage, volatile or consistent, private, or public.

¹ The Roundhouse continues to be an event venue to the present day. A website with a current photo gallery and a 3D virtual tour gives an impression of the vastness of the building. Roundhouse Trust Ltd., 2022.

Archives run the gamut from storing exclusively analog material that is only accessible on-site to online archives holding solely born-digital content and every thinkable combination in between.

Preliminary research on the congress by the author included online research and analyses of audio recordings made at the congress. It yielded results in the identification of additional nonwhite speakers and the discovery of hitherto unpublished speeches. The research on Carmichael's participation in the congress was in the hope of contributing to a future digital archive that displays the audio files. However, due to copyright issues, this will not be possible in the foreseeable future, as spelled out later in the text.

The project goal was to research the audio files and documentation on the material on the congress in Berke's estate and preserve previous research results, focusing on Carmichael's contributions. A prototype was created to document and preserve the research in an archival and at the same time accessible and extensible format without violating any copyright restrictions. It was designed to be scaled to the entire congress, used for further research, and to serve as a basis for a wide variety of visual presentations. The information on Carmichael's interaction with members of the Black Liberation movement in the UK will hopefully contribute to the field of Black Studies in Britain that was introduced as degree courses at Birmingham City University as recently as 2017 (Birmingham City University).

While preparing for the project, the author became aware of the lack of academic discussions of digital archives from the perspective of cultural studies. There is practical guidance on the digitization of analog archives, digital technologies are applied in the field of humanities and there is a wide range of digital projects, e.g. editions with, among others, archival purposes. The abstract concept of the archive has been discussed widely in the humanities, notably in literary and cultural studies, to a point that in 2015, the American Society of Historians observed that "(...) the terms *archive* and *archives* have proven remarkably elastic" (American Historical Association, 2015). However, the critical perspectives on archival models most of the time did not apply to the practice of actual archiving, because they were based on vague or outdated ideas of actual archival work, and their authors were not knowledgeable of archival terminology (Fertig, 2011, p. 2).

The author argues that there is a need for a basic knowledge of historical and current discourses on the term *archive* and actual archives to create a practical concept for an academically operated digital archive of the Dialectics of Liberation congress from the specific perspective of cultural science. According to the contemporary academic

consensus, every decision on this path is performative and will inherently be part of the final product. This report forms a part of this process by documenting the progress of the work on this project.

2. Congress on the Dialectics of Liberation

The congress was organized by the Institute of Phenomenological Studies², mainly by Joseph Berke and Leon Redler, assisted by a wide range of helpers (Berke, 1969, p. 411). Among the intellectuals contributing were Gregory Bateson, Julian Beck, Stokely Carmichael³, David Cooper, Edmundo Desnoes, John Gerassi, Allen Ginsberg, Lucien Goldmann, Paul Goodman, Emmett Grogan, Igor Hajek, Jules Henry, Ronald D. Laing, John La Rose, Herbert Marcuse, Thich Nat Hanh, Gavriilo Petrovic, Ross Speck, Paul Sweezy, and Simon Vinkenoog. Winston Branch, Obi Egbuna, Roy Sawh, and Michael X broadened the range of speakers by contributing to the event that addressed the Black community.

According to participant Susan Sherman, who was invited by Berke to report on the congress, the public lectures in the morning were attended by up to 3000 people daily. In the afternoons there were question-and-answer sessions, seminars, and discussion groups, as well as informal meetings in between the scheduled events, to discuss ways to change violence and destruction. The evening sessions included poetry readings⁴, music performances and films⁵, and a kinetic theater performance directed by Carolee Schneemann⁶. There were representatives from the West Indies, African countries, Canada, and America, students from West Berlin, the Provos from Holland, and political activists from Norway and Sweden⁷ (Sherman, 2007). Berke experienced the event as a “Tribe Meeting” or “Be-in” as opposed to the usual conception of a congress (Berke, 1969, p. 411). A website about an event in reminiscence of the congress staged in 2016 presents

² The Institute of Phenomenological Studies was founded in 1966 by a group of radical existential psychiatrists: Dr. Joseph Berke, Dr. David Cooper, Dr. John Heaton, Dr. Ronald Laing, Dr. Leon Redler, and Dr. Paul Senft. Jakobsen, 2012 According to information that James Harding received from the former archivist Craig during a visit to the PET Archives that holds Berke’s estate, the institute’s main function was to organize and administer the congress. Harding, 2010, p. 123.

³ Stokely Carmichael changed his name to Kwame Ture in 1978. In this document the name Stokely Carmichael is used when referring to the speeches at the congress in 1967 when he was known under that name.

⁴ Among others by Allen Ginsberg, Thich Nhat Hanh, John La Rose, Susan Sherman

⁵ E.g. on the dangers of technology by Roy Battersby

⁶ *Round House*, which included her films *Fuses* and *Viet Flakes*. Harding, 2010.

⁷ Sherman was invited by Berke to join the congress and write a report for the *Ikon* magazine which she published at the time. The report was republished in her autobiography in 2007. Sherman, 2007, pp. 134–141.

additional anecdotal information, a list of well-known participants, and film stills (Davis, Ivimy, & Levy). There is a short Wikipedia article based on secondary sources.⁸

The main events of the congress were recorded on magnetic tape by Roy Battersby and Ben Churchill (Battersby, 2010). A set of 23 LPs featuring the main lectures was printed from the recordings.⁹ In 1968 Penguin published a book with transcripts of eleven speeches based on recordings made at the congress (Cooper, 1968) which was republished in 2015 by Verso (Cooper, 2015). *Counter Culture*, an assemblage of contributions from counterculture activists, features a second speech by Carmichael¹⁰ which is not published in the Penguin/Verso book (Berke, 1969, pp. 182–194).¹¹

While women contributed to the organization of the congress (Berke, 1969, pp. 411–412) and participated in discussions and poetry readings, the only woman contributing to the program of the congress was the artist Carolee Schneemann, who was invited by Berke but was not listed on the official advertising for the congress. According to her recollections as well as testimony by Sherman and other participants Schneemann was treated with contempt by many of the male contributors of the congress.¹² Quite contrarily to the lack of appreciation for her approach at the time, the most comprehensive research on the congress to date centers on Schneemann's kinetic theater performance *Round House*. In *Dialectics, Decorum and Collage – Sabotaging Schneemann at the Dialectics of Liberation Congress, London 1967*, a chapter in his book *Cutting Performances* on feminist artists, James Harding cites Schneemann and sources from the Joseph Berke Archive¹³. Harding depicts in detail the intellectual, misogynist, and hostile-to-the-arts atmosphere Schneemann encountered during the congress. He points out how Schneemann's project, including her plan to show her films *Fuses* and *Viet Flakes* as part of the performance, radically challenged the self-assuredness of the organizers and their assumption of representing the spearhead of societal change (Harding, 2010).

Kristine Stiles claims that the role model for the Dialectics congress was the

⁸ A detailed description of the available sources can be found in a preliminary paper by the author. Naumann, 2022.

⁹ They are listed as available at a few university libraries in the US (WorldCat). The British Library in London has a set of the LPs as well as CD-R format playback copies created by the library (Information obtained in an email in March 2022 from Stephen Cleary, Lead Curator, Literary and Creative Recordings at the British Library) British Library, Sound & Moving Image Catalogue, 2022.

¹⁰

¹¹ This book is only available in libraries or online at the Internet Archive since 2021.

¹² Harding citing from Schneemann's *More than Meat Joy* in his book *Cutting Performances*, Harding, 2010, Sherman in her article on the congress. Sherman, 1967 and in an interview conducted by the author, participants cited on the website reminiscing the congress, Davis, Ivimy, & Levy.

¹³ PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021 More detailed information on the archive is provided later in the text.

Destruction in Art (DIAS), a counterculture artists event that took place from 9 to 12 September 1966 at the Africa Center in London with additional happenings at various locations.¹⁴ DIAS was conceived and orchestrated by the stateless artist and political activist Gustav Mezger, assisted by poet John Sharkey. According to Stiles a three-day trial against the two of them took place during the Dialectics congress for presenting a performance of the controversial Austrian artist Hermann Nitsch at DIAS (Stiles, 1987, 31; Stiles, 1992, 85, 86). Harding suggested that this might have contributed to the Dialectics' organizers' disapproval of Schneemann's plan of showing the film *Fuses* which some perceived as pornographic. Mezger was a participant in the Dialectics congress and was filmed by Peter Davis¹⁵ during a discussion with among others Carolee Schneemann and Susan Sherman (Davis, 1968).

Carmichael equally stood out, both in the contemporary reaction to his speeches as well as from the present-day perspective. He was invited as the only non-white intellectual to give a main speech at the congress. During his stay, he met with people involved in the Black Liberation movement in England. One of these meetings brought about the plan to organize a second speech at the congress which would involve other Black speakers and a decisively Blacker audience.¹⁶ The audio recordings and video footage of the events featuring Carmichael give an impression of the heated discussions during all the events he participated in. The reception of the press, as cited by Harding using sources kept at the PET Archives, documents the turmoil Carmichael's presence created in the UK.

As one of the main organizers of the congress Berke kept most, if not all material related to the congress. He handed it over to a community archive, among other materials, when he was still alive.¹⁷ The archive had very little funding and information on the material was only available on-site. In 2018, the ownership of the archive was transferred to The Mulberry Bush Organisation, the site was renamed The Mulberry Bush Third Space and became known as the PET Archives and Special Collections. A team of professional archivists is currently working on bringing the management and the service in line with

¹⁴ Stiles claims that Erving Goffman spoke at the congress. However, he was invited and originally scheduled as speaker (schedule held at PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021) but did not attend the congress. Stiles must have used an advertising poster as source that claimed Goffman would be one of the speakers.

¹⁵ The film is available on YouTube and consists of clips from various events at the congress.

¹⁶ Michael X and Phil Epstein refer to this in the audio recordings of the event of 23, July 1967. One of the meetings was recorded and Epstein tried to play the recording at the event. However, the attempt failed because the quality was bad, and the audience could not understand.

¹⁷ Berke deceased in January 2021.

international archival standards and best practices (The Mulberry Bush Limited, 2022) as endorsed and accepted by the International Council on Archives (ICA). A website was launched in 2020, featuring an online catalog¹⁸ with the first brief collection-level descriptions (The Mulberry Bush Third Space, 2022a). This is a huge step forward in the provision of information on the Berke estate's content, however, it requires knowledge of its existence in the first place.¹⁹

The literature on Carmichael's contribution to the congress and his influence on the further development of the Black Liberation Movement in the UK mainly relies on one source, which is the printed version of the speech he gave on 18 July 1967, either cited from the Penguin/Verso book (Cooper, 2015) or the collection of Carmichael's speeches *Stokely Speaks* published in 1971 (Carmichael, 1971).²⁰ Another source of information is Carmichael's autobiography *Ready for the Revolution*, co-authored by Ekwueme Michael Thelwell, which was published postmortem in 2003 (Carmichael & Thelwell, 2003).²¹ In the latter, Ture²² recounts his sojourn in the UK on the occasion of his invitation to the congress and cites parts of the first speech on 18 July 1967. As interesting as the accounts of his encounter with Michael X and the events at the congress are, some of them don't bear scrutiny. For example, Ture mentions that he invited the audience to join in a minute of silence to commemorate John Coltrane who had died a day earlier before he gave his speech on the morning of 18 July (Carmichael & Thelwell, 2003, p. 578). The audio recordings prove that it wasn't him but Michael X who did so, and not in the morning before Carmichael's speech but in the afternoon before the panel discussion featuring Carmichael, John Gerassi, C.L.R. James, George Rawick, and David Cooper²³. Then Ture remembered a large number of Black people in the audience. However, although there were Black people listening to the first speech, it was mainly attended by a white audience. It was the second speech on 23 July 1967 that attracted a larger nonwhite audience²⁴. These are examples of how researching the audio files can rectify memories that might have been unclear when written down years after the event.

¹⁸ The Mulberry Bush Third Space, 2022b.

¹⁹ To improve the findability the author edited the Joseph Berke website on Wikipedia by adding a description of the estate mentioning the Dialectics of Liberation Congress held at the PET Archives and Collections and a link on 2022-05-12. Wikipedia, 2022a.

²⁰ Other literature additionally used the film by Peter Davis as source of information.

²¹ For example Ashley Dawson in *Black Power in a Transnational Frame*. Dawson, 2010 and Peniel Joseph in the biography of Carmichael. Joseph, 2014

²² Stokely Carmichael changed his name to Kwame Ture in 1978 to honor the president of Ghana, Kwame Nkrumah and the president of Guinea, Ahmed Sékou Touré.

²³ Source: Audio file 4_04/1_4_04, minutes 0:00 to 1:40

²⁴ Source: Phil Epstein and Michael X in audio file 2_24/1_2_24.

Whereas the first, advertised speech is referred to as the speech Carmichael gave at the congress, the speech Carmichael gave at the extracurricular event organized by the Black community fell into oblivion, although it has also been published as a record and in Berke's *Counterculture* book (Berke, 1969)²⁵. The other Black speakers' contributions were never published at all, neither on LPs nor in print. The same goes for the question-and-answer sessions that provide valuable information on the themes interesting to the audience. The speakers at the event referred to the entirely different atmosphere at this second event with policemen in the Roundhouse and a larger share of nonwhite audience. With this project, the author aims at informing about these sources without violating the copyrights regarding the audio data.

3. Archives and Digital Technology

This chapter aims at shedding a light on the complex, interdependent history of digital technologies and archives in theory and practice. It is in no way comprehensive but intended to provide basic theoretical knowledge as a foundation for the envisioned digital archive.

3.1 Archives - General Introduction

The wish to preserve knowledge and transmit it to future generations seems to be inherent to humankind and related efforts date back to long before the invention of writing 5000 years ago. Oral traditions are most probably the oldest form of doing so and still exist next to written forms. The urge to record human activities for various purposes seems likewise inherent.

The term *archive* is derived from the Greek word *arché*, meaning *beginning* or *origin* (Liddell & Scott, 1940). Archives form part of a group of facilities referred to as memory institutions that serve as keepers and providers of memory and knowledge. Other major memory institutions are museums and libraries which can also keep archives as part of their mission (Society of American Archivists, 2016).

Government-run official archives and business archives on one end of the range to private collections named archive by their owners and the email archive on your email account on the other end have one trait in common: Their content has by some sort of

²⁵ In this book Berke published many contributions that Cooper had excluded from his book published by Penguin.

system been selected²⁶ and sorted and indexed. Professional archivists deal with this process daily with sophisticated practical procedures based on the historical evolution of the profession. Scholars from other disciplines and private people creating archives necessarily apply some sort of system, often without awareness of the historical roots and implications.

Archival methodology and practice used to be of interest predominantly to archivists who managed and historians who used the archives. Archival practice was mainly developed in the 19th century by Prussian State archivists (Brichford, 1982, pp. 90–92) adhering to the newly established methodological principles of History as a “scientific discipline”, established by Leopold von Ranke, that required archives as ostensibly objective reservoirs of facts (Walsham, 2016, p. 9). Duranti defined *archival theory* as the whole of the ideas about what archival material is, *archival methodology* as the whole of the ideas about how to treat it, and *archival practice* as the way that archivists apply these ideas to their work (1994, p. 330).²⁷ While these terms center on the Western definition of archives, recent research on the poorly understood genealogy and archaeology of archives examines subjugated and parallel archival histories in different settings using different methods and technologies (Lowry & MacNeil, 2021; Yeo, 2021).

In 1889, the Dutch state archivists Muller, Feith, and Fruin (Ridener, 2007) published the so-called *Dutch Manual*, thereby creating the basis for the standardization of archival terminology and archival practice in Europe, North America, and Australia, according to the Canadian archivist Terry Cook (1997). In 2021, Ketelaar and Frings-Hesami stressed the enduring influence of the Dutch Manual, which was translated into several languages²⁸ (2021, pp. 1–3).

The Dutch manual drew mainly from French and German practice (Brichford, 1982, p. 93) defining an archive as “...the whole of the (...) documents (...) officially received or produced by an administrative body (...)” (Muller, Feith, & Fruin, 1940, p. 13). The concepts of provenance and original order state that archives “...must be kept carefully separate” (Muller et al., 1940, p. 39), and their arrangement “...must be based

²⁶ Even letting a private email archive grow by not deleting or even sorting the emails represents a system.

²⁷ In 2001, she defined *archival science* as a system inclusive of theory, methodology, practice, and scholarship. Duranti, 2001.

²⁸ Muller, Feith and Fruin supervised the translation into German in 1905, which consecutively was translated into Italian in 1908. The Dutch original was translated into French in 1910. Based on the French version, translations were made into Bulgarian in 1912 and into Russian in 1931. The first translation into English was made in 1940. The English translation was translated into Chinese in 1959 and into Portuguese in 1973. In 2001 an Estonian translation was published.

on the original organization of the archival collection (...) (Muller et al., 1940, p. 58).²⁹ Both concepts are closely related. At the International Congress of Archivists and Librarians in Brussels in 1910³⁰, archivists discussed the principle of provenance against the backdrop of their respective traditions and accepted it as fundamental for their profession (Cuvelier & Stainier, 1912, 246, 633-635, 650-658).

In the twentieth century, the amount of material to archive grew exponentially.³¹ On the one hand World War I produced a huge number of official records. On the other hand, there were demands to preserve judicial records, records relating to the labor movement and social questions, and census records, as well as tendencies to preserve archives from private firms³² (Dascher, 2015, p. 701). With the advance in technology, yet another explosion of records in World War II, as well as the noticeable broadening of both state and private archives from primarily written text to include other media, the cultural heritage and memory dimension of archives gained importance next to their administrative role (Cook, 2013, p. 109). The problem of dealing with the sheer amount of material evoked contrary perspectives on the role of the archivist in *appraisal*, the process of identifying the materials with sufficient value to preserve³³.

The British archivist Sir Hilary Jenkinson³⁴ heavily influenced archival theory and methodology, and thereby the practice in Great Britain and other European countries. In his *A Manual of Archive Administration*, first published in 1922, Jenkinson drew clear lines between the task of the administrator, the historian, and the archivist. He assigned the task of reducing the material to the administrator while producing the records, following carefully framed regulations that he lays out in his manual (1937, pp. 149–152). The archivist's concern was to preserve records for future research, independently of any research subject. Historians should not be involved in these processes to keep them impartial (Jenkinson, 1937, pp. 146–147). In retrospect, Terry Cook labeled this approach

²⁹ Cook, 1997.

³⁰ Representatives from: Alsace-Lorraine, Austria-Hungary, Bavaria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain and Ireland, Italy, Luxemburg, Monaco, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Prussia, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United States. Cuvelier & Stainier, 1912, pp. XIV–XXIV.

³¹ Between 1861 and 1916 the United States federal government's accumulation of records mounted from 108,000 to 1,031,000 cubic feet. McCoy, 1985, p. 2

Regarding the United Kingdom, Jenkinson cites from the first version of his manual (1922) that "The Royal Commission estimated that the bulk [created during the war period] was as large as that of the total previous contents of the Public Record Office." Jenkinson, 1937, p. 20.

³² E.g., in Germany the first private business archives were established in first decade of the twentieth century. Dascher, 2015, p. 701.

³³ Greg Bradsher calculated that in 1985 the U.S. National Archives and Records (NARA) retained approximately one percent of records permanently as archives. Bradsher, 1985.

³⁴ Hilary Jenkinson, 1882-1961

*the first archival paradigm*³⁵ in 2012, the key concept of which was *evidence* (2013, p. 107).

The American archivist Theodore R. Schellenberg³⁶, like Jenkinson, authored a manual on archival theory and practice which was first published in 1956: *Modern Archives; Principles and Techniques*. He accorded two types of values to archives, the primary ones to the originating government agency and the secondary ones to other agencies and non-government users (1998, p. 16). In contrast to Jenkinson, Schellenberg laid out guidelines for the archivist to intervene and participate in the process of selecting documents for preservation. He called for the archivist to have "...professional knowledge of research resources, research needs, and research methods ..." (1998, p. 148) to test the informational value of records, based on their content regardless of their relation to other records, to decide whether or not to preserve records on both formal and content-based criteria (Dascher, 2015, p. 701), and to even rearrange records if deemed necessary (1965, pp. 100–105). As Tschan points out, the strikingly different opinions Schellenberg and Jenkinson held on the subject of the appraisal of archival records reverberate in archival theory even in the twenty-first century, in debates surrounding the management of electronic records (2002, pp. 192–195)

The Canadian archivist Lamb stated in 1966 that the archivist had changed from being primarily a custodian to becoming a gatherer of records and manuscripts. He described the archival profession as dynamic and charged with the responsibility of determining which documentation of the present and the past would be available to future scholars (1966, pp. 4–6). Cook labeled this development the *second archival paradigm* with *memory* as its key concept (2013, p. 109).

3.2 Archives and Digital Technologies

Archivists have always been creating, among others, inventories, file lists, and finding aids for their holdings. Records managers additionally capture descriptive information about their organization's records. This so-called metadata helps archivists to preserve the archival material and is used by researchers to identify, find, and interpret it. For the greater part of the 20th century, the creation of metadata lacked standards (Duff & van Ballegoie, 2006).

³⁵ In an essay published in 2012 Cook argues that archival paradigms have gone through four phases over the past 150 years. Cook, 2013

³⁶ Theodore R. Schellenberg, 1903-1970

Before the invention of the computer, national variations of analog punched-card systems were used for cataloging and finding aids in government agencies and businesses. From the 1950s up to 1964 computers were very expensive specialized machines called mainframes that were accessed via punch cards and used data storage systems such as magnetic drums, cores, and tapes. By 1964 most Federal agencies in the United States had computerized systems, and computer use for important decision-making by government executives made the related computer data sources potential records needed to prepare to deal with a great increase in information sources, as well as the complex and highly specialized problems of appraising raw scientific data. The urgent need to create appraisal rules for machine-language records was discussed on an international level for the first time at the ICA in 1965 (Fishbein, 1972, pp. 35–43).

In 1965, the International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) released the flexible and upgradable System/360, a family of general-purpose computers, all running the same programs and using the same tapes, disks, and printers. This led to a surge in computer usage in a wide variety of settings. However, computers were still large mainframes with transistor technology and access via punch cards (Computer History Museum, 1996-2022). Writing additional programs to those provided by IBM was a big undertaking only specialists could accomplish (Jackson, 2014). Archives and libraries from various countries in the Global North³⁷ experimented with the use of computers for consistent and repetitive tasks, remarking that standardization was one of the important problems of mechanization (McCallum, 2003, pp. 1–3).

In contrast, in most countries of the Global South throughout the 1950s and 1960s, the focus on archival work was on emergency programs to preserve archival material in the first place. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), in close cooperation with ICA, provided mobile microfilming units and expertise on-site and published terminological and bibliographic tools³⁸ (Evans, 1987). UNESCO set up a program to train information professionals of all countries in the full range of technology related to their discipline despite different levels of technological development and the obstacles posed by the *development trap*³⁹. The Global South

³⁷ Canada, Germany, Sweden, UK, USA, and the Soviet Union

³⁸ *Guides to the sources of the history of nations*, listing locations of archival and other historical materials of former colonies in Latin America, Africa, Asia, and Oceania in repositories in Europe and the United States. The 60-volume guide was published in English, French, German, Italian, and Spanish between 1958 and 1984. A WorldCat search lists available copies in various libraries.

³⁹ Meaning that the faster the richer countries develop, the harder it is for the poorer ones to keep up.

continues to face additional challenges due to e.g., financial restraints, climate conditions, human-induced constraints such as wars, and dispersal of material because of colonial history.⁴⁰

Even in the Global North, in the early 1970s computers were used only in large and well-funded archives. During the 1980s, the national archives of most developed countries computerized their control systems. It was only in the mid-1980s, when cheaper personal computers and versatile software packages became more widely available, that the ICA stated a runaway development of different computer systems in municipal and provincial archives, archives or records management units of private firms, and specialist organizations (Cook, 1989).

3.3 Archives under the Scrutiny of Academics

From the 1970s to the 1990s new archival theories evolved: As Tschan cites Boom and Ham, the archivist's task was to preserve as complete and faithful a picture of the whole of society as possible (2002, p. 178). The American archivist Norton's theories of what should be preserved were at the core of what came to be called *governance* in the 1990s: the political processes that exist in and between institutions and the affected public (Cook, 2004, p. 11).

The late 1960s and early 1970s brought forth general and widespread changes in society. The French philosopher, Michel Foucault drew the academic world's attention to question the idea of archives. He coined the term *episteme* as a set of unconscious rules that determine what is to be taken seriously by the scientific community and society during a certain time and called the discussion within this *episteme* the related *discourse*. Foucault characterized the archive in an abstract way⁴¹ as "the general system of the formation and transformation of statements". The "system of [their] enunciability" and "system of its [their] functioning" (1982, pp. 129–130) determined what could and could not be said, which could only be described once it had changed.

Foucault's theory of discourse as knowledge and power inspired scholars from a wide range of disciplines to discuss the role of archives as institutions creating and legitimizing individual and collective memory. However inspiring this growing literature was, the authors lacked a rudimentary understanding of archives and the archivist's profession,

⁴⁰ Information on current endeavors for physical and digital preservation worldwide can be found on both UNESCO's and ICA's websites.

⁴¹ The book "L'archéologie du savoir" was published in 1969 by Éditions Gallimard. It was translated by A.M. Sheridan Smith and published by Pantheon Books in the United States and England in 1972.

they very rarely cited worldwide archival professional literature and did not provide practical approaches (Schwartz & Cook, 2002, p. 2).

By the same token, most archival research remained focused on the technology and mechanics of archival processes avoiding examining the interpretative role of the archivists in performing their task (Cook & Schwartz, 2002, p. 175). In the 1990s, approximately two dozen English-speaking archivists explored how contemporary academic ideas on archiving could influence its practice⁴² (Schwartz & Cook, 2002, 10,11).

Around the same time, groups that did not see themselves adequately represented in mainstream archives, with women leading the way as the most marginalized group, successfully established their own archives claiming their part in history, through their own way of seeing themselves (Carter, 2006, pp. 231–232). A broad range of collections and archives curated by groups unified by self-defined communalities would later be subsumed in the name community archives. They are often community-based and community-led, and the result of active collection and creation, thus either inadvertently or intentionally not complying with archival standards. In the latter case, they challenge the existing process of making history by employing the term archive (Duranti & Franks, 2015, pp. 145–147).

3.4 Archives and Digitalization - the First Digital Archives

Digital text editing to prepare printed editions required highly specialized knowledge before the advent of the personal computer and the text editing program Microsoft Word in the early 1980s. The wish to address cross-disciplinary and cross-project challenges in the use of information technology and to share data independently from specific software systems spurred the need for a standardized text encoding language. This led to the foundation of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) (Thaller, 2017, pp. 6–10). National and international associations promoting and supporting digital research and teaching across arts and humanities disciplines were founded in the Global North that united under the umbrella organization Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO) in 1989, representing a broad concept of cross-disciplinary thinking and practice encompassing various ways of applying digital methods in research in the humanities (ADHO, 2022).

Many archives and libraries launched projects to digitize portions of their holdings

⁴² A list of these authors and their articles can be found in footnote 17 in Schwartz & Cook, 2002, 10,11.

in the 1980s. In 1989, the large-scale digital reformatting project of the Archivo General de Indias (AGI)⁴³ (Gobierno de España, 2022) in Seville claimed the greatest variety of achievements worldwide: Eleven million pages were available for direct on-screen consultation, supported by image-enhancing tools, complemented by descriptive information available electronically through a unified data system that integrated all traditional finding aids. The digitized documents can be accessed online.

The public launch of the World Wide Web (WWW) in 1993 provided new ways for text exchange and display through webpages linked to each other via hyperlinks. The possibility to display graphics was modest in the beginning but rapidly and constantly improved with evolving technology. In 1994, anticipating future developments, Jacques Derrida once again focused the Humanities on re-evaluating the notion of the archive. He laid out the connection he saw between archives, memory, and the concepts of Freudian psychoanalysis, making the theory of psychoanalysis a theory of the archive. He raised the question of the future of archives, against the backdrop of modern technologies which do not merely store content but actively structure archives and influence human memory (Derrida, 1995). These reflections and the experience of the impact of the rapidly evolving new possibilities sparked a resurgence of the academic discussion of the archive.

The WWW spawned entirely new concepts of data exhibition and access combining features of libraries, encyclopedias, collections, and archives. Some trendsetting examples which expanded the traditional notion of archives and are still online nowadays include the following:

- In 1995, Ward Cunningham put the WikiWikiWeb online, a user-editable website operated by the Wiki software, to make the exchange of ideas between programmers easier. Dozens of similar wiki engines were designed and there are innumerable public or internal Wikis nowadays (Wikipedia, 2022c). The largest⁴⁴ is Wikipedia, a crowd-sourced online encyclopedia written and maintained by a community of volunteers, launched in 2001 by Jimmy Wales and Larry Sanger.
- In 1996, Brewster Kahle founded the Internet Archive with the mission to provide universal access to all knowledge, using web crawlers to preserve as much of the public web as possible. Kahle and Bruce Gilliat developed the Wayback Machine that since

⁴³ The AGI a massive repository of official documents produced by the Spanish government for the administration of the Spanish Empire's overseas territories in the Americas and Asia.

⁴⁴ On 29, April 2022 Wikipedia had 55,680,027 pages. Wikipedia, 2022b Initially available only in English, it has 326 language editions in 2022 (Wikipedia, 2022c).

2001 allows users to download and upload websites. The non-profit organization defines itself as an archive as well as a library and is funded through donations, grants, and by providing web archiving and book digitization services for its partners through Archive-It, founded in 2006. Archive-It allows institutions and individuals to create their specific digital archives. Millions of books, movies, audio, and TV content, as well as software, are accessible (Internet Archive, 2022).

- Also in 1996, the artist Kenneth Goldsmith launched the shadow library UbuWeb, an online database originally intended to post hard-to-find works of concrete poetry. Although most of the material posted on the website openly violates copyright norms, UbuWeb has never been sued. It grew into an essential archive providing thousands of freely downloadable avant-garde artifacts including among others writing, sound, video, comics, and ethnopoetics. UbuWeb is based on the ideas of gift economy and folk practice and is purposely fragmented, biased, subjective, and incomplete (Goldsmith, 2012; Goldsmith, 2020a; Goldsmith, 2020b).

Two pioneer digital projects with scholarly archival aspirations set benchmarks and are still operating and evolving:

- The Women Writers Project grew out of early modern women's studies, aiming at reclaiming the cultural importance of early women's writing. It was founded at Brown University in the USA in the late 1980s. Electronic text encoding was used as a method of bringing previously inaccessible texts back into use, preserving them in the long term. The project substantially contributed to establishing the TEI Guidelines. In 1999 Women Writers Online was published which made the collection available electronically (Women's Writers Project, 2022).
- The Blake Archive was conceived to provide unified access to major works of the disparate visual and literary art of William Blake, the physical originals of which being widely dispersed. Initially supported by the Institute for Advanced Technology in the Humanities (IATH) the project went online in 1996, and constantly adapted and refined the most advanced technologies for the digitization of drawings and paintings. Both projects required considerable funding proportionate to their size and were only possible through respective grants.

The possibility to access ever more information remotely not only changed everyday life but had a huge impact on the working mode in academics. Goldsmith supposed the paradigmatic truism in 2005 was that what didn't exist on the internet, didn't exist. However, international databases that contained most of the world's scientific articles

were only available to students and researchers affiliated with universities that had paid to access them. Goldsmith demanded free and unfettered access for everyone (Goldsmith, 2005). Less privileged students worldwide began to aggregate *shadow libraries*, small online collections of unauthorized digital copies of books and articles, in the early 2000s, some of which grew into larger, curated archives. The largest to date is Sci-Hub⁴⁵, launched in 2011 by Aleksandra Elbakyan, challenging the restriction of access to research papers and other scientific or educational sources by copyright laws (Karaganis, 2018a, p. 1).⁴⁶

3.5 Archives in the 21st Century

The first two decades of the 21st century brought about substantial progress in the digital world. The development of ever more efficient hardware, the expansion of web traffic, the introduction and meanwhile ubiquitous use of mobile devices, and the arrival and growth of social media, created an ever-growing amount of unstructured and semi-structured data⁴⁷. Traditional data analysis based on techniques for the handling of relational databases transformed into *Big Data*: A whole range of software for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers was developed to handle these new data types with wide-ranging implications for businesses, government, science and humanities that affect everyday life and societies as a whole. This theme would merit a chapter of its own but exceeds the scope of this project.

This development influenced, as Derrida predicted, not only the technical aspect of data storage but the whole concept of memory and archiving. With growing data storage capacities and lower costs, the previously unfeasible aspiration of keeping all data and abandoning selection (Bell, 1975, p. 48) is yet again topical and discussed in all fields. However, Yeo predicted that even though largescale retention would become a universal professional practice, human input would remain necessary, focusing on high-level aspects of curation, to guarantee the usability and re-usability of the data, and the trustworthiness of the holdings (Yeo, 2019).

⁴⁵ SciHub provides access to more than 84 million of research papers as of May 2022. Sci-Hub.

⁴⁶ “Shadow Libraries: Access to Knowledge in Global Higher Education” gives an overview of the international development of shadow libraries. Karaganis, 2018b

⁴⁷ According to the International Data Cooperation’s (IDC) findings, in 2020, 64.2 ZettaByte (ZB) of data was created or replicated, 98 percent of which were for the purpose of consumption, and less than two percent saved. The IDC forecasts a compound annual growth rate of global data creation and replication of 23 percent over the 2020-2025 period (80 percent of which will be unstructured), driving the growth of the Global StorageSphere which reached a capacity of 6.7 ZB in 2020 (Rydning & Shirer, 2021).

Next to preserving born-digital records, large archives digitize analog material for conservational purposes, to facilitate access to frequently requested items, or to focus on specific contents. Despite ongoing digitization programs in the larger archives, it has not been possible to digitize the huge mass of records stored, only parts of the material are digitized, and an even smaller part is accessible online.⁴⁸ The U.S. National Archives and Records Administration still applies the low-cost, low-tech, reliable, standardized, microfilm technology⁴⁹ to records for long-term storage as well. It is particularly justified to prevent wear and tear in frequently referenced valuable records in non-digitized holdings (NARA, 2017).

The selection of the records to be digitized and made accessible online due to financial restraints is a current demonstration of how the workings of an archive are influenced by the prevalent societal and academic discourse. The German *Bundesarchiv* recently published the complete digitized version of the records of the *Reichskolonialamt*, which controlled the administration of the German colonies, as a contribution to accounting for the past (Bundesarchiv, 2018).

The WWW became a massive number of dynamic digital archives in the sense of stored information. It unlocked the potential to actively create new sorts of archives. Individuals archive digital content and present their personal selections of whatever they choose on social media or websites. Easily manageable online content management systems allow private and public institutions to assemble collections and build online archives.⁵⁰ The visual and functional design developed significantly in recent years and influenced the form of presentation which shifted from textual to visual and audio communication.

In the online Open History Archive, Ruggeri collected a range of digital history projects using novel narrative formats conceived for online users that are dominated by visual communication. He points out that the interdependent influence of content and multimedia representation that is possible in online digital archives is a new field of research. He considers the archive a source for research about ways to rethink the communication of history in the Information Age (2019, p. 17; 2022).

⁴⁸ This holds true for all memory institutions. For example, the most recent European data from the ENUMERATE survey in 2017 on the state of digitization in memory institutions stated that a median value of 10% of analogue heritage collections has been digitally reproduced by then. Nauta, van den Heuvel, & Teunisse, 2017, p. 28.

⁴⁹ Microfilm images have an estimated life-expectancy of hundreds of years.

⁵⁰ A search engine quest for guides to digitization of archives and collections will yield numerous results with precise directions how to proceed.

In the last twenty years, a generation of academics across the humanities investigated archives by deconstructing the modes of their creation. Drawing on postcolonial, feminist, and intersectional approaches, often applying digital methods, they produced a plethora of research unveiling information previously hidden or present in its absence. For example, the authors of a collection of essays published by Walsham in 2016 applied a methodology called reading ‘along the archival grain’ by Stoler to historic archives, turning traditional approaches and investigating the process rather than the product. They considered the process of record creation and preservation, paid attention to the materiality of the objects, and regarded the history of records and archives, the methods and sites of knowledge making, thereby revealing how the archive is not merely a source but itself part of history (Walsham, 2016, 45, 10).

The archival profession as represented by the ICA embraced the contemporary mindset and defines archives as “the documentary by-product of human activity retained for their long-term value” that are of value to society as a trusted resource because they are as authentic, reliable, complete, and usable as possible. Archives can’t be regarded as whatever ‘truth’, “only as a contemporaneous record from an individual or organization with a particular level of involvement and point of view”. The users’ own experiences and culture affect their interpretation of an archival resource (International Council on Archives, 2016). Uncounted articles in professional journals⁵¹ document an ongoing lively and diverse discussion among archival scientists and practitioners about the key issue of appraisal against the backdrop of the current academic and social attitude regarding archives and the rapidly evolving information technologies.

3.6 Archives and Access

According to the Universal Declaration on Archives⁵², “open access to archives enriches our knowledge of human society, promotes democracy, protects citizens’ rights,

⁵¹- *The American Archivist*, a peer-reviewed, online journal, the leading international publication in the archives field, published semi-annually in English by the Society of American Archivists

- *Archivaria*, *The Journal of the Association of Canadian Archivists*, online journal, two issues per year, most recent two issues with embargoed access via account, primarily English, but also French, all articles with English and French abstracts, main publisher of translations of seminal non-English language articles

- *Archival Science*, International Journal on Recorded Information, Springer, English, promotes the development of archival science as an autonomous scientific discipline, four issues per year, most articles either open access or accessible via institutional login

- *Archives and Manuscripts*, Australian Society of Archivists, published by Taylor & Francis, English, peer-reviewed articles, reviews, and information about the theory and practice of archives and recordkeeping worldwide, three issues per year, most articles either open access or accessible via institutional login

- national associations in various countries have publications for members only

⁵² The declaration was adopted by ICA in 2010 and endorsed by UNESCO in 2011.

and enhances the quality of life” (ICA, 2010). Paradoxically, this aspiration was at the same time facilitated as it was restricted in the digital environment of the information society. Memory institutions navigate a narrow path between adhering to Intellectual Property laws and guaranteeing access to the Public Domain. The Public Domain covers works on which copyright protection has expired⁵³ and the essential commons of information that is not covered by copyright⁵⁴.

Copyright is part of Intellectual Property⁵⁵ laws. Minimum standards for copyright protection for works of authors, musicians, poets, painters, etc., are automatic without mandatory registration in all states party to the *Berne Convention*⁵⁶ adopted in 1886 (WIPO, 1971). The *Rome Convention*⁵⁷ entered into force in 1964 and secured protection for performers, producers of phonograms, and broadcasting organizations (UN, 1964). In 1967, the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) was established to lead the development of a balanced and effective international IP system. The digital age enabled faster and easier copying of IP, thereby enormously expanding the field of IP rights. WIPO addressed these challenges with the so-called *Internet treaties*⁵⁸ WCT and WPPT.

Although the Internet treaties secure rights for creators, they infringe on the open access to archives, as Dryden argued in his demand for copyright exceptions to the Internet treaties for archives. He laid out in detail why archives need these exceptions in the areas of preservation, cross-border uses, reproduction for research, orphan works, limited liability, technological protection measures, and contractual override of exceptions. Although the issue has been discussed in WIPO since 2011 there is no solution on the horizon yet and archivists continue to advocate for a treaty to establish these exceptions to allow archives, libraries, and museums to fulfill their public duties (Dryden, 2017).

Cox argued that even if digitizing documents of questionable ownership opened

⁵³ This varies per country, e.g., in most of Europe, copyright for a work lasts for 70 years after the death of its longest living creator.

⁵⁴ The essential commons are regarded as too important for the functioning of societies to be legally restricted even for a limited period, as e.g., laws, and judicial and administrative decisions.

⁵⁵ IP refers to “creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce (...) [and] is protected in law by, for example, patents, copyright and trademarks”. WIPO, 2022a.

⁵⁶ Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, last update in 1971, several amendments, 181 parties in 2022.

⁵⁷ Rome Convention for the Protection of Performers, Producers of Phonograms and Broadcasting Organizations, 96 parties in 2022.

⁵⁸ The WIPO Copyright Treaty (WCT) deals with protection for authors of literary and artistic works, musical works, audiovisual works, works of fine art and photographs, computer programs, and original databases. The WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty (WPPT) deals with the rights of performers, and producers of phonograms 1996. The treaties entered into force in 2002 and have 112 (WCT) and 111 (WPPT) contracting partners WIPO, 2022b.

more powerfully archival collections for scholarly and public use it could result in legal quagmires for archives. However, digitizing only documents with clear institutional ownership would result in ignoring vast amounts of important archival evidence. He encouraged archivists not only to become more proficient technically but also to enhance their knowledge of copyright to tackle these issues (2018, p. 227). Whatever is published on the internet needs to be in the public domain or be covered by the permission of the copyright owner to be displayed⁵⁹. Because of this restriction most of the items that are accessible in digital archives date from past centuries, the most recent from the early 20th century.

4. Practical Project, Methodology

The general overview showed that what an archive is or represents depends on who archives what, under which conditions and circumstances, for which purpose, at what time, at which location, and by what method. The practical project's goal is to prepare information on the congress by using digital methods and preserve it in a way that it is possible to use digital methods to analyze it.

4.1 List of Tools, Software, and Websites

- Anaconda Environment Interface, version 4.9.2 (Anaconda, Inc., 2022)
- Google Speech Recognition Tool in YouTube (Google)
- Microsoft Office Word and Excel, version 2207 (Microsoft, 2022)
- Notebook Interface JupyterLab, version 1.2.6 (Jupyter, 2022)
- OxGarage Conversion, version 3.1.0 (Rahtz, 2020)
- Oxygen XML Editor, version 23.1 (Syncro Soft SRL, 2022)
- Pandas - Python Data Analysis Library, version 1.3.5 (Reback et al., 2021)
- Python programming language, version 3.7.6 (Python Software Foundation, 2022)
- Roma, ODD Customization Tool, version 0.3.1 (Mittelbach & Rahtz, 2022)
- TEI by Example Tutorials (TBE project team, 2020)

⁵⁹ For example, with Creative Commons (CC) licenses: licenses or agreements which copyright owners voluntarily place on their online content to simplify rights permissions for them and provide greater access to their online content.

- TEI Text Encoding Initiative P5 Guidelines (TEI Technical Council Members, 2007)

4.2 List of Data

The author registered as a researcher at the PET Archives and was provided with the material by the archive.

- *Planned Environment Therapy Trust Archive and Study Centre, Material given by Dr. Joseph Berke, 1995.8/1 Archives of the Institute of Phenomenological Studies, Initial List*, PP-JB-IPS.docx (PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021)
- *1995.8/1, Institute of Phenomenological Studies Archives, Reel to Reel Tape Recordings, Initial List*, PP-JB-IPS_Tapes.docx (PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021)
- *TAPE TRANSFER LOG, PETT FOLDER 1.txt* (PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021)
- Digital audio files of the magnetic tapes containing audio recordings made at the congress, numbers
1_1_21, 1_2_12, 1_2_18, 1_2_19, 1_2_20, 1_2_24, 1_2_26, 1_2_29, 1_2_30,
1_3_15, 1_3_16, 1_3_23, 1_3_25, 1_4_04, 1_4_10, 1_4_17, 1_4_28, 1_4_34,
1_4_35, 1_4_42, 1_4_43, 1_4_44, 1_4_46, 1_4_48, 1_4_49, 1_4_50
(PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021)

4.3 Analysis of Inventory Lists of Berke's Estate at the PET Archives

The project is based on material related to the congress in the estate of Joseph Berke held by the PET Archives. Conforming to archival standards, the archive keeps the material in the form and order it was received. The boxes and storage case holders contain material related to the Institute of Phenomenological studies, which is partially related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress. It can be accessed onsite upon request. The paper material has not been digitized, and the archive has only limited resources to provide copies, making remote research on individual items impossible. However, the archive created lists documenting the contents of the boxes and folders. Copies of these lists allow for remote research on the level of metadata.

The first step was to study the inventory lists provided by the archive and determine the content related to the congress. According to the *Archives of the Institute of*

*Phenomenological Studies, Initial List, PP-JB-IPS.docx*⁶⁰ (*PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021*), the archive holds copies of 14 of the 23 LPs, photographs, 23 folders with transcripts, copies of the advertising material for the congress as well as reports, four storage case holders with correspondence related to the congress sorted by alphabet, and one with correspondence regarding the records, film, publicity, etc., a Danish, Swedish, Brazilian and Japanese edition with transcripts of speeches held at the congress and films, and a manila envelope with royalty and bank statements, most probably related to the books and LPs. This material would have to be studied on-site and could certainly provide valuable information on the preparation and aftermath of the congress.

The *Reel-to-Reel tape recordings, Initial list, PP-JB-IPS_Tapes.doc*⁶¹ (*PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021*) provides the information written on the tape boxes. Most of the tapes were recorded at the congress, some on other occasions. The archivists added accession numbers and information on the physical condition of the tapes. The magnetic tapes were digitized by the archive to preserve them. The digitization was documented in the *Tape Transfer Log, PETT FOLDER 1.txt*⁶² (*PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021*).

The list of tape recordings and the transfer log document were deemed potentially useful in providing more detailed information by using Pandas, a Python library for data analysis. For this purpose, the information in the text documents needed to be transferred to a tabular format. Pandas is based on data frames, a two-dimensional tabular data structure with labeled rows and columns and potentially heterogeneous cell content.

4.3.1 Documentation of the Analysis

The *Reel-to-Reel tape recordings, Initial list, PP-JB-IPS_Tapes.doc* contains a varying amount of data provided for each tape. Table 1 gives two examples in a formatted version.

Table 1: Examples for Entries in Reel-to-Reel Tape Recordings, Initial List; PP-JB-IPS-tapes.doc

<i>accession number</i>	<i>Reel size</i>	<i>Tape length</i>	<i>Tape material</i>	<i>Manufacturer/make</i>	<i>Condition</i>
2.12	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	very furry
	7 1/2 IPS, Master, Congress, Stokely Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July 1967, 370 m, Tracks II & IV - Carmichael continue, - total length of speech 62 min, track 2 white - 370 in - Stokely Car, or 100 back from red []				
4.43	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	some spots

⁶⁰ A processed version of this list containing the entries related to the congress is available in Annex A.

⁶¹ A processed version of this list containing the entries related to the congress is available in Annex B.

⁶² A processed version of this list containing the entries related to the congress is available in Annex C.

[Mono] 7 1/2 ips, Congress July 18th Master, Stokeley Carmichael, John Gerassi, C.L.R. James, George Rawick, David Cooper, Panel Discussion - Afternoon, Track I First Half Discussion, Track III Last part of Discussion

There is technical information about the magnetic tapes, the content of the recordings, transcripts made from the recordings, the duration of the tape, etc. The information was transferred to an excel file, split up into 27 columns representing a range of information that can be logged separately for each tape to make it potentially extractable and sortable and thereby useful for analysis with digital tools (*pre_tapes_analysis.xlsx*)⁶³:

tape_box, accession_number, reel_size_in_inches, tape_length_in_feet, tape_speed_in_inches_per_second_ips, tape_material, manufacturer_make, condition, text, duration, DL_record_number_and_side, Master, letters_for_tapes, matching, not_used, speaker_A, speaker_B, speaker_C, speaker_D, speaker_E, title, date, time, time_word, language, duplicate, transcription.

Each of the 121 rows has an index number and represents one tape. For this project, the focus is on the events Carmichael participated in. The goal of the analysis is to create a sorted set of the audio files featuring Carmichael.

The following section is a documentation of the analysis of the pandas dataframes. It can be read separately or in parallel or additionally to the jupyter notebooks.⁶⁴ For easier handling and reference, the code was split up into several notebooks. Each step of the processing is coded in a separate cell. This approach was deliberately chosen to make the steps of the analysis transparent and comprehensible. The code is commented, and the result of every step can be conveniently displayed by removing the # in the *#display* of the cells in the notebook. The code in the notebooks for the greatest part conforms to the PEP 8 style guide. However, for traceability of the process, the names of the files are very long. A table with the results of the analysis is presented in the results chapter.

- The excel file was converted to the csv file *pre_tapes_analysis.csv*, uploaded into a pandas dataframe in the ipynb notebook *tapes_analysis.ipynb*, cleared of alterations due to that process and saved for further analysis as *tapes_analysis.csv*
- A subset of 26 tapes featuring Carmichael was created by selecting the rows that include Carmichael in one of the *speaker* columns. According to cross reference with info from album sleeves (discogs) Carmichael is featured on the LP numbers 6, 7, 13, and 14. Since the rows with record numbers 13 and 14 in the *DL_records_and_sides* column don't have Carmichael's name in one of the *speaker* columns, they were added to the set.

⁶³ If useful in a different context, the number of columns could be extended for an even more detailed analysis, e.g., by adding a column listing the tracks.

⁶⁴ All the files and notebooks are saved in the folder Naumann_Masterarbeit_pandas_ipynb_csv_xlsx.

Some rows have values in the *date* and *time* values, some don't, some have values in the *time_word* column, some don't. This dataframe was sorted by the *date* column and saved as *df_SC_date.csv*.

- The next step was to select the subset of tapes dated 1967-07-18 and save it as *df_SC_1967_07_18.csv*. From this set two subsets were created, one with the value *afternoon* in the *time_word* column and one with no value in the column. The rows were re-indexed to their index from the original dataframe and saved as *df_SC_1967_07_18_afternoon.csv* and *df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon.csv*. A subset for the rows dated 1967-07-22 was created, it contains the tapes with the values 13 and 14 in the *DL_records_and_sides* column which were added to the file name *df_SC_1967_07_22_DL_13_14.csv*. A subset for the rows dated 1967-07-23 in the *date* column was created and saved as *df_SC_1967_07_23.csv*. At last, the rows with no value in the *date* column were grouped, sorted by the value of the numbers in the *DL_records_and_sides* column and saved as *df_SC_not_dated.csv*.

The *Tape Transfer Log*, (PETT FOLDER 1.txt), written in upper case letters, was converted from txt file to docx file (PETT_FOLDER_1.docx). Sorted by the original accession number prefixed by the box number it lists remarks on the processing of the audio tapes before digitization. The info related to the audio tapes of the congress was changed to lower case letters while capitalizing names and thus prepared to add to the dataframes.

Separate notebooks were created to add the information from the *Tape Transfer Log* to the dataframes saved in the previous process.

- The file *df_SC_1967_07_18_afternoon.csv* was uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_18_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.ipynb*. A new column was added to hold the information on the digitization process from the tape transfer log and the dataframe was saved as *df_SC_1967_07_18_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*.

- The file *df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon.csv* was uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.ipynb*. A new column was added to hold the information on the digitization process from the tape transfer log. The dataframe was saved as *df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*.

- The file *df_SC_1967_07_22_DL_13_14.csv* was uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_22_DL_13_14_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.ipynb*. A new column was

added to hold the information on the digitization process from the tape transfer log and the dataframe saved as *df_SC_1967_07_22_DL_13_14_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*.

- The file *df_SC_1967_07_23.csv* was uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_23_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.ipynb*. A new column was added to hold the information on the digitization process from the tape transfer log and the dataframe saved as *df_SC_1967_07_23_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*.

- The four tapes listed in the file *df_SC_not_dated.csv* without any dates in the *date* column have the values 6 and 7 in the *DL_records_and_sides* column. By cross-referencing the information from the other columns, the DL records 6 A and 6 B could be associated with the set of July 18, not afternoon and the DL records 7 A and 7 B with the set of July 23. The file *df_SC_not_dated.csv* was uploaded to the notebook *df_SC_DL_6_7_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.ipynb*. A new column was added to hold the information on the digitization process from the tape transfer log and the dataframe saved as *df_SC_DL_6_7_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*.

- The two dataframes *df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv* and *df_SC_DL_6_7_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv* were uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_DL_6_added_PETT_FOLDER_1.ipynb*. The rows with the value 6 in the *DL_records_and_time* column were added to the first dataframe which was saved as

df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_DL_6_added_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv

- The two dataframes *df_SC_1967_07_23_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv* and *df_SC_DL_6_7_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv* were uploaded to the notebook *SC_1967_07_23_DL_7_added_PETT_FOLDER_1.ipynb*. The rows with the value 7 in the *DL_records_and_time* column were added to the first dataframe which was saved as

df_SC_1967_07_23_DL_7_added_PETT_FOLDER_1.csv

- In the last notebook *Sets_SC.ipynb* the four subsets *df_SC_1967_07_18_not_afternoon_DL_6_added_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv* and *df_SC_1967_07_18_afternoon_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv*

df_SC_1967_07_22_DL_13_14_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv

df_SC_1967_07_23_DL_7_added_PETT_FOLDER_1_added.csv

were uploaded and combined in one dataframe, the columns necessary for the further analysis in this project chosen and renamed, and the dataframe saved as

tei_set_Stokely_Carmichael.csv

4.4 TEI XML Encoding of Information about the Congress

The goal of this part of the practical project was to encode information on Carmichael's contribution to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress, based on research results from a preliminary project, the audio files, transcripts of audio files, and research results from the analysis of the inventory lists of Berke's Estate at the PET Archives.

The encoding should

- a. archive the research results
- b. make the encoded information easily retrievable
- c. offer a wide variety of representation and additional information
- d. allow for further encoding by the author or other researchers with other interests
- e. allow for extension and diversification
- f. make the transcripts comparable from a perspective of cultural science

The TEI XML format seemed ideal for the purpose.

4.4.1 TEI XML

XML stands for Extensible Markup Language. In the most general definition, a markup language is metadata used to annotate a document and is both human- and machine-readable. XML is software- and hardware-independent and used for storing and transporting data. It provides mechanisms for defining the grammatical structures of specified encoding languages, including the *P5 Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange* (TEI Technical Council Members, 2007). These guidelines are released by the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), a consortium that collectively develops and maintains a standard of encoding methods for texts in the humanities, social sciences, and linguistics that are at the same time human- and machine-readable. The information encoded following these guidelines is at the same time preserved and easy to retrieve and

present, for example for online research or teaching. XML and thus TEI⁶⁵ are organized in a hierarchical tree structure. The information is encoded within start and end tags of elements that can be nested within each other and specified by attributes. There are currently 584 elements grouped in 124 model classes, 268 attributes grouped in 81 attribute classes, and 34 specified datatypes. Classes can refer to other classes making it possible to create hierarchies of element and attribute groups sharing some features while others are specific to what subclass the groups belong to. Model classes that frequently co-occur are grouped into macros, logical groups of elements that can occur in the same hierarchical context in a TEI document. The highly modular system is extensible and allows for the creation of new elements and attributes. The P5 Guidelines present groups of related elements (for use in a specific application area, or to support a particular kind of usage) and their declarations in so-called modules.

4.4.2 ODD

No project will need all elements and attributes, making it necessary to develop a customized TEI schema. A TEI schema limits the choice of elements and attributes and their functionalities to the desired range. This makes sure that the encoding is consistent even if done by different people and the margin of errors is limited. The schema is defined in a TEI-conformant XML document, an ODD (One Document Does it all), with the help of 22 TEI documentation elements and respective attributes. The customization process can include different kinds of modifications such as the addition and deletion of elements, the modification of content models, the modification of attribute and attribute-value lists, the modification of class membership, and the creation of entirely new elements and attributes. From the customized ODD a formal representation of the elements and attributes expected in the document can be expressed in a schema language like e.g., RELAX NG and associated with the XML document to validate the encoding (TEI Consortium, 2022).

4.4.3 Roma ODD Customization Tool

The Roma ODD customization tool (beta version) is a web application that was designed to help navigate the complex TEI system and create TEI customizations without having to write the XML code. It provides an interface to pick and choose elements, attribute classes, model classes, and datatypes and modify them, starting from pre-defined

⁶⁵ *TEI* is often used as reference to the language defined in the TEI P5 guidelines.

templates. The customization can be downloaded in several formats. Previously saved ODD customizations can be uploaded and changed (Mittelbach & Rahtz, 2022).

4.4.4 Schematron

Constraints on the content of the XML document that cannot be expressed in the TEI language can be expressed with the Schematron language, a rule-based language that uses path expressions to make assertions applied to a specific context within the document. The author of the rules supplies a diagnostic message that is supplied if the assertion fails to help correct the encoding mistake. The element `<constraintSpec>` can be used in the ODD to express these additional rules in TEI language. The `@scheme` attribute records that the notation in which the rules are expressed is Schematron.

4.4.5 OxGarage Conversion

OxGarage is a web service provided by the TEI to transform documents between a variety of formats. After selecting the type of the document one wants to convert the tool presents a choice of formats it can be converted to. The TEI format is used as a pivot format for the majority of the conversions.

4.4.6 Oxygen XML Editor

The editor provides an interface with many options to facilitate the editing and formatting of the XML documents. It checks if the document is well-formed, conforming to the XML syntax rules, and validates XML documents, for example against RNG schemas that may contain embedded Schematron rules. It is a very helpful tool that during the process of encoding suggests lists of valid elements and attributes as specified in the schema.

4.4.7 Transcription of Audio Files

The process was an explorative one, starting with the results of the analysis of the lists at the archive, the audio files, and the transcript of one audio file. As a part of a preliminary research project, the author had identified audio file 1_2_24 as containing a large part of the event that was organized for the Black community but lacking the end. Audio file 1_2_12, about one hour of audio recordings, containing Carmichael's and some other speaker's speeches starting at some point in the event, had been transcribed. Audio file 1_2_24 contains the beginning of the event.

The first step in this part of the project was thus to transcribe the about two hours of recording from audio file 1_2_24 that are not contained in audio file 1_2_12. The audio file had been transformed from mp3 audio format to mp4 video format for the previous project. The mp4 video file was uploaded to a private YouTube channel and the automatically created transcript in lower case letters was proofread and downloaded as txt file. In the process of the creation of the TEI schemata and XML files and the alignment of audio recordings and transcripts, the missing part was identified on audio file 1_1_21, transcribed, and added to the transcript.

4.4.8 Process of TEI Encoding

The following paragraph gives a summary of the highly explorative process of the TEI schema specification and encoding. The first step was a basic encoding of persons and places by creating separate schemata for a list of names and a list of places. These first schemata were created with the Roma tool. They were associated with an XML file and the first encoding was done by reading the transcript in the XML file and adding a few names and places to the XML documents for the persons and places. In an iterative back and forth between the XML document, the Roma tool, the P5 guidelines, and the TEI by Example website the architecture of the set of schemata, XML lists, and the choice of elements and attributes evolved. Schemata were created, downloaded, associated with the XML document, and tested, then re-uploaded to the Roma tool and changed or discarded. Different encoding strategies were applied by either adding to or deleting from prefabricated schemes. Because the tool has quite a few bugs and often crashed it was finally decided to create the ODDs manually. Some of the element specifications were copied from the different test ODDs that had been created along the way, others were created according to these templates or from scratch. The direct coding in the ODD document makes it possible to add formal constraints, expressed in the Schematron language, which is not possible with the Roma tool. The ODD documents were converted to RNG documents with the OxGarage tool and then associated with the corresponding XML documents. The explorative, iterative process brought forth new research results which during the process were used to expand the set of schemata and lists and complete the transcript for one event. ⁶⁶

⁶⁶ All the ODD, RNG and XML files are in the folder Naumann_Masterarbeit_TEI_xml_odd_rng.

5. Results

5.1 Results Analysis of Inventory Lists

The next four tables represent all the rows but only the major columns that contain all the information. In the much larger original dataframe which can be studied in the notebook *Set_SC.ipynb* this information is spread into columns to make comparison easier. The index number is the number assigned to the tapes in the table *tapes_analysis.csv* created by the author from the *PP-JB-IPS_Tapes.docx*. The accession number is the number on the magnetic tapes at the PET archive. The column *List_Magnetic_Tape_Recordings* contains the description of each tape in the *PP-JB-IPS_Tapes.docx*. The column *Digitization_Tape_Transfer_Log* contains the information regarding the digitization of the respective tape in the *PETT_FOLDER_1.txt*. If no information was provided it could mean that the tapes did not need any special treatment before digitization. *No information in file/tape not used for printing record* was added by the author to otherwise empty cells for clarity.

Table 2: Audio Recordings 18 July 1967, morning

Date	Index	accession number	List_Magnetic_Tape_Recordings	Digitization_Tape_Transfer_Log	Record_number_and_side
1967_07_18 _not afternoon	85	4_10	Congress July 18th (3 3/4), Stokely Carmichael, Public Address & Floor Questions & Press Conference, Tracks 1 & 2, (transcription), (transcribed ASD)	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	103	4_34	Mono 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 18th, Stokeley Carmichael, Public Address, Tracks 1 & 3, Track 1 First Half of Address (white) 32 minutes, Track 3 Questions from floor (red)	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	104	4_35	Mono 7 1/2 IPS, Carmichael, 18 July, Questions 1083, NOT USED, Bob Woolford Sound	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	111	4_42	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 18th Master, Stokely Carmichael, Public Address, Tracks 2 & 4, Track 2 Second half of public address & beginning of floor questions, Track 4 Last part of floor questions and press conference	1.4.42 Stokley Carmichael Congress 1967.07.18 public address Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques tail out 19 cm/sec iec equalisation, half track mono good output Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 'track 2: second half of public address and beginning of floor questions track 4: last part of floor questions and press conference Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	tape not used for printing record
	46	3_16	Intersound Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - To Congress - DL6 - Side A, (1050') Duration 28 mins – secs, Start Yellow Leader, No Scrolls, End Orange, 7 1/2 1/2 track	1.3.16 Stokely Carmichael to Congress DL6-side A 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono quarter inch open reel analogue tape Scotch 175 18 cm polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present removed dub excerpt from Carmichael master Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	6, A
	45	3_15	Intersound Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - To Congress - DL6 - Side B, (1150') Duration 30 mins 30 secs, Start Yellow, No Scroll, End Blue, 7 1/2 1/2 track	no information in file	6, B

Table 2 lists the six magnetic tapes with the accession numbers 4_10, 4_34, 4_35, 4_42, 3_16, 3_15 and the corresponding digital files 1_4_10, 1_4_34, 1_4_35, 1_4_42, 1_3_16, 1_3_15 related to the event on the morning of July 18, 1967.

Table 3: Audio Recordings 18 July 1967, afternoon

Date	Index	accession number	List_Magnetic_Tape_Recordings	Digitization_Tape_Transfer_Log	Record_number_and_side
1967_07_18 _afternoon	79	4_04	Congress July 18th (3 3/4), Stokeley Carmichael, Panel Discussion – Afternoon, Track I (track 2 blank), John Gerassi, CLR James, George Pavick [?], David Cooper, including 1 minute silence for John Coltrane, (transcription)	No information in file	tape not used for printing record
	112	4_43	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 18th Master, Stokeley Carmichael, John Gerassi, C.L.R. James, George Rawick, David Cooper, Panel Discussion – Afternoon, Track I First Half Discussion, Track III Last part of Discussion	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	113	4_44	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 18th Master, Stokely Carmichael, Panel Discussion – Afternoon, Track 2 Second Half of Discussion - not to the end, Track 4 blank	1.4.44 Stokley Carmichael Congress 1967.07.18 afternoon panel discussion Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques tail out 19 cm/sec iec equalisation, half track mono good output Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 violence, power and anti-power end as source this file is put into file 1.4.43 as I think it sits between the two files in there as a continuum of the programme. it does because the edit points exist Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	tape not used for printing record

Table 3 lists the three magnetic tapes with the accession numbers 4_04, 4_43, 4_44 and the corresponding digital files with the numbers 1_4_04, 1_4_43, 1_4_44 related to the event in the afternoon of July 18, 1967.

Table 4: Audio recordings 22 July 1967, 8 pm

Date	Index	accession number	List_Magnetic_Tape_Recordings	Digitization_Tape_Transfer_Log	Record_number_and_side
1967_07_22	102	4_28	Congress 3 ¾, Saturday July 22nd Transcription, 8 p.m., Laing/ Carmichael/ Ginsberg/ Cooper/ E. Brogan, Tracks 1 + 2, Transcribed	1.4.28 Laing, Carmichael, Ginsberg, Cooper, E Brogan Congress 1967.07.22 2000 HRS International Electronics polyester 360m open reel 8mm tape 1/2 track mono 9.5 cm/sec iec&nab equalisation required cleaning and leaders added good copy requiring editing of sides one and two together as one, required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, air sealed for 18 months with silica gel to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	tape not used for printing record
	34	2_30	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Congress Master, Saturday July 22, 8 p.m.,Laing/ Carmichael/ Ginsberg/ Cooper/ E. Grogan, Tracks I & 3	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	30	2_26	[Mono], I.P.S. 7 ½, Congress Master, Saturday July 22, 8 p.m., Laing/Carmichael/ Ginsberg/ Cooper/ E. Grogan, Tracks 2 & 4	1.2.29 Laing_Carmichael_Ginsberg_Cooper_E.Brogan 1967.07.22 2000 hrs Dialects of Liberation congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 1/2 track mono Scotch 175 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present track 5	tape not used for printing record
	33	2_29	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Congress Master, Saturday July 22, 8 p.m., Laing/ Carmichael/ Ginsberg/ Cooper/ E. Grogan, Track 5	1.2.26 Laing_Carmichael_Ginsberg_Cooper_E. Brogan 1967.07.22 2000 Hrs Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 1/2 track mono Scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present animated discussions, good audio	tape not used for printing record

	117	4_48	Intersound, Master, Title Saturday Night - DL13 Side A, 773' Duration 20 mins 40 secs., Start yellow, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track	1.4.48, Allen Ginsberg, Stokely Carmichael, Saturday Night DL13 side A contains chanting with accordion, Japanese, English, discussion 1967.07.22 Intersound recordings dub, 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono, Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, Stokely Carmichael, discussion: violence, cultural imposition, culture adoption, fight for cultural integrity, imposition of culture on the Third World, Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	13, A
	53	3_23	Intersound Master, Title Saturday Night DL13 Side B, Duration 28 mins - secs., Start Yellow, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track, level []	1.3.23, Saturday Night DL13 side B master from congress, two track stereo on quarter inch open reel, Scotch LP 150 18cm reel, iec1 equalisation (ccir) 19 cm/sec speed	13, B
	115	4_46	Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Saturday Night DL14 Side A, 1037 Duration 27 mins 40 secs., Start yellow, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track	1.4.46, Saturday night DL14 side A, R D Laing, Stokely Carmichael: demystification of violence, 19 cm/sec iec equalisation half track mono, Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, excerpt from Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967PETT_folder_1	14, A
	119	4_50	Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Saturday Night DL14 Side B, 1225 Duration 32 mins. 50 secs., Start yellow, no scroll, end blue, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track	1.4.50, Stokely Carmichael, Allen Ginsberg, Beck open discussion on individualism, Saturday Night DL 14 side B, Intersound recordings dub, 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono on 18 cm reel, Scotch 175 polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, return to self, suppressed and oppressed culture, police, Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	14, B

Table 4 lists the eight magnetic tapes with the accession numbers 4_28, 2_30, 2_26, 2_29, 4_48, 3_23, 4_46, 4_50 and the corresponding digital files with the numbers 1_4_28, 1_2_30, 1_2_26, 1_2_29, 1_4_48, 1_3_23, 1_4_46, 1_4_50 related to the event in the evening of July 22, 1967.

Table 5: Audio recordings 23 July 1967

Date	Index	accession_number	List_Magnetic_Tape_Recordings	Digitization_Tape_Transfer_Log	Record_number_and_side
1967_07_23	29	2_24	Congress 3 ¾, Stokely Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July, 1967, Tracks I + II (Transcribed)	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	91	4_17	7 1/2 IPS, MASTER, Stokley Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July, Track V, Carmichael questions began about 325 in	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	28	2_20	7 1/2 IPS, Master, Stokeley Carmichael Congress, Sunday 23rd July, Track I & III – red, - Carmichael continued, whole side	1.2.20 Stokely Carmichael, Roundhouse, Congress, London 1967.07.23 Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 2 track mono Scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present the predicament coloured people are in	tape not used for printing record
	27	2_19	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS, Carmichael, 23rd July, Questions II o564', Not Used, Bob Woolford Sound	1.2.19 Stokely Carmichael 1967.07.23 questions ii 12.5 cm reel full track mono 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present hippies, exploitation of minority groups	tape not used for printing record
	26	2_18	[Mono], 7 1/2 IPS Carmichael, 23rd July, Lecture III 0266', Ed-mundo des Noyes 073', Questions I 0636', Not used, Bob Woolford Sound	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	20	2_12	7 1/2 IPS, Master, Congress, Stokely Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July 1967, 370 m, Tracks II & IV - Carmichael continue - total length of speech 62 min, track 2 white - 370 in - Stokely Car or 100 back from red []	1.2.12 Stokely Carmichael 1967.07.23 (Sunday) congress master 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 2 track mono Scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present some writing undistinguishable in red ink on the box number 9 on plastic reel	tape not used for printing record
	9	1_21	Master Tape, Stokely Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July, Track 6, Changed for K', Carmichael questions - [], altogether about 20 mins	no information in file	tape not used for printing record
	118	4_49	Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - Black Community - DL7 - Side A, 1180 Duration 31 mins 20 secs, start yellow leader, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track	no information in file	7, A
	55	3_25	Intersound Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - Black Community - DL7 - Side B, (1215') Duration 32 mins 30 secs., Start White Leader, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 1/2 track	1.3.25 Stokely Carmichael Black Community DL7 Side B Intersound master 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, from 1/2 track mono 1215 feet of tape Scotch lp150 polyester Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967	7, B

Table 5 lists the nine magnetic tapes with the accession numbers 2_24, 4_17, 2_20, 2_19, 2_18, 2_12, 1_21, 4_49, 3_25 and the corresponding digital files with the numbers 1_2_24, 1_4_17, 1_2_20, 1_2_19, 1_2_18, 1_2_12, 1_1_21, 1_4_49, 1_3_25, related to the event on July 23, 1967.

The set of recordings related to the event on 23 July 1967 was exemplarily analyzed by examining the data with a rudimentary knowledge of analog recording techniques: Magnetic tapes were edited by physically cutting the recording tape, removing unwanted parts, and rejoining the tape with a so-called splicing tape. This adhesive tape was also used to identify the beginning and end of selections.

Tapes number 4_49 and 3_25 represent the tapes that were used to print the vinyl LP 7. The texts *start yellow leader, no scroll, end red* for 4_49 and *Start White Leader, No Scroll, End Red* for 3_25 most probably mark the beginning and the end of the speech to be printed on LP, indicating that the tape contains a preceding and following part. Six of the tapes seem to be parts of the event according to the information in the text reproduced here in brackets: 4_17 (...*Carmichael questions began about...*), 2_20 (...*Carmichael continued...*), 2_19 (...*Questions II...*), 2_20 (...*Lecture III...*), 2_12 (...*Carmichael continue...*), 1_21 (...*Carmichael questions...*). Tape 2_24 is the only tape that was recorded at a speed of 3.75 instead of 7.5 inches per second like the others, which indicates that it contains a longer part of the event. It runs for three hours, one of which was transcribed for a preceding project⁶⁷.

5.2 Results TEI XML Project

The final set of schemes in ODD and Relax NG format includes

1. a schema for the transcripts
2. a schema for the list of persons
3. a schema for the list of places
4. a schema for the list of organizations
5. a schema for the list of events
6. a schema for the list of audio recordings
7. a schema for the list of terms

The final set of TEI XML documents includes

1. an encoded transcript
2. an encoded list of persons

⁶⁷ Naumann, 2022.

3. an encoded list of places
4. an encoded list of organizations
5. an encoded list of events
6. an encoded list of audio recordings
7. an encoded list of terms

The following sections visualize the choice of elements and attributes in the XML documents defined by the ODD schemata. The elements and attributes are arranged in tables sorted by required and optional usage. This approach was chosen over the usage of yet another representation, e.g., the Unified Modeling Language(UML) which would only add another layer of abstraction. The actual encoding needs to be looked up in the XML documents. The same applies to the schema definitions in the ODD documents. The schema specification will be presented in short excerpts of code. The complete set of ODD and XML documents represents thousands of lines of code. It would be unreasonable to add them in printing. Besides, they are born-digital content which is meant to be applied digitally.

5.2.1 List of Persons

The XML document *List of Persons Related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress* (`dlc_list_persons.xml`) contains data of persons related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress in whatever way, e.g. organizing, contributing, participating, being mentioned in speeches, handling material related to the Congress, or others. Assuming that most of the persons are public figures the elements and attributes were chosen to provide on the one hand directly available information for humans reading the TEI XML document as well as a broad range of additional information that is optionally retrievable via machine reading. The schema was defined in the document *dlc_list_persons.odd*, converted to the document *dlc_list_persons.rng*, and associated with the XML document.

Table 6 below shows the permitted elements and attributes.

Table 6: Elements and Attributes allowed in Element <listPerson> in the List of Persons

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Additional Possible Elements		Possible Attributes	Possible Attribute Values
<pre> <listPerson> <person xml:id=""> <persName></persName> <sex value=""></sex> <birth> <date></date> <placeName></placeName> </birth> <death> <date></date> <placeName></placeName> </death> </person> </listPerson> </pre>	<pre> <persName> <addName/> <forename/> <genName/> <namelink/> <note/> <roleName/> <surname/> </persName> </pre>	<pre> <addName> <forename/> <surname/> <note/> </addName> </pre>	<pre> <forename type =”first”> <forename type =”mid- dle”> </pre>	<pre> <sex value =”f” <sex value =”m” <sex value =”d” </pre>
		<pre> <forename> <note/> </forename> <surname> <note/> </surname> </pre>	<pre> <persName from=” “> <persName to=” “> </pre>	
	<pre> <birth> <note/> </birth> <death> <note/> </death> </pre>	<pre> <date> <note/> </date> </pre>	<pre> <date when=” “notBefore= “ “ notAfter=” “source=” “/> </pre>	<pre> <idno type=”viaf”/> <idno type=”wiki- data”/> </pre>
	<pre> <idno/> </pre>	<pre> <placeName> <note/> </placeName> </pre>	<pre> <placeName key =”pl_000” source=” “/> </pre>	

Table 7: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <person> in the List of Persons

<pre><person xml:id="pe_000"> <persName>unidentified person </persName> <sex value="d"></sex> <birth> <date></date> <placeName></placeName> </birth> <death> <date></date> <placeName></placeName> </death> </person></pre>	<pre><persName> <forename type="first">Cyril</forename> <forename type="middle">Lionel</forename> <forename type="middle">Robert</forename> <surname>James</surname> </persName> <persName> <forename>Michael</forename> <surname>de Freitas</surname> <addName>Michael Abdul Malik</addName> <addName>Michael X</addName> </persName> <persName to="1969"> <forename>Stokely</forename> <surname>Carmichael</surname> </persName> <persName from="1969"> <forename>Kwame</forename> <surname>Ture</surname> </persName></pre>
<pre><date when="1940-04-21" source="https://www.snccllegacyproject.org/george- ware"/></pre>	<pre><placeName key="pl_0016" source="https://web.archive./web/20220708190421/ https://soundsfromthepark.on-the-record.org.uk/people/roy-sawh/">Guyana</placeName></pre>
<pre><date when="2003-07-27" source="wikidata"/></pre>	<pre><placeName key="pl_0014"/></pre>

Table 7 showcases a variety of alternative encodings that are all valid against the schema. The list of persons counts 64 persons after the encoding of the first transcript.

The schema provides that the XML editor allows only the element <person> within the element <listPerson>. The left column of Table 6 shows the pattern with the required elements and attributes. The attribute @xml:id provides a unique identifier for each person. The name of the person can be encoded individually by using one of the several possible elements. Names, sex, and dates of birth and death are listed in the respective elements. The forename can be additionally specified by using the attributes @first or @middle. If the person changed her name, there is the possibility to add a second <persName> element and differentiate with the attributes @to and @from. The <date> element for birth and death is specified by the @when attribute. The @source attribute provides the source for the date. It will in most cases, but not always, be Wikidata. In the case of approximate dates, the @notBefore and @notAfter attributes can be applied. The placename of birth and death is referred to by the attribute @key pointing to the respective element in the separate document *List of Places*. The element <note> can be added to most of the elements to provide additional information or remarks. If available, the VIAF and/or Wikidata identification numbers are provided in the element <idno> specified by the @type attribute. These numbers allow retrieving a multitude of additional information that could potentially be used for example in further research and for a website. VIAF files are single virtual authority files that link together identical records from different national authority files. A standard data number refers to the original authority records and provides users with convenient access to the world's major name authority files (OCLC). The free and open knowledge base Wikidata gives access to the structured data of all Wikimedia sister projects and provides a wealth of textual and visual information that can be accessed by machines. The name of the person can be specified by using a broad spectrum of elements if necessary. Most elements can, but do not have to contain text. The constraint specifications make sure that the @xml:id conforms to the pattern *pe_000*, that the @key conforms to the pattern *pl_0000*, and that there are no duplicate numbers in the <idno> elements.

This excerpt of the TEI XML code in the *dlc_list_persons.odd* shows how the attribute *first* is added to the value list in the @type attribute for the element <forename>:

```
<elementSpec id="forename" mode="change"> (...)</attList><attDef id="type" mode="change" usage="opt"><desc>defines whether the name is the first name or an additional forename when there is more than one forename</desc><valList type="closed" mode="change"><valItem mode="add" id="first"><desc>first name</desc> </valItem>( ... )</valList></attDef></attList></elementSpec>
```

5.2.2 List of Places

The schema *dlc_list_places.odd* is designed to validate a List of Places xml document (*dlc_list_places.xml*) that eventually will contain all the places related mentioned at the events at the congress as well as all the birth and death places of the persons in the *List of Persons*. The elements and attributes were chosen to provide a placename to the human reader and a multitude of information that is retrievable for further research. Each place has an ID and is specified by a type chosen from a closed list of types. The placename is complemented by geographical data as well as their identification numbers at the knowledge graph wikidata.org and the database geonames.org, if available.

Table 8: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the `<listPlace>` Element in the List of Places

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Additional Possible Elements	Possible Attributes	Possible Attribute Values, closed lists
<code><listPlace></code> <code><place xml:id="" type="" ></code> <code><placeName></placeName></code> <code><location></code> <code><geo></geo></code> <code></location></code> <code><idno type="wikidata"/></code> <code><idno type="geonames"/></code> <code></place></code> <code></listPlace></code>	<code><placeName></code> <code><settlement/></code> <code><country/></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><country/></code> <code><bloc/></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><country/></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><placeName></code> <code><bloc/></code> <code><placeName></code>	<code><location target="" /></code> <code><placeName from="" to="" /></code> <code><placeName from="" /></code> <code><placeName to="" /></code>	<code><place type ="street"/></code> <code><place type ="park"/></code> <code><place type ="square"/></code> <code><place type ="district"/></code> <code><place type ="settlement"/></code> <code><place type ="region"/></code> <code><place type ="country"/></code> <code><place type ="bloc_union"/></code> <code><place type ="bloc_continent"/></code> <code><place type ="bloc_geoRegion"/></code> <code><place type ="bloc_ocean"/></code> <code><place subtype ="historical"/></code> <code><place xml:id="pl_0000"/></code> <code><geo decls="WGS"</code> <code>source="geonames"/></code> value list for @source semi-open

Table 9: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <place> in the List of Places

<pre><place xml:id="pl_0027" type="settlement"> <placeName>Sharpeville</placeName> <country key="pl_0007"/> <location> <geo decls="#WGS" source="geonames">-26.68415, 27.87434</geo> </location> <idno type="wikidata">Q1422014</idno> <idno type="geonames">956162</idno> </place></pre>	<pre><place xml:id="pl_0086" type="country" subtype="historical"> <placeName>State of Aden</placeName> <place xml:id="pl_0104" type="bloc_union"> <placeName>Commonwealth of Nations</placeName> <location target="https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Member_states_of_the_Commonwealth_of_Nations.svg"> <geo/> </location> <place xml:id="pl_0153" type="ocean"> <placeName>Atlantic Ocean</placeName></pre>
<pre><place xml:id="pl_0017" type="bloc_continent"> <placeName>Africa</placeName></pre>	<pre><placeName from="1965" to="1979">Rhodesia</placeName> <placeName from="1980">Zimbabwe</placeName></pre>
<pre><place xml:id="pl_0038" type="region"> <placeName>Georgia</placeName> <country key="pl_0011"/></pre>	<pre><place xml:id="pl_0042" type="bloc_geoRegion"> <placeName>West Indies</placeName></pre>
<pre><place xml:id="pl_0134" type="park"> <placeName>Tompkins Square Park</placeName> <settlement key="pl_0013"/></pre>	<pre><place xml:id="pl_0089" type="country" subtype="historical"> <placeName>French Indochina</placeName> <location target="https://en.wikipe- dia.org/wiki/French_Indochina#/ media/File:Map_of_French_Indochina_expansion.svg"> <geo/> </location></pre>

Table 9 showcases a variety of alternative encodings for places that are all valid against the schema.

The schema provides that the XML editor allows only the element <place> within the element <listPlace>. The attribute @xml:id provides a unique identifier for each place. The attribute @type specifies the type of place from a closed list of values. The attribute @subtype can be added in the case of a historical place. The left column of Table 8 shows the pattern with the required elements and attributes for the element <place>: the elements <placeName>, <location>, and <idno>, the latter specified by the attributes @wikidata or @geonames. The element <placeName> provides the name of the place. It can occur twice if the place changed its name and is then specified by the attributes @to and/or @from. Depending on the value in the attribute @type in the element <place> the place can be assigned to a superior entity (either settlement, country, or bloc). These elements may, but do not have to contain text. E.g., in case of a <place type="settlement"> an additional element <country> can be added with a respective attribute @key referring to that country. The element <location> will in most cases be specified by the element <geo> that it contains. The attribute @decls refers to the element <geoDecl> in the tei-Header that defines the notation and the datum used for the geographic coordinates in the content of the geo element (World Geodetic System WGS84). The source will in most cases, but not always, be *GeoNames*. Sometimes the location might have to be specified by other means, using the element <location> specified by the attribute @target. If available, the Wikidata and/or GeoNames identification numbers are provided in the element <idno> specified by the @type attribute. These numbers allow to retrieve a multitude of additional information about the places that could potentially be used for example in further research and for a website. GeoNames is a geographical database under a creative commons attribution license that is available for download free of charge. It is based on multiple data sets and integrates geographical data such as names of places in various languages, elevation, population, and others (Unxos GmbH).

The constraint specifications make sure that the attribute @xml:id in the element <place> conforms to the pattern *pl_0000*, that there is text content in the <placeName> element, that the @key attribute in the elements <settlement>, <country> and <bloc> conform to the pattern *pl_0000*, and that there are no duplicate numbers in the <idno> elements. The list currently contains 166 place names.

5.2.3 List of Organizations

The schema for the list of organizations was designed to validate an XML document with a list that contains all the organizations related to or mentioned in the speeches at the congress.

Table 10: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the <listOrg> Element in List Organizations

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Additional Possible Elements	Possible Attribute Values, Recommended, Semi-Open list	Attribute Value, Required, closed list
<pre> <listOrg> <org xml:id=" " > <orgName></orgName> <location> <placeName key=" " ></placeName> </location> <desc></desc> </org> </listOrg> </pre>	<idno></idno>	<desc target=" " /> <desc source=" " />	<idno type = "wiki-data" />
	<note></note>	Possible Attribute Values, Optional	
	<address></address>	<orgName to=" " /> <orgName from=" " />	
	<addrLine></addrLine>		
	<email></email>		

The excerpt of the code in the *dlc_list_org.odd* for the specification of the <org> element shows how the content of the element is defined.

```
<elementSpec ident="org" mode="change">(...)
```

```

<content><elementRef key="orgName" minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="unbounded"/><elementRef key="location" minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="1"/><elementRef key="desc"
minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="1"/><elementRef key="idno" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/><elementRef key="note" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/></con-
tent>(...)</elementSpec>

```

Table 11: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <org> in List Organizations

<pre><org xml:id="org_004"> <orgName>Roundhouse</orgName> <location> <placename key="pl_0002"> </placeName> </location> <desc source="wikidata">performing arts and concert venue</desc> <idno type="wikidata">Q1422014</idno> </org></pre>	<pre><location> <placeName key="pl_0056"/> <address> <addrLine>Church Lane</addrLine> <addrLine>Toddington</addrLine> <addrLine>Gloucestershire</addrLine> <addrLine>GL54 5DQ</addrLine> <addrLine>UK</addrLine> </address> <email>archives@mulberrybush.org.uk</email> </location></pre>
<pre><orgName to="2018">Planned Environment Therapy Trust</orgName> <orgName from="2018">Planned Environment Therapy Ar- chives and Special Collections, including The National Child Care Library The Mulberry Bush Organisation Third Space (MB3) Registered Charity Number 309565 </orgName></pre>	<pre><orgName>SNCC</orgName> <location> <placeName key="pl_0037">Atlanta</placeName> </location> <desc source="wikidata">Student Nonviolent Coordinating Committee, largest student-led civil rights organization during the American Civil Rights Movement</desc> <idno type="wikidata">Q127723</idno></pre>
<pre><orgName>University of Oxford</orgName> <location> <placeName key="pl_0040"/> </location></pre>	<pre><desc target=https://web.archive.org/web/*/https://mulberrybush.org.uk/mb3/ar- chives/about-us/">The PET Archives and Special Collections support The Mulberry Bush Organisation in its mission to provide services that meet the needs of emotionally troubled and traumatised children, young people, their families and communities. (...)The archive holds the Joseph Berke Archive, 1960-2003. </desc></pre>

Table 11 showcases a variety of alternative encodings for organizations that are all valid against the schema.

The schema provides that the XML editor allows only the element `<org>` to be nested in the element `<listOrg>`. The attribute `@xml:id` provides a unique identifier for each organization. The left column of Table 10 shows the pattern with the required elements and attributes nested in the element `<org>`: the elements `<orgName>`, `<location>` and `<desc>`. The element `<orgName>` can occur twice if the place changed its name and is then specified by the attributes `@to` and/or `@from`. The element `<location>` can contain different elements allowing for various degrees of detail. It requires the element `<placeName>` with a `@key` attribute referring to the place. For some organizations, the location is obvious because it is implicit in the organization's name. For others, the `@key` reference suffices for possible machine reading, sometimes it might be useful to add the place-name for human readers. Therefore, the element may but does not have to contain text. For some organizations, an address and/or email address might be necessary. The element `<address>` can be supplemented with nested elements `<addrLine>`. A short description is required. The source will in most cases, but not always, be Wikidata, specified in the attribute `@source`. If the source of the description is a website, it can be referenced by the attribute `@target`. If available, the Wikidata identification number is provided in the element `<idno>` specified by the `@type` attribute.

The constraint specifications make sure that the attribute `@xml:id` in the element `<org>` conforms to the pattern `org_000`, that there is text content in the `<orgName>` and `<desc>` elements, that the `@key` attribute in the elements `<placeName>` conforms to the pattern `pl_0000`, and that there are no duplicate numbers in the `<idno>` elements. The list currently contains 24 names of organizations.

5.2.4 List of Terms

The initial question that led to the design of this schema and list was how to encode information in the speeches that could enable an analysis of the content from a perspective of cultural science. The element `<term>` defines terms that are used in the speeches. The choice of terms was guided by the goal to represent the content of the speeches and ultimately make them comparable. The definition for the element was changed to "defines a word and specifies it as a noun, lemma or abbreviation of a term". The list contains terms that occur very often as well as terms that are used more rarely but are significant to the respective speech. Each term has an ID. The terms should be grouped into one of the three types "noun, lemma, or abbreviation". A description is required. The source for a noun or abbreviation can be Wikidata and/or any other reference. A lemma indexes a lexeme listed in the description. The TEI P5 guidelines do not include

an element <listTerm>, so this element was created equivalent to existing elements like <listOrg>.

Table 12: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in the <listTerm> Element in List Terms

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Additional Possible Elements with Required Attributes	Attribute Values, Required, Closed Lists
<pre><listTerm> <term xml:id=" " type=" "> <w></w> <desc></desc> </term> </listTerm></pre>	<pre><idno type="wikidata"/> <ref target=" "/></pre>	<pre><term xml:id="te_000"</pre>
	<p>Additional recommended attributes</p> <pre><desc @target/> <desc @source/></pre>	<pre><term type="abb"/> <term type="lemma"/> <term type="noun"/></pre>

Table 13: Examples of Alternative Encoding Options in Element <term> in List Terms

<pre><term xml:id="te_010" type="lemma"> <w>rac</w> <desc>lexem includes the nouns race, racist and racists, the adjective racist, the nouns racialist, racialists, racialism and the adjective racialist</desc> </term></pre>	<pre><term xml:id="te_032" type="lemma"> <w>African</w> <desc>lexem includes the nouns African, Africans, and the adjective Afri- can</desc></term></pre>
	<pre><term xml:id="te_016" type="noun"> <w>white power</w> <desc>power exerted by people either belonging to the "white race" or to the capitalistic, imperialistic sys- tem</desc></term></pre>
<pre><term xml:id="te_080" type="noun"> <w>Emko</w> <desc target="https://web.ar chive.org/web/20220726161001/https://am ericanhistory.si.edu/collections/search/ob ject/nmah_1278791">brand name of a spermicide, Nonoxynol9</desc> </term></pre>	<pre><term xml:id="te_011" type="noun"> <w>solidarity</w> <desc source="wikidata">unity of feeling or action on a common inter- est</desc> <idno type="wiki- data">Q815726</idno></term></pre>
	<pre><term xml:id="te_007" type="abb"> <w>HP</w> <desc>HP, HP system: no infor- mation on meaning of abbreviation yet</desc></term></pre>

The schema provides that the XML editor allows only the element <term> to be nested in the element <listTerm>. The attribute @xml:id provides a unique identifier for each term. The left column of Table 12 shows the pattern with the required elements and attributes nested in the element <term>: the elements <w> (for *word*) and <desc> (for *description*). A short description is required. The source will in most cases, but not always, be Wikidata, specified in the attribute @source. If the source of the description is

a website, it can be referenced by the attribute @target. If there is no specification by attribute it means that the author provided the description.⁶⁸ If available, the Wikidata identification number is provided in the element <idno> specified by the @type attribute.

The constraint specifications make sure that the attribute @xml:id in the element <term> conforms to the pattern te_000, that there is text content in the <w> and <desc> elements, and that there are no duplicate numbers in the <idno> elements. Table 13 shows a variety of alternative encodings for organizations that are all valid against the schema. The list currently contains 99 terms.

The excerpt of the code in *dlc_list_terms.odd* shows how the class membership of the <desc> element was changed to fit the desired usage. The element is member of the attribute classes att.global, att.translatable, and att.typed. Only one of the attributes defined in these classes is needed: the @source from the att.global.source class which inherits from the att.global class. The attribute @target belongs to the att.pointing class which the <desc> element is not a member of. The long list of attributes in the att.global class and two attributes of the att.pointing class that were not needed were deleted in <attDef> elements contained by the <attList> element. The remaining @source and @target elements were specified in respective <attDef> elements (to be looked up in *dlc_list_terms.odd*).

```
<elementSpec ident="desc" mode="change"><classes mode="change"><memberOf key="att.translatable" mode="delete"/><memberOf key="att.typed" mode="delete"/><memberOf key="att.pointing" mode="add"/></classes>(...)<attList><attDef ident="xml:id" mode="delete"/>(...)</attList>
```

5.2.5 List of Audio Recordings

The schema validates the XML document List of Audio Recordings which is designed to eventually contain all the audio recordings made at the events of the congress in the *dlc_list_audio_recordings.xml*. The TEI P5 guidelines do not include an element <listAudio>, so this element was created equivalent to existing elements like <listPlace>. It can only contain <audio> elements. The element <audio> is not included in the guidelines either and was likewise created. It contains information characterizing the magnetic tapes recorded at the events of the congress and their digital conversions. Each element <audio> has a unique ID.

⁶⁸ If more people use this schema a key for the encoders could be identified with an @xml:id and a @key referencing the respective encoder could be added.

Table 14: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <audio> and Example of Encoding for the Element in the List of Audio Recordings

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Example of Encoding; optional attributes
<pre> <listAudio> <audio xml:id="audio_000" dur="PT0H0M0S" corresp="mi_000"> <idno type=" " "></idno> <idno type=" " "></idno> <desc type=" " "></desc> <title></title> <note></note> <event key="ev_000"> <date/> <time/> </event> <listPerson> <head></head> <person key="pe_000"> <personName/> </person> </listPerson> </audio> </listAudio> </pre>	<pre> <audio xml:id="audio_004" dur="PT0H31M20S" corresp="mi_008 mi_009"> <idno type="mag">4_49</idno> <idno type="dig">1_4_49</idno> <desc type="mag">reel size: 7 inch, tape length: 1800 feet, tape speed: 7.5 inches per second, brand: Scotch 150</desc> <title>Speech Stokely Carmichael, First Part, DL 7 A</title> <note>magnetic tape marked as used for printing the first side of the vinyl record "Stokely Carmichael, Address to Black Community, Dialectics of Liberation Congress DL 7 A", starts with end of Obi Egbuna's speech</note> <event key="ev_04"> <date when="1967-07-23">Sunday</date> <time when="15:00:00">afternoon</time> </event> <listPerson> <head>Speakers</head> <person key="pe_011"> <persName>Obi Egbuna</persName></person> <person key="pe_004"> <persName>Stokely Carmichael</persName></person> </listPerson> </audio> </pre>

The schema that validates the XML file with the list of audio recordings is very tight. The left column of Table 14 lists the required elements and attributes. The element `<listAudio>` can only contain `<audio>` elements. The `<audio>` element needs to be specified by the attribute `@xml:id` to provide a unique identifier, the attribute `@dur` for the duration of the recording, and the attribute `@corresp` that lists the elements `<milestone>` that the audio is related to. This element will be described in the documentation for the schema for the transcripts. The element `<audio>` contains the two elements `<idno>` which are specified by the `@type` attribute with either the value “mag” for magnetic tape or “dig” for digital file. The elements contain the number of the tape or file. The element `<desc>`, specified by the attribute `@type` with the value “mag” contains the technical data related to the magnetic tape. The element `<title>` roughly indicates the part of the event the recording contains. The element `<note>` gives more detailed information. The `<event>` element specifies the event at which the recording was made, with the date and time indicated in elements that include the optional “when” attribute. The element `<date>` can contain additional information like the day of the week. In case the time of the day can’t be exactly determined and for additional information for the human reader the element `<time>` can contain text like e.g., “afternoon” or “evening”. The `<listPerson>` element lists the speakers in the recording, referred to in the attribute `@key` in the element `<person>` and mentioned by name for the human reader in the element `<persName>`. The `<head>` element specifies the list. If all persons are identified it is *List of Speakers*, otherwise *List of Identified Speakers*. The right column of Table 14 showcases a possible valid encoding.

The constraint specifications make sure that the attribute `@xml:id` in the element `<audio>` conforms to the pattern `audio_000`, that the attributes `@key` in the elements `<person>` and `<event/>` conform to the pattern `pe_000` and `ev_00`, that there is text content in the `<head>`, `<title>`, `<note>` and `<idno>`, and that there are no duplicate numbers in the `<idno>` elements. The excerpt from the `dlc_list_audio_recordings.odd` shows the code for creating the new element `<audio>` and its attribute class membership.

```
<elementSpec ident="audio" mode="add"><desc>Characterizes a magnetic tape and the digital conversion of it. Recorded at the events of the Dialectics of Liberation Congress</desc><classes mode="change"><memberOf key="att.global" mode="add"/><memberOf key="att.global.linking" mode="add"/><memberOf key="att.duration.w3c" mode="add"/></classes>(…)</elementSpec>
```

5.2.6 List of Events

The schema validates the XML document *List of Events* which was designed to eventually contain information about all the events of the congress.

Table 15: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <event> and Examples of Encoding for the Element in the List of Events

Required Elements, Required Attributes	Example of Encoding, no audio recordings added yet
<pre> <listEvent> <event xml:id="" when=""> <label></label> <listPerson> <note></note> <person key=""> <persName></persName> </person> </listPerson> </event> </listEvent> </pre>	<pre> <event xml:id="ev_01" when="1967-07-18T10:30:00"> <label>Public Address, Questions and Answers, Press Conference</label> <listPerson> <note>list of identified speakers as of August 2022</note> <person key="pe_004"><persName>Stokely Carmichael</persName></person> <person key="pe_006"><persName>Allen Ginsberg</persName></person> </listPerson> </event> </pre>
<p>Example of Encoding, list of audio recordings added</p>	
<pre> <event xml:id="ev_04" when="1967-07-23T15:00:00"> <label>Public Address to the Black Community, Question and Answers</label> <listAudio> <note>List of the audio data related to this event, the key references the information in the separate file "List Audio Data", the idno of the digital file is added here for convenience</note> <audio key="audio_001">1_2_24</audio> <audio key="audio_002">1_2_20</audio> <audio key="audio_003">1_2_12</audio>(some <audio/> elements deleted for this example) </listAudio> (other elements deleted for this example) </event> </pre>	

The element `<listEvent>` can only contain `<event>` elements, which are specified by the required attributes `@xml:id` and `@when`. The required element `<label>` contains information on the type of event. If identified, a list of the matching audio recordings with the respective attribute `@key` as well as an element `<note>` with information for the human reader is added in an element `<listAudio>`. A list of speakers is provided in the element `<listPerson>`, either the identified speakers as of August 2022 (results in 5.1) or from research on the transcript of the event.

The constraint specifications make sure that the attribute `@xml:id` in the element `<event>` conforms to the pattern `ev_00`, that the attributes `@key` in the elements `<audio>` and `<person>` conform to the pattern `audio_000` and `pe_000` and `ev_00`, that there is text content in the `<label>` and `<note>`. Table 15 lists the required elements and attributes in the upper left column, as well as possible valid encodings in the other main cells.

5.2.7 Transcript

The schema defined in `dlc_transcripts.odd` was designed to validate an XML document with a transcript of the audio recordings of an event of the congress. Table 16 shows the required as well as the optional elements and attributes. The element `<div>` (division) divides the transcript of the event into major parts, specified by the required attribute `@type` with a value from the closed list of values `speeches`, `question-and-answer-audience`, `questions-and-answers-press`. The `<div>` element can only contain `<contrib>` elements. The `<contrib>` (contribution) element was created to divide the different major parts of the event into contributions by individuals. It needs to be specified by the `@type` attribute with a value from the closed list of values `address`, `announcement`, `answer`, `chanting`, `poetry reading`, or `question`. The `<speaker>` element identifies the person who contributes with a name for human readers and a `@key` attribute referencing an entry in the list of persons. If the person is unknown the key is `pe_000`. Additional information on the person can be added in a `<note>` element, possibly complemented by the elements `<placename>` and `<orgName>`. The transcribed text contained by the `<contrib>` element can be tagged with the elements `<persName>`, `<placename>`, `<orgName>` and `<term>` with a required attribute `@key`, referencing the respective lists. The element `<placename>` requires a `@type` attribute with a value from the closed list of values `geo` or `pol` to define whether the place name is used as a geographical reference or in a political context as a synonym for the respective government. The element `<term>` requires a `@type` attribute with a value from the closed list of values `cul`, `geo`, `phil`, or `pol` to define the context/meaning in which the term is used: cultural, geographical, philosophical, or political.

The element <vocal> indicates vocalized but not necessarily lexical phenomena, specified by the required attribute @who (list of values open) which in most cases will be the value *audience*. An optional attribute @toWhom is available. The required attribute @type specifies the element with a value from the closed list of values *cheering*, *interjection*, *laughter*, *mumbling*, or *turmoil*. The element <kinesic> marks a non-vocalized communicative phenomenon, specified by the required attribute @who, which will most of the time be the audience, and the @type attribute with the closed list of values *applause* and *mic_tapping*. The element <milestone> is an element without content that marks the text contained in an audio file by indicating the boundary points unaffected by the tree hierarchy of the XML language. It needs to be specified by several required attributes: the @xml:id provides an id conforming to the pattern *mi_000*, @key references the audio file to which this milestone is related, listed in the separate list of audio recordings, the @dur (duration) indicates the time stamp in the audio that this point in the text represents. The optional attributes @next and @prev reference the next and the previous milestone related to the audio file.

The specification of the <milestone> element in the *dlc_transcript.odd* was difficult because the desired outcome differed from the predefined attributes and datatypes in the TEI P5 guidelines. The excerpt of the code shows the solution that was found⁶⁹.

```
<elementSpec ident="milestone" mode="replace">(...)
<classes mode="replace">
<memberOf key="att.global" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.milestoneUnit" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.typed" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.spanning" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.breaking" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.edition" mode="delete"/>
<memberOf key="att.canonical" mode="add"/>
<memberOf key="att.duration" mode="add"/>
<memberOf key="model.milestoneLike" mode="add"/>
</classes>
<attList>
<attDef ident="calendar" mode="delete"/>
(...)
<attDef ident="dur" mode="replace" usage="req">
<datatype><dataRef key="teidata.duration.w3c"/>
</datatype>
</attDef>
<attDef ident="xml:id" mode="replace" usage="req">
<datatype><dataRef key="teidata.text"/>
</datatype>
</attDef>
<attDef ident="key" mode="replace" usage="req">
<datatype><dataRef key="teidata.text"/>
</datatype>
</attDef>
<attDef ident="prev" mode="add" usage="rec">
<datatype><dataRef key="teidata.text"/>
</datatype>
</attDef>
<attDef ident="next" mode="add" usage="rec">
<datatype><dataRef key="teidata.text"/>
</datatype>
</attDef>
</attList>
</elementSpec>
```

⁶⁹ If a more elegant code is possible suggestions are welcome.

Table 16: Elements and Attributes to be Nested in Element <div>in the XML Document for Transcripts

Required Elements, Required Attributes	List of Attributes, required, closed list	
<div><contrib type="" /> </div>	<kinesic type="" applause"/> <kinesic type="" mic_tapping"/>	<placename key="" type="" pol /> <placename key="" type="" geo />
Optional Elements in <contrib>, Required Attributes <contrib type=""> <incident/> <kinesic who="" type="" /> <milestone xml:id=""mi_000" key=""audio_000 dur=""PT0H0M0S" /> <orgName key=""org_000"/> <persName key=""pe_000"/> <placename key=""pl_0000"/> <speaker key=""pe_000"/> <term key=""te_000" type="" /> <textnode/> <vocal who="" type="" /> </contrib> Optional additional elements <incident><desc/></incident> <speaker key=""><note/></speaker> <note><orgName/></note> <note><placeName/></note>	<contrib type=""address"/> <contrib type=""announcement"/> <contrib type=""answer"/> <contrib type=""chanting"/> <contrib type=""question"/> <contrib type=""poetry_reading"/> <term key="" type=""cul"/> <term key="" type=""geo"/> <term key="" type=""phil"/> <term key="" type=""pol"/>	<div type=""speeches"/> <div type=""questions_and_answers_audience"/> <div type=""questions_and_answers_press"/> <vocal type=""cheering"/> <vocal type=""interjection"/> <vocal type=""laughter"/> <vocal type=""mumbling"/> <vocal type=""turmoil"/>
	List of Attributes, recommended, closed list	Attributes, optional
	<milestone prev=""mi_000"/> <milestone next=""mi_000"/>	<kinesic who="" /> <vocal toWhom="" />

Table 17: Examples of Encoding, Transcript

Examples of Encoding for the elements <div> and <contrib>	
<pre><div type="questions_and_answers_audience"> <contrib type="question"> <speaker key="pe_000"> unidentified <note>from <placeName type="geo" key="pl_0016"> Guyana</placeName> founding member SNCC</note> </speaker></pre>	
Mr. Speaker I think you refer to<placeName key="pl_0044" type="pol">Russia</placeName> as an enemy of the<term key="te_036" type="pol">Third World</term>	
position of <term key="te_096" type="pol">armed resistance</term><kinesic who="audience" type="applause"/><vocal who="audience" type="cheering"/>	
<pre><milestone xml:id="mi_022" key="audio_008" dur="PT0H6M47S" prev="mi_021" next="mi_023"/> as a fellow <term key="te_032" type="cul">African</term> or<term key="te_044" type="cul">Afro-American</term>I'd like to put a question to you concerning the revolutionary struggle of <term key="te_008" type="pol">Black people</term></pre>	
it's set out to accomplish in providing a a true <term key="te_098" type="phil">dialectics</term> a true opposition of just not just the <term key="te_097" type="phil">theory</term> but the action	
the <term key="te_024" type="pol">English</term> will probably not let us come back	
we have to tell the <term key="te_003" type="pol">white man</term> that when his <orgName key="org_009">CIA</orgName>	
<incident><desc>audio tape is played, unintelligible</desc></incident><<	
he would be speaking <term key="te_089" type="cul">Swahili</term><term type="cul" key="te_090">Ibo</term> or whatever the tribes	
in <term key="te_032" type="cul">African robes</term>	one of the leading <term key="te_043" type="cul">American poets</term>

Table 17 shows examples of encoding from dlc_transcript_1967_07_23_15_00.xml

5.2.8 TEI header

Each TEI XML document needs to be documented. This is accomplished in a set of descriptions, prefixed to it in the <teiHeader> element. A minimal <teiHeader> element contains a file description, a title statement, a publication statement, and a source description. The schemata created for this project all include the minimal set of elements plus some additional information, varying according to the content. The TEI header for the list of audio recordings is the most differentiated one and is presented in the following table.

Table 18: Required Elements TEI header List of Audio Recordings

<pre><teiHeader> <titleStmt><title/><author/><titleStmt> <publicationStmt> <publisher/> <date/> <email/> <availability><licence/><note/><availability/> <publicationStmt/> <notesStmt/> <encodingDesc><p/></encodingDesc> <sourcedesc> <bibl> <title/> </bibl> <note/> </sourcedesc> <recordingStmt> <respStmt><resp/><person/></respStmt> <equipment/> <date/> </recordingStmt"> <revisionDesc"/></pre>
--

The <titleStmt> element provides the title and the name of the author of the XML document. The <publicationStmt> element groups information concerning the

publication of the document in the elements <publisher>, <date> and <email>. The <availability> element supplies information about restrictions in the use of the document in the <licence> element which is complemented by the <note> element. The <notesStmt> element provides additional information about the document in one or more <note> elements. In this case, the list is born digital in the sense that it was created as XML document, however, it is based on the information described in the <sourceDesc> element. It is specified in the element <bibl> (bibliographic citation) that can contain the elements <title>, <author>, <date>, and <orgName>. The element <encodingDesc> gives instructions how to encode the information by describing the required and optional elements and attributes in a <p> (paragraph) element. The element <recordingStmt> provides information about the recording of the audio data. The element <revisiondesc> (revision description) was added to the TEI header in anticipation of future revisions of the prototypes. Custom elements and attributes can be added to the schema once an actual revision takes place. The elements have no attributes except for the <date> element that can optionally be specified with the @when attribute, additionally to the textual information. Table 19 exemplifies the use of the elements in a truncated version.

Table 19: Truncated Examples of TEI header List of Audio Recordings

<availability><licence>CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</licence><note>The licence applies to the content of this list. The audio recordings listed are copyrighted.</note></availability>
<notesStmt><note>This is an extensible list of audio data related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress. It was designed to eventually list the audio data to all the events at the congress once it has been evaluated.(...) </note> </notesStmt><
<encodingDesc><p>Each "audio" element has an identification number in the @xml:id attribute and is specified by the @dur attribute indicating the length of the recording and the @corresp attribute listing the related milestone elements.(...)</p></encodingDesc>
<sourceDesc><bibl><title>Digital Audio Files, Dialectics of Liberation Congress 1967</title><orgName key="org_001">PET Archives and Special Collections </orgName></bibl>(...)</sourceDesc>
<recordingStmt><recording type="audio"><respStmt><resp source="...">Location recording (...)</resp><person key="pe_001"><persName> Roy Battersby </persName></person>(...)</recordingStmt>

5.2.9 Audio Recordings, Milestone Element

The explorative methodology with an iterative back and forth between the various ODD documents and the TEI list documents and the transcript resulted in the identification of the relation of the different audio recordings with the entirety of the event. It was ultimately revealed through the tagging of the transcript with the milestone element and its attributes. It needed several steps to solve the puzzle.

Table 20: *Equivalents of the xml:id of the Audio Recordings and the Digital File Number*

xml:id of audio file in xml file <i>List of Audio Recordings</i>	Number of Digital Audio File
audio_001	1_2_24
audio_002	1_2_20
audio_003	1_2_12
audio_004	1_4_49
audio_005	1_3_25
audio_006	1_4_17
audio_007	1_2_18
audio_008	1_2_19
audio_009	1_1_21

Table 21: *Milestones Sorted by Audio Files*

Audio ID	Milestone ID	Timestamp Audio File	Preceding Milestone	Next Milestone
audio_001	mi_001	0H0M0S		next mi_024
audio_001	mi_024	3H07M24S	prev mi_001	
audio_002	mi_002	0H0M0S		next mi_004
audio_002	mi_004	0H31M34S	prev mi_004	next mi_005
audio_002	mi_005	0H31M35S	prev mi_005	next mi_006
audio_002	mi_006	1H3M42S	prev mi_006	
audio_003	mi_003	0H0M0S		next mi_007
audio_003	mi_007	0H14M45S	prev mi_003	
audio_004	mi_008	0H0M0S		next mi_009
audio_004	mi_009	0H31M19S	prev mi_003	
audio_005	mi_010	0H0M0S		next mi_011
audio_005	mi_011	0H32M22S	prev mi_010	
audio_006	mi_012	0H0M0S		next mi_013
audio_006	mi_013	0H32M22S	prev mi_012	
audio_007	mi_016	0H0M0S		next mi_017
audio_007	mi_017	0H16M54S	prev mi_016	
audio_008	mi_018	0H0M0S		next mi_019
audio_008	mi_019	0H2M44S	prev mi_018	next mi_020
audio_008	mi_020	0H2M45S	prev mi_019	next mi_021
audio_008	mi_021	0H6M46S	prev mi_020	next mi_022
audio_008	mi_022	0H6M47S	prev mi_021	next mi_023
audio_008	mi_023	0H14M58S	prev mi_022	
audio_009	mi_014	0H0M0S		next mi_015
audio_009	mi_015	0H32M1S	prev mi_014	

Table 20 lists the @xml:id identification of the audio recordings in the list of audio recordings that correspond to the names that the audio files have in the PET archive. Table 21 lists the milestone elements sorted by the audio @xml:id identification listing the respective preceding and following milestone elements. Table 22 lists the milestone elements in chronological order in that they appear in the transcript. The rows are colored in different shades of grey, or font in italics or bold print to differentiate them by audio file.

Table 22: Milestones Sorted by their Chronological Order in the Transcript

Audio ID	Milestone ID	Timestamp Audiofile	Preceding Milestone	Next Milestone
audio_001	mi_001	0H0M0S		next mi_024
audio_002	mi_002	0H0M0S		next mi_004
audio_003	mi_003	0H0M0S		next mi_007
audio_002	mi_004	0H31M34S	prev mi_004	next mi_005
audio_004	mi_008	0H0M0S		next mi_009
audio_002	mi_005	0H31M35S	prev mi_005	next mi_006
audio_004	mi_009	0H31M19S	prev mi_003	
audio_005	mi_010	0H0M0S		next mi_011
audio_002	mi_006	1H3M42S	prev mi_006	
audio_006	mi_012	0H0M0S		next mi_013
audio_003	mi_007	0H14M45S	prev mi_003	
audio_005	mi_011	0H32M22S	prev mi_010	
audio_007	mi_016	0H0M0S		next mi_017
<i>audio_009</i>	<i>mi_014</i>	<i>0H0M0S</i>		<i>next mi_015</i>
audio_006	mi_013	0H32M22S	prev mi_012	
audio_007	mi_017	0H16M54S	prev mi_016	
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_018</i>	<i>0H0M0S</i>		<i>next mi_019</i>
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_019</i>	<i>0H2M44S</i>	<i>prev mi_018</i>	<i>next mi_020</i>
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_020</i>	<i>0H2M45S</i>	<i>prev mi_019</i>	<i>next mi_021</i>
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_021</i>	<i>0H6M46S</i>	<i>prev mi_020</i>	<i>next mi_022</i>
audio_001	mi_024	3H07M24S	prev mi_001	
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_022</i>	<i>0H6M47S</i>	<i>prev mi_021</i>	<i>next mi_023</i>
<i>audio_008</i>	<i>mi_023</i>	<i>0H14M58S</i>	<i>prev mi_022</i>	
<i>audio_009</i>	<i>mi_015</i>	<i>0H32M01S</i>	<i>prev mi_014</i>	

Figure 1: Overlap of the Audio Files related to the Event on 23 July 1967, Public Address to the Black Community, Questions and Answers

An alternative visualization is presented in Figure 1. The milestones are sorted in chronological order in boxes with their @xml:id identification in a grey box representing the transcript from left to right on the top of the figure. The distance between the milestones is equal in the graphical presentation because a representation of the relative distance would not fit on the page. Milestones that represent the same point in the text are placed vertically on top of each other. Vertical lines connect the milestone boxes with their related audio file boxes labeled with their respective @xml:id identification. Audio element boxes that relate to milestones that represent the same point are placed vertically on top of each other. Horizontal lines between the audio file boxes represent uninterrupted stretches of recording.

5.2.10 Constraint Specifications

The following example illustrates how the Schematron language was encoded in TEI XML code the ODD to embed it in the RNG document that validates the TEI encoded XML file.

```
<constraintSpec ident="correctPlaceID" scheme="schematron"><constraint><s:rule context="tei:place"><s:assert test="matches(@xml:id, '^pl_\d{4}$')">a place-id must conform to the pattern: "pl_0000"</s:assert></s:rule></constraint></constraintSpec>
```

The element <constraintSpec> is specified by the attribute @ident with a name for the rule that is defined and the attribute @scheme that supplies the language in which the constraint is defined. The element <constraint> contains the formal rule and assertion of the constraint. The element <s:rule> defines the node in the tree hierarchy in the attribute @context. The element <s:assert> specifies the condition to be met in the attribute @test. In this case the xml:id attribute in the <place> element must conform to the defined regex. The rule is added in text form and will be shown in the XML editor if the user enters a non-conforming place-id.

6. Discussion

6.1 Discussion Analysis of Inventory Lists

The Pandas Data Analysis library proved to be a very useful tool to analyze the content of the inventory lists. In this case, it was successfully applied to determine which audio recordings are related to which event. The notebooks created for this project could be used to produce a schedule of the congress with a list of the audio recordings corresponding to the respective events. Given the richness of detailed information provided in

the tables that were produced from the original text data, it could also be used for many other analyses, for example for researchers interested in the technical aspect of the recordings. Depending on the research purpose, columns could be omitted, or information could be split up into even more detailed columns.

In addition to the contribution to this specific research project, the analysis proved that important information can be discovered by using digital tools on metadata provided by an archive without needing to access the analog material. However, it also showed the limitations of this approach.

The existence of a varying number of tapes related to each event bears the question of how and why they were produced. Was there more than one recording device? Are they copies of one main tape per event? Detailed knowledge about analog recording on magnetic tapes could probably help answer some of the questions by looking at the data. The mentioning of transcripts might indicate that parts of the event were copied and given to the respective transcribers. Ultimately, only a closer look at the transcripts, a review of the correspondence with the company that printed the vinyl records, and a physical examination of the magnetic tapes in Berke's estate ⁷⁰ kept at the archive will help answer these questions.

6.2 Discussion TEI XML Project

The expectations in the use of the TEI encoding were not only met but exceeded. The project resulted in an organized, functional set of TEI ODD schemata with the respective XML documents that preserves information about the congress, is extensible in several ways, and provided research insights in the process of creation even before an analysis of the XML documents with a query language. There are powerful open-source tools, like OMEKA, for museums, libraries, and archives to publish collections and narrative exhibits on the web. But they rely on existing metadata of archived content and are not conceived for researching it, whereas the TEI XML language is in the first place an academic research tool with a wide range of possible usage.

Although the purpose of the elements and attributes that are defined in the P5 Guidelines is to facilitate data exchange and comparison in the humanities, they do not represent a fixed standard. It is therefore advised to create schemata for the individual

⁷⁰ Box 4 *Transcripts of sessions at Dialectics of Liberation Conference, 1967*; Box 5, contains miscellaneous information on Intersound Recordings PET Archives and Special Collections, 2021

research project by choosing from the predefined set and modifying it according to the specific needs. In case of individual tagging needs that are not adequately represented the creation of new elements and attributes is advised. Since this project aimed at preserving information and making it easily accessible the encoding should meet the following requirements:

- be as detailed as necessary and as simple as possible
- be easy to read for humans studying the XML document
- provide logical tagging for automated information retrieval

The project included common tasks like preparing a list of persons, a list of places, and a list of organizations from the names of persons, places, and organizations in the transcript. The elements were taken from the existing pool. It provides a wide range of elements that enable a great variety of encoding patterns.

The List of Audio Recordings presented a different challenge. It is not a product of the tagging of the transcript, but an independent document that is related to the transcript via the <milestone> elements. It was considered to use the <recording> element for the identification of the audio recordings. This might have been a choice if there was only one recording from which the transcript was derived. The element was used for the entirety of audio files in the <teiHeader> with the @type attribute specifying it as audio recording. The elements <audio> and the element <listAudio> were created to identify and group the abundance of individual audio files. As of August 2022, it lists only the audio data related to the event on the afternoon of 23 July 1967, the address to the Black Community, one of the four events Carmichael participated in, as identified in the first part of the practical project.

The approach of combining the <audio> elements with the <milestone> elements resulted in a tool to identify the position of each audio file in relation to the entire transcript of the event. It was a complicated process for this project because the schemata for the List of Audio Recordings and the transcript needed to be created and adjusted several times to fulfill this function. The audio files related to the other events similarly probably represent cuts and clips. Future analyses of the relation of audio files to other events can be made much faster now that the process is clear. The milestone elements can be extracted automatically.

The List of Events lists the four events that Carmichael participated in as identified in the first part of the practical project. The list of participating persons for three of

the events was created from the information provided in the lists provided by the PET archive. Only the list of persons contained in the description of the event of 23 July 1967 was verified by listening to the audio files, only this event is specified with the verified list of audio files. Although the audio files related to the other events were identified in the analysis, only the audio files for this event were verified by listening to them and comparing them with the transcript prepared from two of them.⁷¹

The transcript is a representation of speech. There is a predefined collection of elements in the TEI P5 guidelines for speech representation. This schema was used in one of the first attempts to create a customized schema for the transcript. However, the predefined schema is rather suited to annotating from a linguistic perspective and therefore included many elements superfluous for this project while lacking others deemed necessary.

The <contrib> element was created for this project because the existing alternatives to subdivide the <div> (division) element did not seem adequate. The mere numbering of the elements in <div1> did not seem specific enough, a <p> (paragraph) element is associated with a printed text, and the corresponding element <u> (utterance) is associated with shorter divisions like in a theater play. The <contrib> element states in its name that it is some kind of contribution to the event, which can be specified in the @type attribute. The event that was transcribed for this project had speeches, questions, answers, and announcements. The list has entries that mention chanting and poetry readings⁷² in other events, so these values were added to the list of values for future use.

All non-lexical, communicative, or incidental occurrences were tagged with the elements <vocal>, <kinesic>, and <incident> in a basic manner and can be used for a comparison of the interaction between the speakers and the audience. Researchers with more specific interests could add additional attributes e.g., the duration of an applause, or could tag additional linguistic phenomena like the filler utterances *uh* and *um* which are present in the transcript but have not been tagged.

The goal to tag text content in the transcript that could be of use for analysis and comparison of the content of the speeches from a perspective of cultural studies presented a challenge. The tagging of names, dates, places, etc. is comparatively objective in the sense that they are obvious in the text. The aspiration was to create a tagging system that

⁷¹ Although it can be presumed that the content of the audio files corresponds to the description this needs to be verified by listening to them.

⁷² For example, 3.30, 3.32 and 4.37 in Annex B.

allowed for more precise identification and comparison of topics than the results that can be achieved by applying a topic modeling text-mining tool. These tools use statistical algorithms to discover the latent semantic structures of texts. They can be useful for a basic analysis of large text corpora but don't meet the requirements of detailed contextual analysis⁷³.

However, the choice of elements and attributes, the choice of content of the elements and attributes, and the decision of which parts of the text to tag with which elements and attributes all are acts of interpretation. The aspiration was to provide accurate tagging that represents the content of the speeches and makes the choice as transparent as possible. The element <term> as characterized in the TEI Guidelines can contain any single or include multi-word lexical item, symbolic designation, or phraseological unit without any restriction so it can be used in whatever context.

The first interpretative step was thus the identification of three groups by studying the transcript: nouns, members of a lexeme, or abbreviations. They are specified in the list of terms in the <w> (word) element, which is obvious for a term represented by a noun or an abbreviation. The element <lem> for lemma is reserved for specific linguistic purposes in the TEI P5 guidelines and is not used in this context. Instead, a lemma is defined in the <w> element and the corresponding lexeme described in the <desc> description element. Many of the terms are interrelated, e.g., the lemmata *coloni* and *rac* for all the words related to colonialism and racism. In the process of the schema definition, there was a stage where an attribute @corresp was added to the <term> element in the *List of Terms* to reference these interrelations. Ultimately it was deleted because it added another layer of interpretation. Even if some relations seem obvious at first sight it seems more adequate to leave possible groupings of terms up to the individual researcher.

The next interpretative step was taken when the corresponding terms were tagged in the transcript because they require an attribute specifying them as being used in a cultural, philosophical, political, or geographical context. While the list of terms gives an overview of the terms used in either a specific speech or the totality of speeches, the specification by the attributes in the tagging of the transcript allows for a more granular analysis of their usage. However, since the choice of attributes requires interpretation and may be debatable it does not have to be considered in an analysis. The practicability and

⁷³ The author studied this in a previous project by applying the Python-based Gensim topic modeling library in the analysis of a large set of twitter tweets. Naumann, 2021.

possible added value need to be tested once more transcripts are annotated. This should take considerably less time than the tagging of the first transcript because the schemata are created and many of the names of persons, places, and organizations as well as terms are already defined in the lists. Much of the tagging can be done by adding elements and keys, only new names, places, organizations, and terms need to be added to the lists.

The set of schemata and XML files was created as a prototype to eventually grow into a digital archive that covers all the events and retrievable information about the congress. Figure 2 shows the architecture of the set of XML documents that have been created so far. The information is stored in the transcript and separate lists where certain elements that are individually identified by the @xml:id attribute subsume details on the item. This information can be tied to an element in a different XML file by adding specific attributes (most of the time the @key attribute) to the element. Each person, place, organization, audio recording, event, and term is defined once and can be referred to from all other existing files and future files that might be added to the project. The concept allows for convenient handling of possible changes or corrections because they can be made in the separate lists without affecting the other documents.

The figure also shows how the content of the archive is not only built by research in the sense of finding the sources, in this case, the material held at the archive but is also produced by research in creating lists with content created from the sources.

Figure 2: Relation of XML Documents

The set of lists could be extended by adding a list for photographs, a list for secondary sources related to the congress, and a list corresponding to the list of audio recordings with information on video data. The film by Davis is available online on YouTube but copyrighted. In 2021 and 2022 Davis published several additional short video clips from the congress. This data could be analyzed and connected to the transcripts with milestone elements like the audio recordings and the web source referenced without violating copyright. There are quite a few photographs taken at the congress by the photographer John Haynes, who copyrighted them but published them on his website (Haynes). By cross-referencing with the videos, the transcripts of the relevant events could be tagged with an element that would have to be chosen for this purpose and equally connected to the web source by reference. This approach would allow to make the videos and photos easily accessible and directly linked to the transcripts of the events without any breach of copyright.

6.3 Discussion of the Term Digital Archive in Relation to this Project

A digital archive is an entity that differs from the definition of an archive in several ways. It is not a digitized version of an archive that holds analog material. These archives need to meticulously conform to their standards of preservation and standardized organization of their holdings. These standards might be subject to changes in the long term, but they guarantee the reliability of the sources they provide.⁷⁴ Digitalization of metadata, inventory lists, and other higher-level information on the holdings are a first step in providing easier access to the material and can lead a long way as this project proved. Digitalization of individual items would provide even better remote access and allow for even more detailed research. However, digital copies are representations of the original if they are not born digital and some information will always be only available by physically examining the objects. In this case, only a physical examination of the magnetic tapes can confirm where a tape was spliced or taped and help identify whether it is a copy or an original.

A digital archive can be a lot of different things, from a loose collection of information about a theme to a sophisticated highly engineered online presentation of content centered on a specific topic. The following statements outline theoretical guidelines that this digital archive with academic aspirations should follow. It needs to keep up to certain standards of documentation. Authorship of the content should be declared, and sources

⁷⁴ They comply to the ISAD(G) – General International Standard Archival Description.

should be meticulously listed and referred to. Unlike a digitized version of an archive, it does not need to keep the material in any specific order or grouping related to its origin. Quite in contrary, a digital archive can recombine material from different sources and will deliberately do so to create new connections and produce research results.

Digital copies of analog material can be subject to access restrictions that the physical counterparts do not have or comply with. For example, the audio files could not be made freely available even if the PET archives had the human power and financial possibilities to carry out such a project. The copyright held by various rights owners makes this impossible, at least for the moment. The copyright for the audio recordings is held by Battersby and Churchill. The rights to the content of the speeches are held by the speakers. Since the transcript for this project was made directly from the audio recordings the text can be published provided that the speakers or their heirs permit it. Speeches of unidentified persons or unidentified rights holders could be published subject to withdrawal.⁷⁵ The publication of transcripts could provide access to hitherto unpublished parts of the events. The fine-grained encoding of the XML document allows for selected publication in case permission would not be granted for some of the speeches.

It is possible to gain access to the audio recordings at the PET archives for individual research purposes. This is where this project of a digital archive of the congress could augment the number of potential users. The publication of the research conducted on the audio files is not restricted. The lists created in this project already provide information on one event and the related audio files and could potentially cover the entire congress. The availability of this information combined with a link to the PET archives could contribute to a wider knowledge about the audio files. It could lead to valuable research that takes into account the qualities the audio recordings reveal without any copyright infringement.

There is a consensus nowadays that archives are and will always be biased in many ways: the creation of the material, the choice of material to be preserved, the handling of it, the presentation – everything depends on humans making certain decisions, either individually or based on rules issued by humans. By handing over the audio tapes and all other material related to the congress to the PET archive Berke made sure that it would not get lost and made accessible to the public. As far as it is possible to tell, all the

⁷⁵ A disclaimer needs to be added that the copyright user despite best effort failed to obtain a valid authorization from the copyright owner due to either the identity or the location of the copyright owner being unknown.

officially announced and scheduled events were recorded. Due to the choice of what was printed on vinyl records and printed in books only the main speeches were made accessible and preserved for the public. This was an editing choice made at the time. The choice of material that was created at the time nowadays represents an object of research in itself.

This project is biased in the way of choosing a specific set of materials for the prototype of the archive and in the approach to dealing with it. The entire project is based on researching digital sources by applying digital tools. A digital archive with academic aspirations should document the process of creation along with the results. For the time being this project represents a digital archive in the sense that information has been gathered by digital means and is stored digitally. However, it can and hopefully will be made digitally available on a website. Ruggeri made clear that the visualization and the way the information is accessible online represent an important part of the perception and usage. How this could be accomplished in a way that conforms to academic standards is a whole new research question that would have to be considered carefully.

7. Conclusion

Overall, the project succeeded in creating a practical concept for an academically operated digital archive of the Dialectics of Liberation congress from the specific perspective of cultural science. The complexity of the TEI language is at the same time its greatest advantage and its greatest disadvantage. To create schemata needs careful consideration and takes a great amount of time. Once the schemata are designed, the encoding is much less time-consuming, especially the longer the lists are and the more can be referenced. If the time devoted to this project bears fruit only time will show.

The author is planning on eventually annotating the event that took place on the morning of 18 July 1967⁷⁶ and extending the lists accordingly. From the panel discussions that took place on the afternoon of 18 July 1967 and in the evening of 22 Jul 1967 only the contributions of Carmichael will be transcribed and encoded. The second research field the author is interested in is the female contributors.⁷⁷ It is planned to add the contribution of Susan Sherman to the poetry reading that took place on 27 July 1967.⁷⁸ The political officer of the student committee⁷⁹ of the Free University in Berlin was a young

⁷⁶ Carmichael's first speech, question-and-answer session audience, question-and-answer session press

⁷⁷ Besides to the content contributors there were identified and not yet identified women who contributed to the organization of the congress

⁷⁸ Audio file 3-27/1_3_27, see Annex B, p. 89. Sherman confirmed her participation, provided the text version of her poems, and granted permission to the author to publish them.

⁷⁹ AStA, Allgemeiner Studierendenausschuss der FU Berlin

woman, Gabriele Kuby. At the Anti-Institution Seminar, she gave a detailed account of the demonstration against the Shah of Persia's visit to Berlin that had taken place on 2 June 1967.⁸⁰ She changed her political convictions and did not grant permission to publish a transcript of her speech.⁸¹ Nevertheless, it is a very informative eyewitness report, and at the same time the very fact of her speaking there as a young woman adds to the research material related to the congress itself. The existence of the audio recording could be made available on the website.

This project could grow into an archive for the entire congress only in collaboration with other researchers, not only because it is too big for one person. The prototype created in this project needs to be tested by annotating more transcripts and conducting comparative analyses. If necessary, adjustments could be made. The author hopes to find interested researchers who would like to cooperate and advise. The schemata were coded directly in the ODD documents in learning by doing manner. They are tightly designed and perform well. Constraints in the Schematron language were added to reduce some undesired encoding options that the TEI schema definition elements can't specify. However, persons who were not involved in the process of creating the schemata might recommend additional constraints. The code written for the analysis of the content of the inventory lists of the archive fulfills its purpose. Since the author does not have professional coding knowledge it might be overly complicated in some places. In this case, recommendations for a more elegant code are welcome.

It is planned to create a website and make the project available online. As such it will be a dynamic, open-ended, user-orientated, performative archive like Laermans and Gielens describe the notion of digital archives. This project was possible through close cooperation with the PET Archives. According to senior archivist Debra Doggett the most frequently requested material at the archive is that related to the congress, specifically the correspondence of Joseph Berke. The results of this project might help the archive in their project of making sense of the collection of audio files in Berke's estate.

The goal of this archive is not as much to preserve information for a far-ahead future as to provide material that is not easy to access and research results on this material in the present and near future. However, the choice of the TEI XML format might guarantee the survival of this project for a while, even with future changes in technology.

⁸⁰ Audio file 2.3/1_2_03 see Annex B, p. 82

⁸¹ Personal communication.

8. Reference List

- American Historical Association (2015). *From Source to Subject: Historical Writing and the "Archival Turn": Session Abstract*. AHA Session 162. Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://aha.confex.com/aha/2015/webprogram/Session12018.html>.
- Anaconda, Inc. (2022). *Anaconda Navigator*. Retrieved August 10, 2022, from <https://anaconda.org/anaconda/anaconda-navigator>.
- Battersby, R. (2010). *Memories of the Congress: The congress taped*. Retrieved May 16, 2022, from <https://web.archive.org/web/20220516123118/http://www.dialecticsofliberation.com/1967-dialectics/memories/>.
- Bell, L. (1975). Reviews. *The American Archivist*, 38(1), 47–64.
- Berke, J. (Ed.) (1969). *Counterculture*. London: Owen.
- Bradsher, G. (1985). *The Percentage of Permanent Records in the National Archives: A 1985 Article Revisited*. Retrieved May 08, 2022, from NARA: <https://web.archive.org/web/20220508172056/https://text-message.blogs.archives.gov/2020/04/14/the-percentage-of-permanent-records-in-the-national-archives-a-1985-article-revisited/>.
- Brichford, M. (1982). The Origins of Modern European Archival Theory. *The Midwestern Archivist*. (Vol. VII No. 2), 87–101. Retrieved February 23, 2022, from <https://minds.wisconsin.edu/handle/1793/44735>.
- British Library, Sound & Moving Image Catalogue (2022). *Dialectics of Liberation Congress: 25 titles*, from <http://cadensa.bl.uk/uhtbin/cgiisirs/x/0/0/5?searchdata1=Dialectics%20of%20Liberation%20Congress>.
- Bundesarchiv (2018). *Grenzexpedition und Völkermord – Quellen zur Kolonialgeschichte*. Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://www.bundesarchiv.de/DE/Content/Artikel/Entdecken/quellen-zur-kolonialgeschichte.html>.
- Carmichael, S. (1971). *Stokely Speaks: Black Power back to Pan-Africanism*. New York: Random House.
- Carmichael, S., & Thelwell, E. M. (2003). *Ready for Revolution: The life and struggles of Stokely Carmichael (Kwame Ture)*. New York, NY: Scribner.
- Carter, R. G. (2006). Of Things Said and Unsaid: Power, Archival Silences, and Power in Silence. *Archivaria, The Journal of the Association of Canadian Archivists*. (61), 215–233. Retrieved March 02, 2022, from <https://archivaria.ca/index.php/archivaria/article/view/12541/13687>.
- Computer History Museum (1996-2022). *Exhibition Mainframe Computers*. Retrieved May 14, 2022, from <https://web.archive.org/web/20210725085236/https://www.computerhistory.org/revolution/mainframe-computers/7/intro>.
- Cook, M. (1989). The Role of Computers in Archives. *Information Development*, 5(4), 217–220.
- Cook, T. (1997). What is Past is Prologue: A History of Archival Ideas Since 1898, and the Future Paradigm Shift. *Archivaria, The Journal of the Association of Canadian Archivists*. (43), 17–63. Retrieved February 21, 2022, from <https://archivaria.ca/index.php/archivaria/article/view/12175>.
- Cook, T. (2004). Macro-appraisal and Functional Analysis: documenting governance rather than government. *Journal of the Society of Archivists*, 25(1), 5–18.
- Cook, T. (2013). Evidence, memory, identity, and community: four shifting archival paradigms. *Archival Science*, 13(2-3), 95–120.

- Cook, T., & Schwartz, J. M. (2002). Archives, Records, and Power:: From (Postmodern) Theory to (Archival) Performance. *Archival Science*. (Volume 2, issue 3-4), 171–185. Retrieved March 01, 2022, from <https://asset-pdf.scinapse.io/prod/2041373518/2041373518.pdf>.
- Cooper, D. G. (Ed.) (2015). *Radical thinkers. The Dialectics of Liberation*. London, New York: Verso.
- Cooper, D. G. (1968). *The Dialectics of Liberation. A Pelican Original*. Harmondsworth: Penguin.
- Cox, R. J. (2018). Appraisal and the future of archives in the digital era. In J. Hill (Ed.), *The Future of Archives and Recordkeeping* (pp. 217–242). Facet.
- Cuvelier, J., & Stainier, L. (1912). *Congrès international des Archivistes et des Bibliothécaires: Congrès de Bruxelles 1910*: Commission permanente des Congrès internationaux des Archivistes et des Bibliothécaires.
- Dascher, O. (2015). Data Bases and Statistical Systems: Archives and Historical Databases. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (pp. 700–703). Elsevier.
- Davis, P. (1968). *The Anatomy of Violence*.
- Davis, P., Ivimy, J., & Levy, M. *Dialectics of Liberation*. Retrieved August 12, 2022, from <http://www.dialecticsofliberation.com/>.
- Davis, P., Ivimy, J., & Levy, M. *Dialectics of Liberation, Memories*. Retrieved August 15, 2022, from <http://www.dialecticsofliberation.com/1967-dialectics/memories/>.
- Dawson, A. (2010). *Mongrel Nation*: University of Michigan Press.
- Derrida, J. (1995). Archive Fever: A Freudian Impression. *diacritics*. (25.2), 9–63. Retrieved February 20, 2022, from <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1297885671/fulltextPDF/8BA41B702E141C0PQ/1?accountid=13049>.
- discogs. *Dialectics of Liberation: Stokely Carmichael Black Power*. Retrieved July 06, 2022, from <https://www.discogs.com/de/release/1266424-Stokely-Carmichael-Black-Power/image/SW1hZ2U6ODY4NzcyMw==>.
- Dryden, J. (2017). *Copyright exceptions: an archivist's perspective*. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from https://www.wipo.int/wipo_magazine/en/2017/04/article_0003.html, https://web.archive.org/web/20220512172624/https://www.wipo.int/wipo_magazine/en/2017/04/article_0003.html.
- Duff, W. & van Ballegooie, M. (2006). *DCC, Digital Curation Manual: Instalment on "Archival Metadata"*. Retrieved August 15, 2022, from University of Toronto: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-reference-manual/completed-chapters/archival-metadata>.
- Duranti, L. (1994). The Concept of Appraisal and Archival Theory. *The American Archivist*, 57(2), 328–344.
- Duranti, L. (2001). The impact of digital technology on archival science. *Archival Science*. (1), 39–55, from http://www.interpares.org/display_file.cfm?doc=ip1_dissemination_jar_duranti_archival_science_1_2001.pdf.
- Duranti, L., & Franks, P. C. (2015). *Encyclopedia of Archival Science*. Lanham, Boulder, New York, London: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Evans, F. B. (1987). Promoting Archives and Research: A Study in International Cooperation Cooperation. *The American Archivist*. (Vol. 50 No. 1), 48–65. Retrieved March 16, 2022.
- Fertig, J. (2011). *Die Archivfalle*. Retrieved February 21, 2022.
- Fishbein, M. (1972). Appraising Information in Machine Language Form. *The American Archivist*, 35(1), 35–43. Retrieved 17.03.2022.

- Foucault, M. (1982). *The archaeology of knowledge*. New York, NY: Pantheon Books.
- Gobierno de España (2022). *Portada del Archivo General de Indias*. Retrieved May 02, 2022, from Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte - Archivo General de Indias: <https://www.culturaydeporte.gob.es/cultura/areas/archivos/mc/archivos/agi/portada.html>.
- Goldsmith, K. (2005). *If It Doesn't Exist on the Internet, It Doesn't Exist*. Retrieved May 02, 2022, from The University of Pennsylvania: https://web.archive.org/web/20220319090626/https://writing.upenn.edu/epc/authors/goldsmith/if_it_doesnt_exist.html.
- Goldsmith, K. (2012). *Kenneth Goldsmith: "Archiving is the new popular art": Interview with the founder of UBU Web*, from CCCB, Centre de Cultura Contemporània de Barcelona: <https://www.cccb.org/en/multimedia/videos/kenneth-goldsmith-archiving-is-the-new-popular-art/211605>.
- Goldsmith, K. (2020a). *About UbuWeb*. Retrieved May 03, 2022, from <https://www.ubuweb.com/resources/about.html>.
- Goldsmith, K. (2020b). *Duchamp is My Lawyer: The Polemics, Pragmatics, and Poetics of UbuWeb*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Google. *Youtube*. Retrieved August 10, 2022, from <https://www.youtube.com/>.
- Harding, J. M. (2010). *Cutting performances: Collage events, feminist artists, and the American avant-garde. Theater*. Ann Arbor, Mich.: Univ. of Michigan Press.
- Haynes, J. *RD Laing & The Dialectics of Liberation, 1967*. Retrieved May 18, 2022, from <https://johnhaynesphotography.net/rd-laing/>.
- ICA (2010). *Universal Declaration on Archives*. Retrieved May 14, 2022, from https://www.ica.org/sites/default/files/20190510_ica_declarationuniverselle_en_0.pdf.
- International Council on Archives (2016). *What are Archives?* Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://www.ica.org/en/what-archive>.
- Internet Archive (2022). *About the Internet Archive*. Retrieved May 03, 2022, from <https://archive.org/about/>.
- Jackson, J. (2014). *The mainframe turns 50, or, why the IBM System/360 launch was the dawn of enterprise IT*. Retrieved May 15, 2022, from <https://web.archive.org/web/20220315122240/https://www.pcworld.com/article/444734/the-mainframe-turns-50-or-why-the-ibm-system360-launch-was-the-dawn-of-enterprise-it.html>.
- Jakobsen, J. (2012). *Institute of Phenomenological Studies: Facsimile from Joseph Berke Archive, PETT*. Retrieved February 04, 2022, from <https://antihistory.org/post/20005902201/the-institute-of-phenomenological-studies>.
- Jenkinson, H. (1937). *A Manual of Archive Administration: New and Revised Edition*: Percy Lund, Humphries & Co Ltd.
- Joseph, P. E. (2014). *Stokely: A life*. New York, NY: Basic Civitas.
- Jupyter (2022). *Free software, open standards, and web services for interactive computing across all programming languages*. Retrieved August 10, 2022, from <https://jupyter.org/>.
- Karaganis, J. (2018a). Introduction: Access from Above, Access from Below. In J. Karaganis (Ed.), *Shadow Libraries*. The MIT Press.
- Karaganis, J. (Ed.) (2018b). *Shadow Libraries*: The MIT Press.
- Ketelaar, E., & Frings-Hessami, V. (2021). Scholarly and professional communication in archives: archival traditions and languages. *Archives and Manuscripts*, 49(1-2), 1–7.
- Lamb, W. K. (1966). The Changing Role of the Archivist. *The American Archivist*, 29(1), 3–10.

- Liddell, H. G. & Scott, R. (1940). *A Greek-English Lexicon: Revised and Augmented throughout by Stuart Jones with the Assistance of Roderick McKenzie*. Retrieved May 22, 2022, from Oxford University Press: [https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.04.0057:entry=a\)rxh/](https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.04.0057:entry=a)rxh/).
- Lowry, J., & MacNeil, H. (Eds.) (2021). *Archival Thinking: Archaeologies and Genealogies. Archival Science*. (Volume 21, issue 1): Springer.
- McCallum, S. (2003). *40 Years of Technology in Libraries: A Brief History of the IFLA Section on Information Technology, 1963/64 - 2003*. Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://repository.ifla.org/handle/123456789/771>.
- McCoy, D. R. (1985). The Struggle to Establish a National Archives in the United States. In T. Walch (Ed.), *Guardian of heritage. Essays on the history of the National Archives* (pp. 1–15). Washington, D.C.: National Archives and Records Administration.
- Microsoft (2022). *Microsoft 365*, from <https://www.microsoft.com/de-de/microsoft-365/microsoft-office>.
- Mittelbach, A. & Rahtz, S. (2022). *Roma - ODD customization: Version 0.3.1*. Retrieved August 12, 2022, from <https://romabeta.tei-c.org/>.
- The Mulberry Bush Limited (2022). *About the PET Archives*. Retrieved May 11, 2022, from https://web.archive.org/web/*/https://mulberrybush.org.uk/mb3/archives/about-us/.
- The Mulberry Bush Third Space (2022a). *Catalogue Help*. Retrieved May 16, 2022, from <https://archives.mulberrybush.org.uk/help>.
- The Mulberry Bush Third Space (2022b). *Home*. Retrieved May 11, 2022, from Planned Environment Therapy Archives and Special Collections including the National Childcare Library: <https://archives.mulberrybush.org.uk/>.
- Muller, S., Feith, J., & Fruin, R. (1940). *Manual for the Arrangement and Description of Archives: Drawn up by direction of the Netherlands Association of Archivists*. Translation of the Second Edition by Arthur H. Leawitt: The H.W. Wilson Company.
- NARA (2017). *Microfilm*. Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://www.archives.gov/preservation/formats/microfilming.html>.
- Naumann, N. (2021). *Lassen sich durch digitale Analyse der sozialen Medien Fragestellungen im Bereich der Gender Studies beantworten? – Ein Thinkering-Projekt zum Karen-Phänomen auf Twitter: Seminararbeit*. Universität Paderborn.
- Naumann, N. (2022). *Dialectics of Liberation Congress Digital Archive Audio File Project*. Paderborn: Universität Paderborn.
- Nauta, G. J., van den Heuvel, W., & Teunisse, S. (2017). *Europeana DSI 2– Access to Digital Resources of European Heritage: D4.4. Report on ENUMERATE Core Survey 4*. Retrieved May 20, 2022, from https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Projects/Project_list/ENUMERATE/deliverables/DSI-2_Deliverable%20D4.4_Europeana_Report%20on%20ENUMERATE%20Core%20Survey%204.pdf.
- OCLC. *VIAF: Virtual International Authority File*. Retrieved August 03, 2022, from <https://viaf.org/>.
- PET Archives and Special Collections (2021). *The Joseph Berke Archive, 1960-2003*. Retrieved June 27, 2022, from https://archives.mulberrybush.org.uk/search/all:records/0_50/all/score_desc/%20berke.
- Python Software Foundation (2022). *Python*. Retrieved August 13, 2022, from <https://www.python.org/>.
- Rahtz, S. (2020). *Oxgarage*. Retrieved August 13, 2022, from <https://oxgarage.tei-c.org/>.

- Reback, J., jbrockmendel, Wes McKinney, Joris Van den Bossche, Tom Augspurger, Phillip Cloud, et al. (2021). pandas-dev/pandas: Pandas 1.3.5: Zenodo.
- Ridener, J. (2007). *From Polders to Postmodernism: An intellectual History of Archival Theory*. Master's Thesis, San Jose State University, San Jose. Retrieved March 3, 2022.
- Roundhouse Trust Ltd. (2022). *Why hire the Roundhouse?* Retrieved August 15, 2022, from <https://www.hire.roundhouse.org.uk/>.
- Ruggeri, G. (2019). *Designing the Communication of Historical Knowledge through the Web*. Vilnius, Lithuania: Vilnius Academy of Arts Press.
- Ruggeri, G. (2022). *Open History Archive: A ortal to the History Web*. Retrieved May 06, 2022, from <https://www.openhistoryarchive.com/home/>.
- Schellenberg, T. R. (1998). *Modern Archives: Principles and Techniques* (© 1956 by T.R. Schellenberg. Published 1956. Reprinted 1976. © 1996 Kansas State Historical Society, published 1996. Reprinted 1998.). *Archival Classics Reprint: The Society of American Archivists; Kansas State Historical Society*.
- Schellenberg, T. R. (1965). *The Management of Archives*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Schwartz, J. M., & Cook, T. (2002). Archives, Records, and Power:: The Making of Modern Memory. *Archival Science*. (Volume 2, issue 1-2), 1–19. Retrieved March 01, 2022, from <https://journalofburmesescholarship.org/pprs/SchwartzCook-Archives.pdf>.
- Sci-Hub. *Sci-Hub, About*. Retrieved February 03, 2022, from <https://sci-hub.hkvisa.net/>.
- Sherman, S. (1967). The Dialectics of Liberation. *IKON magazine*. (4), 4–7.
- Sherman, S. (2007). *America's child: A woman's journey through the radical sixties* (1st ed.). Willimantic, Conn.: Curbstone Press.
- Society of American Archivists (2016). *What are Archives*. Retrieved March 13, 2022, from <https://web.archive.org/web/20220313120925/https://www2.archivists.org/about-archives>.
- Stiles, K. (1987). Synopsis of the Destruction in Art Symposium and Its Theoretical Significance. In Performance Project, Inc. (Ed.), *The Act* (Vol. 1, No. 2, 22-31). New York,
- Stiles, K. (1992). *Survival Ethos and Destruction Art* (Discourse). Retrieved February 08, 2022, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41389219>.
- Syncro Soft SRL (2022). *Oxygen XML Editor: Version 23.1*. Retrieved August 12, 2022, from <https://www.oxygenxml.com/>.
- TBE project team (2020). *TBE, TEI by example*, from <https://teibyexample.org/>.
- TEI Consortium (2022). *23 Using the TEI*, from <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/USE.html>.
- TEI Technical Council Members (2007). *P5: Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange*. Retrieved June 17, 2022, from <https://www.tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/index.html>.
- Tschan, R. (2002). A Comparison of Jenkinson and Schellenberg on Appraisal. *The American Archivist*, 65(2), 176–195.
- UN (1964). *Rome Convention*. Retrieved May 14, 2022, from https://treaties.un.org/pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=XIV-3&chapter=14&clang=_en.
- Unxos GmbH. *GeoNames*. Retrieved June 24, 2022, from <https://www.geonames.org/>.
- Walsham, A. (2016). The Social History of the Archive: Record-Keeping in Early Modern Europe. *Past and Present*, 230(Supplement 11), 9–48. Retrieved March 02, 2022.

- Wikipedia (2022a). *Joseph Berke*. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Joseph_Berke.
- Wikipedia (2022b). *Size of Wikipedia*. Retrieved April 29, 2022, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Size_of_Wikipedia.
- Wikipedia (2022c). *Wiki*. Retrieved April 29, 2022, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wiki>.
- WIPO (1971). *Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works*. Retrieved May 14, 2022, from <https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ip/berne/>.
- WIPO (2022a). *What is Intellectual Property?* Retrieved May 14, 2022, from <https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>, <https://www.wipo.int/about-wipo/en/>.
- WIPO (2022b). *WIPO Internet Treaties*. Retrieved May 14, 2022, from https://www.wipo.int/copyright/en/activities/internet_treaties.html.
- Women's Writers Project (2022). *Women's Writers Project*. Retrieved May 02, 2022, from Northeastern University: <https://www.wwp.northeastern.edu/>.
- Yeo, G. (2019). Can we keep everything? The future of appraisal in a world of digital profession. In C. Brown (Ed.), *Archival Futures* (pp. 45–64). Facet.
- Yeo, G. (2021). *Record-making and record-keeping in early societies*. London, New York, NY: Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.

9. Annex

Annex A

DOCUMENTATION:

This document was created by Natascha Naumann in 2022 from the PP-JB-IPS.docx file. It represents a selection of the original list, containing all the entries obviously or most probably related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress. Typos as in the original.

Changes to the original document:

change of font and font size; the paragraph distance between the log entries was reduced to save space for printing; the information in bold letters was used as source in this project.

Original Document: Planned Environment Therapy Trust Archive and Study Centre Material given by Dr. Joseph Berke, 1995.8/1 Archives of the Institute of Phenomenological Studies, Initial List

Box 1

1 Record Albums. Dialectics of Liberation Congress 1967

1.1 Album covers - sleeves only.

1.2 DL3: David Cooper; "Beyond Words" 4 copies

1.3 DL4; Ronald Laing; "The Obvious" 2 copies

1.4 DL5; Ross Speck; "The Politics & Psycho-therapy of Mini & Micro Groups" Discussions include D. Cooper; Jules Henry

1.5 DL6; Stokely Carmichael; "Black Power One" 12 copies

1.6 DL7; Stokely Carmichael; "Black Power Two" 16 copies

1.7 DL8; John Gerassi; "Imperialism & Revolution in America" 36 copies

1.8 DL9; John Gerassi; cont'd from DL8 Side A. Side B; Herbert Marcuse; "Liberation from the Affluent Society"; cont'd from DL11 10 copies

1.9 DL10; Jules Henry; "Special & Psychological Preparation for War" 3 copies

1.10 DL11; Herbert Marcuse; "Liberation from the Affluent Society"; cont'd on DL8

1.11 DL12; Paul Sweezy; "The Future of Capitalism" 3 copies

1.12 DL16; Allen Ginsberg; "Consciousness & Practical Action" 16 copies

1.13 DL19; Julian Beck; "Money, Sex & the Theatre"; Side B. Side A; Simon Vinkenoog;; "Revolution in Consciousness"; Paul Goodman; "Objective Values"; cont'd from DL17
11 copies

1.14 DL20; Anti institution seminar; Simon Vinkenoog; Allen Krebs; Aage Rosendal Nelson.

1.15 DL23; Challenge Seminar; Ecological destruction by technology; A discussion led by Gregory Bateson, & including Roy Battersby, Allen Ginsberg, Francis Huxley, Ronald Laing and Joseph Rosen-stein 5 copies

Box 2

2 Royalty & Bank Statements; Credit Slips; Correspondence
Stapled together in manila envelope.

- 2.1 Royalty & Bank Statements 1972
- 2.2 Royalty & Bank statements to 30.3.73
- 2.3 Credit slips 1972-73
- 2.4 Correspondence 1972-3
- 2.5 Royalty & bank statements mid to end 1971
- 2.6 Credit slips 1971

Box 4

4 Transcripts of sessions at Dialectics of Liberation Conference, 1967 in manila folders. Many of folders are stamped "Inter-Sound Recordings Ltd. 20 Fitzroy Square, London W.1"

4.1 Folder labelled "DL1 & DL2 / Bateson / 17/7/67" pp1-24

4.2 Folder labelled "DL3 / David Cooper" pp DC1-9 (side one) & 1-4 (Side two) 1st page headed "Beyond Words"

4.3 Folder labelled "DL4 / Ronald Laing" pp 1-25

4.4 Folder labelled "DL6 / Carmichael / 18.7.67" pp. 1-21

4.5 Folder labelled "DL5 DL2 / Speck 1-15 / Cooper 1st page headed 16-19 / Henry 17-22 / Korngold 18-26 / Discussion "Psychiatry & 27- / 24.7.67" pp. 1-36 Anti-Psychiatry"

4.6 Folder labelled "DL7 / Carmichael / 23.7.67" pp Sc2 16-40

4.7 Folder labelled "DL8/9 / John Gerassi" Dated on cover JG1 pp.1-22 sheet 20.7.67

4.8 Folder labelled "DL10 / Jules Henry" 1st page headed pp.1-33 Social & Psychological Preparation for War"

4.9 Folder labelled "DL12 / Paul Sweeney" 1st page headed pp.1-13 "The Future of Capitalism"

4.10 Folder labelled "DL13/DL14 / Saturday Night 1st page headed Discussion / 22.7.67" pp.1- 35 "Laing/Carmichael/ Ginsberg/Cooper/ Brogan"

4.11 Folder labelled "DL17/DL19(Cont) / Goodman 25.7.67"
DL19 Side 2 End. pp.1-25

4.12 Folder labelled "DL18 / Hajek 15 / Petrovik 21 / 27.7.67 pp.15-32

4.13 Folder labelled "DL19/DL15 / Beck / 21.7.67 1st page headed Note DL19 Side 1. pp.1-21 "Living Theatre"

4.14 Folder labelled DL16 / Ginsberg / 27.7.67" Allen Ginsberg & Simon Vinkanoog pp.1-20 4.15

Folder labelled "DL20 / Aage Nielson 1st page headed pp.1-7 & 1-12 "Anti institution"

4.16 Folder labelled "DL21 / Lucien Goldman" Text in French & pp.1-23 English. Short intro. in English by Marcuse

4.17 Folder labelled "DL19(Part) / Simon Vinkanoog / Note: see also 15, 17 / Reflection of Liberation" pp.1-7

4.18 Folder labelled "DL22 / Thich Nat Han / 17.7.67 pp.1-12

4.19 Folder labelled "Berke / 25.7.67 / The Possibilities of Revolutionary Change in Post Capitalist Western Societies: or What are We To Do?" pp.1-22

4.20 Loose notes. Paul Goodman 25.7.67. pp26-45

4.21 Stapled notes headed "Congress; Stokely Carmichael 18.7.67. pp/22-33

4.22 Stapled notes headed "Petrovic" pp.2-32

4.23 Loose notes headed "Stokely Carmichael - Sunday 23rd July 1967" pp.SC2 - 41-57 4.24

Loose notes headed "Stokely Carmichael - Sunday 23rd July, 1967" pp.SC2 1 - SC2 15

4.25 Stapled notes headed "Allen Ginsberg - 27th July 1967. 5.30 p.m. Suggested title: "Consciousness and Practical Action" DL6" pp.1-18

4.26 Stapled notes headed "Congress - Stokely Carmichael 18.7.67 / Discussion" pp. SC22-34

4.27 Stapled notes headed "Lecturer - R.D. Laing / Date 15.7.67" pp.1-6

4.28 Stapled notes, headed "Congress - 22nd July 1967 Discussion" pp. 22/7 - 11 to 22/7 - 22.

(Mostly duplicates of 4.10)

4.29 Stapled notes headed "Stokely Carmichael - Sunday 23rd July 1967" pp SC2 -41 -56

(Mostly duplicates of 4.23)

4.30 Loose notes headed "Discussion - 13; Stokely One page only Carmichael" pp.SC2 - 57 (Rest missing)

4.31 Loose notes headed "Stokely Carmichael - 18th 2 copies of page July 1967" pp SC1 - 33. Includes transcript 32 of Press Conference (pp 32-33)

4.32 Manila folder labelled "Panel discussion / Bateson, Goodman, Speck, Huxley, Eng, Laing / 17.7.67" pp.1-27

4.33 Manila folder labelled "Marcuse / 28.7.67" pp. 1-16

Box 5

5.9 File: "Liberation Record - Brochures and Order Forms"

5.10 File: "John Cassidy - Intersound Correspondence" 1969-1970

5.14 File: "Possible Distributors - Distribution - Terms" 1969

5.16 File: "Intersound Liberation Records Monthly Statements" 1969-1975

5.17 File: "Record Manufacturers" 1968-1972

5.18 Envelope: Intersound Records, Tax matters 1972

5.19 File: "BBC" 1968-1969

5.20 Loose: Order forms [for disks]

5.22 Envelope: "Liberation Records. Correspondence etc." 1971-1972

5.23 File: "Sales - Direct Possible Sales" 1969-1970

5.24 Loose: Correspondence and miscellaneous concerning records 1969-1970

5.25[1] Manila Folder: "Brief Account of Dialectics of Liberation Congress, Speakers & Institute of Phenomenological Studies"

5.26[2] I.Kon Magazine; Vol 1 No. 4; October 26th 1967; ed. Susan Sherman. Includes articles - "Dialectics of Liberation, A Conference" by S. Sherman. pp. 4-7 inclusive, with photos.

5.26[3] New Society Journal (newsheet) No. 253, 34rd. August 1967, London. Includes article "Round House Dialectics" by Roger Barnard. pp.145-147 2 copies.

Box 6

6 Posters for Congress

6.1 Posters for Dialectics of Liberation Congress (A3 and A1 size)

Unboxed

10 A set of grey "Challenge Filing and Storage Case" holders. Mainly correspondence and materials relating to Dialectics of Liberation Conference.

10.1 "Cor on Individuals. A to E inc."

10.2 "Cor. Indvs. cont. F/K inc."

10.3 "Ind Corr L/Sh"

10.4 "Ind. Corr. SH/Z"

10.5 "Corr Re Book Records Film etc."

- a. Prospective publishers
- b. Publicity
- c. Recording cos.
- d. TV and Radio
- e. Enquiries re Tapes, Books, etc.

10.6 "Corr with Inds. Filed in Countries"

11 Books/Pamphlets

Marcuse, Carmichel, Laing m. fl. FRIG RELESENS DIALEKTIK. Oversat af Ole Stig Andersen, Bibliotek Rhodos (Denmark) 1969

R.D. Laing et al., BEFRIESENS DIALEKTIK, Redigerad av David Cooper, Bef rlaget Pan/Norstedts (Stockholm), 1970

Gregory Bateson et al, DIAL CTICA DA LIBERTA O, Organizado por David Cooper, Zahar Editores (Rio De Janeiro), 1968

Stokeley Carmichael and Herbert Marcuse, THE DIALECTICS OF LIBERATION, edited with Notes by Kimiyoshi Yura, The Eihosha Ltd (Tokyo) 1970

Gajo Petrovic, "The Dialectics of Liberation", PRAXIS: Revue Philosophique 4 (1967), 606-613 [off-print]

12 Film: "Dialectics of Liberation". 16mm.

13 Video Cassette: "Dialectics of Liberation July 1967 on Violence".
JVC PRO Video Cassette

14 Reel to reel tape: Stokeley Carmichael, "Black Power", published in Japan by The Eiosha Ltd. (Tokyo).

(V)PP/JB/IPS

Videos which form a part of the personal papers of Dr Joseph Berke which relate to the Institute of Phenomenological Studies

(F)PP/JB/IPS1 16mm " Dialectics of Liberation" (on box)

(V)PP/JB/IPS2 JVC VHS 'DYNAREC' " Dialectics of Liberation July 1967 on violence" (V)PP/JB/IPS2 VHS copy

(P)PP/JB/IPS

Part of the collection PP/JB/IPS

Photographs given by Dr Joseph Berke which relate to the Institute of Phenomenological Studies

Box marked 'Names of participants on the back of one of three copies. Photographs - Dialectics of Liberation. Deborah Rogers. 29 Goodge street WI. from John Haynes. 24, Antrim Mansions, Anrtim Rd. NW3'

(P)PP/JB/IPS 1 Photographs of the Dialectics of Liberation Conference

1.14 Thich Nhat Hahn , 3 copies , 1.15 Ross Speck , 3 copies , 1.16 Stokely Carmichael , 3 copies , 1.17 Stokely Carmichael , 2 copies , 1.18 John Gerassi, 3 copies , 1.19 Jules Henry 3 copies , 1.20 Herbert Marcuse 3 copies , 1.21 R D Laing , 1 copy , 1.22 Allen Ginsberg 2 copies , 1.23 Paul Goodman 3 copies , 1.24 Julian Beck 2 copies , 1.25 Gregory Bateson 3 copies

Annex B

DOCUMENTATION:

This document was created by Natascha Naumann in 2022 from the PP-JB-IPS-Tapes.doc file, typos as in original. Changes to the original document: change of font and font size; the paragraph distance between the log entries was reduced to one pilcrow to save space for printing; the entries in the original listed ALL the tapes in the estate, this list contains only the tapes related to the Dialectics of Liberation Congress

1995.8/1Institute of Phenomenological Studies Archives, Reel to Reel Tape Recordings, Initial List

Please note: Unless otherwise stated, apart from the accession number and remarks on the condition of the tape, all the information given below comes from the tape boxes and may or may not match the tape in the box or its contents. This latter information will come as the tapes themselves are copied and processed. The contents are taken verbatim from box unless otherwise noted.

accession Number	Tape length	Manufacturer/ make
Reel size	Tape material	Condition

1	Reel to Reel Tapes in Tape Box 1	
1.12	7" 1800'	Scotch 150 white spotting
	(Typed label on box:), Intersound Recordings CBS , Title David Cooper - Beyond Words - DL3 Side B, Scroll (Blue leader) 15'55", Duration 26 mins --secs , Start White End Orange leader, Language English, Ref No. DL3/CB/4, 7 1/2 ins/sec CC1R	

- 1.13 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty
Congress Master, July 27th, Public Address, G. Petrovicz - Editor Praxis (Yugoslavia),
and ?? Hajek? (Czechoslovakia), Tracks 2 + 4 (Transcribed), Track 2 - Petrovicz - 1250
- 1.14 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty
Tape 2 Master, Congress July 20th, John Gerassi, Public Address, Track I - doubled recording of
part of Question Time, - matches Track 4 on Tape Box marked Y', Track 2 blank
- 1.15 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very bad
Tape 'X', Congress July 20th Master, John Gerassi, Public Address, Track 1 First part
Public Address, Track 3 Last part of Address - Question 1 -
- 1.16 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very bad
Master [copy to 3 3/4 for transcription, Congress, July 25th 1967, 10.30 a.m., Paul Goodman
(transcribed), Tracks 2 + 4
- 1.17 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very bad
7 1/2 ips, Master [No transcription tape - copy from master to 3 3/4 before transcribing],
Congress, July 25th 1967, 10.30 a.m., Paul Goodman, Tracks 1 + 3 (Transcribed)
- 1.18 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Bad
Splices, Master 7 1/2 ips, Congress Friday 21st July 1967, 10.30 a.m., Paul Sweezy, The Future
of Capitalism, Track 1, " 3
- 1.19 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Spots, Congress July 24th Master,
10.30 a.m., Ross Speck etc. Public Address, Tracks 2 + 4
- 1.20 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Poor (Spotting)
Congress July 24th Master, 10.30 am, Ross Speck } Public Address { Jules Henry etc. David
Cooper}, Tracks 1 + 3
- 1.21 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175
?, Master Tape, Stokeley Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July, Track 6, Changed for K', Carmichael
questions - [], altogether about 20 mins
- 2
Reel to Reel Tapes in Tape Box 2
- 2.2 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 fur spots/splices
Master 7 1/2 IPS, Congress Friday 21st July 1967, 10 30 a.m., Paul Sweezy, The future of
Capitalism, Track 2, " 4
- 2.3 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 fur spots
Starts with A.G. rewind [?], Inter Sound S, Title Anti Institution Seminar DL20 Side
B, 997 Duration 26 mins 30 secs., Start Yellow Leader, 118 Scroll 3'10" green, End Blue leader,
Recorded at 7 1/2 ins./sec 1/2 track C.C.I.R.
- 2.4 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
OK rewind , 722-1888, DL 23 Side B., Spoken Word Only, Mono, 7 1/2 ips 30'00", 1/2 Track
- 2.5 7" EMItape 883/12 some fur
Intersound Recordings Ltd., 20 Fitzroy Sq. London W.1, DL 19 Side A, Speech Only, 7 1/2 IPS
Scroll: 18' 0", : 24' 20", 1/2 Track End: 29' 20"
- 2.6 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 furry
[Mono] 7 1/2 IPS, ((Copy to 3 3/4 for Transcription)), Congress Master, July 25th '67, 10.30 a.m.,
Paul Goodman, Track 5 Transcribed
- 2.7 7" EMItape 883/12 fur spots
DL23 Side A, Spoken Word Only, Mono, 7 1/2 IPS 31'.00", 1/2 Track
- 2.8 7" EMItape 883/12 not too bad
DL5 Side 2 7 1/2 IPS, Speech Only 1/2 track Mono, Scroll At : 7m 45s, Scroll At : 18m 40s, End
: 27m 30s
- 2.9 7" EMItape 883/12 fur spots
Intersound Recordings Ltd., 20 Fitzroy Sq. London, W.1, DL 12 Side A, Speech 7 1/2 IPS, Mono
1/2 Track, Ends 32 Min.
- 2.10 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 fur spots
Intersound, Master, Title Herbert Marcuse - Affluent Society - DL11 - Side A, 1045 Duration 28
mins - secs., Start Yellow Leader, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 ins/sec, 1/2 track C.C.I.R. MB
- 2.11 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 very furry
Intersound Records, Master, Title Herbert Marcuse (Continuation) DL9 Side A, (1125) Duration
30 mins - secs., Start Yellow Leader, (426') Scroll At 11'26" (Blue Leader), End Red Leader,
Recorded at 7 1/2 ins./sec. 1/2 track. C.C.I.R.
- 2.12 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very furry
7 1/2 IPS, Master, Congress, Stokely Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July 1967, 370 m, Tracks II & IV
- Carmichael continue, - total length of speech 62 min, track 2 white - 370 in - Stokely Car, or 100
back from red []

- 2.13 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 Not too bad
Intersound, Master, Title Herbert Marcuse - Affluent Society - DL11 - Side B, (950') Duration 25 mins 30 secs., Start Yellow Leader, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 ins./sec. 1/2 track C.C.I.R.
- 2.14 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Not too bad,
[Mono] 3 3/4 IPS, Congress Transcription, July 25th, 3 p.m., Anti-Institutions - Free University of Berlin/ Provosts/ New Exptl. College, Free [University] of N.Y./ Internationalists/ Centre, Tracks 1 & 2 S.F. Communities (Ginsberg)/ etc.[more detailed notes]
- 2.15 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very furry
[Mono] 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 19th Master, Public Address, Jules Henry, Tracks 2 & 4, Track 2 Second Part of Address & Question , Time beginning, Track 4 Blank
- 2.16 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 furry, 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 19th, Public Address, Jules Henry, Tracks 1 & 3, Track 1 First part of address, Track 3 Most of Question Time (not beginning)
- 2.17 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 furry
- 2.18 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 Not too bad,
[Mono] 7 1/2 IPS, Carmichael, 23rd July, Lecture III 0266', Edmundo des Noyes 073', Questions I 0636', Not used, Bob Woolford Sound
- 2.19 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 Not bad,
[Mono] 7 1/2 IPS, Carmichael, 23rd July, Questions II o564', Not Used, Bob Woolford Sound
- 2.20 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Not too bad, 7 1/2 IPS,
Master, Stokeley Carmichael Congress, Sunday 23rd July, Track I & III - red, - Carmichael continued, whole side, Laing/Carmichael/Ginsberg/Cooper/ E. Grogan, Tracks 2 & 4
- 2.27 7" Emitape Some dirt, July 22 - Sat night, Emmett Grogan, 5 1/2 min, 7 1/2
- 2.28 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty, [Mono] (2) 17 Jly 7 1/2 IPS, Congress Master, Gregory Bateson, July 17th, Tracks 2 and 4 Some slight spluttering & mic position variation on Track 2 (Second-half of Dr. Bateson's Address) , - Use 3 3/4" tape, Track 2 - Second 1/2 of address, Track 4 - Second part of questions, Transcribed - As D
- 2.29 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty, [Mono] 7 1/2 IPS,
Congress Master, Saturday July 22, 8 p.m., Laing/Carmichael/Ginsberg/Cooper/E. Grogan, Track 5, Track 6 blank.
- 2.30 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty, [Mono] 7 1/2 IPS,
Congress Master, Saturday July 22, 8 p.m., Laing/Carmichael/Ginsberg/Cooper/E. Grogan, Tracks I & 3, 3 Reel to Reel Tapes in
- Tape Box 3
- 3.1 7" EMItape 883/12 good
Beck rewind, Intersound Recordings Ltd., DL 19 Side B, Speech, End at 24'40", 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track
- 3.2 7" EMItape OK
Tape 1, Thich Nhat Han
- 3.3 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty, 7 1/2 IPS, Master,
Congress 26th July 1967, 10.30 a.m.
- 3.8 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 spotty
20 Fitzroy Sq., London, W.1, Title DL1 Side B, Duration 27 mins. - secs., Language English, Speech Only, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track mono
- 3.9 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 Spotty
DL22 Mono Fulltrack, Thich Nhat Hanh Side 2, Dialectics of Liberation Congress, Round House Chalk Farm, July 17th 1967, [Edited], Bob Woolford, Sound
- 3.10 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch Spots
3 3/4 IPS, Congress 19-7-67 Unused material, Film -, Discussion "Challenge" "Challenge seminar", Bateson, Track 2 (Transcribed), 4, St. N.W.1., Bob Woolford Sound -- the situation is tightly structured
- 3.12 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 1 spot, Dl 21, Mono OK 7 1/2 IPS,
Goldmann, 26 July, Lecture I 1019', Side , 27 1/2 min ok, Bob Woolford Sound
- 3.13 7" Blank spot
- 3.14 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 1 spot
DL23 Edited, Sides 1 & 2 Orig 3 3/4, 19-7-67 Congress Still to be dubbed, Film - and levelled, Discussion on "Challenge", Bateson, Track 1 (transcribed), 4, St. George's Terr. N.W. 1
- 3.15 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK

- Intersound, Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - To Congress - DL6 - Side B, (1150') Duration 30 mins 30 secs, Start Yellow, No Scroll, End Blue, 7 1/2 1/2 track
- 3.16 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK
- Intersound, Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - To Congress - DL6 - Side A, (1050') Duration 28 mins - secs, Start Yellow Leader, No Scrolls, End Orange, 7 1/2 1/2 track
- 3.17 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK
- Mono Q 7.5, DL18, Title a) Petrovic & Hajek, - major excerpt
- 3.18 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- Intersound Recordings Ltd., DL12 Side B, Mono 1/2 track, Speech 7 1/2 IPS, Scroll 19 1/2 min, End 30 min.
- 3.19 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL 16 Side B, Speech Only, Scroll: 18'20", End: 25' 30", 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track
- 3.20 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL8 Side 2, Ends 28 min
- 3.21 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL2 Side 1, Speech Only (English), Mono 1/2 track, 7 1/2 IPS Scroll at 6m30s, End 24m 15s
- 3.22 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL2 Side 2 7 1/2 IPS, Speech Only 1/2 track Mono, Scroll at: 14m 40s, Scroll at: 24 m -, End at : 31m 20s
- 3.23 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK
- Intersound, Master, Title Saturday Night DL13 Side B, Duration 28 mins - secs., Start Yellow, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track, level []
- 3.24 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 OK
- Mono 3 3/4, Congress Transcription, July 25th, 8.30 p.m., Joe Berke (transcribed), The Possibilities of Revolutionary Change in Post- Capitalist Western Societies or "What are We to Do?", Track I, (Speaker abandoned mic for discussion period)
- 3.25 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK
- Intersound, Master, Title Stokely Carmichael - Black Community - DL7 - Side B, (1215') Duration 32 mins 30 secs., Start White Leader, No Scroll, End Red, 7 1/2 1/2 track
- 3.26 7" EMItape 883/12 OK, DL16 Side A, Speech Only, End at 25' 10", 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track
- 3.27 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Spot
- 3 3/4 ips, Transcription, Congress, Poetry Thursday evening, 27th July 1967, Track I
- 3.28 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 spots
- Mono 7 1/2, Congress July 21 (Interruption blank, Evening 8 pm - power cut off), Allen Ginsberg & Friends, Songs (c) Copyright, The Institute of, Track I Phenomenological Studies [etc], May not be reproduced without written permission.
- 3.29 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Spots
- [taped to front:] Laing 15 July, [Back] Master 15 July '67, Congress, R.D. Laing, Tracks 1 & 3, Cooper, Use intro by Bateson for David - otherwise cut extraneous Bateson stuff, 1st part - David Cooper's intro
- 3.30 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 OK
- 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 21, Evening 8 pm, Allan Ginsberg and Friends, Songs (c) Copyright, Track 2
- 3.31 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 OK
- Mono 7 1/2 IPS, Congress Master, Gregory Bateson, July 17th, Tracks 1 and 3, Track 1 - First Half of Address } Transcribed, Track 3 - Floor Questions } ASD
- 3.32 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Spots
- Mono 3 3/4, Congress, July 17th evening, Thich Nat Han & Poet (transcribed), Track 1 of I 3 3/4"/sec , include poem read in Vietnamese
- 3.33 7" 1800' 1 mil Mylar Robins brand 5 OK
- Intersound Records, Title Julien Beck - Money Sex & The Theatre - Side A, DL 15, 902 Duration 24 mins - secs., Start Green, No scroll, End Orange, 7 1/2 1/2 track
- 3.34 7" 1800' 1 mil Mylar Robins brand 5 OK
- Intersound Records, Title Julian Beck - Money Sex & The Theatre - Side B, DL 15, 902 Duration 24 mins - secs., Start Green, No scroll, End Orange, 7 1/2 1/2 track
- 3.35 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL17 Side B, Speech 7 1/2 IPS, 1/2 track, End at: 28'00
- 3.36 7" EMItape 883/12 OK
- DL10 Side A, Ends 27 min.
- 3.37 7" EMItape 883/12 small spot

- DL5 Side A, Spoken Word Only (English), Mono, 7 1/2 IPS End at 31'00", 1/2 track
- 3.38 7" EMItape 883/12 spots, DL8 Side 1, Ends 27 min
- 3.39 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 OK, Mono 3 3/4, Congress July 20th (transcription), Evening 7 p.m. C.L.R. James, The Dialectical Relationship Between the Proletariat of the Advanced & the Peasants of the Underdeveloped Nations., Track 3 Beginning.
- 3.40 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 OK 3 3/4, Congress July 20th (transcription), Evening 7 p.m., David Horowitz, Nationalism in the Middle East, Tracks 2 - Talk & Discussion continued (transcribed), 8.30 p.m. C.L.R. James, The Dialectical Relationship Between the Proletariat of the Advanced & the Peasants of the Underdeveloped Nations (Cont), Track 4. End.
- 3.41 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Ronald Laing - The Obvious - DL4 - Side B, Mono Speech, 1078 Duration 28 mins 45 secs., No scrolls, Start White Leader, End Orange, Ref. No.
- 3.42 7" EMItape 883/12 OK DL10 Side B, Ends 27 min
- 3.43 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 Spots Master 15 Jly '67, Congress, R.D. Laing, Tracks 2 & 4, 3.44 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty, (3) 17 JI 3 3/4 IPS, Congress Transcription, July 17th, Afternoon - , Panel Discussion (Bateson), Track I - First Half of Discussion (transcribed)
- 3.45 7" no box OK, Laing III & Q, Not used Laing Questions,
- 4 Reel to Reel Tapes in Tape Box 4
- 4.1 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 very spotty Mono 3 3/4, Congress Transcription (1), July 28th, Herbert Marcuse Public Address (transcribed), Track I - Continued on 5" reel.
- 4.2 5" 1200' tensilized New Universal OK Polyester Electronics 3TD5 3 3/4, Transcription, (2), Congress, July 28th, Public Address Herbert Marcuse (transcribed), Track I - continued from 7" reel
- 4.3 5" 600' Gevasonor OK Congress July 20th, John Gerassi Public Address, Question Time - rest of(transcription) Second tape transcribed
- 4.4 5" 1800' 0.5 mil tensilized Ferrodynamics OK Polyester Brand 5 Congress July 18th (3 3/4), Stokeley Carmichael, Panel Discussion - Afternoon, Track I (track 2 blank), John Gerassi, CLR James, George Pavick[?], David Cooper, including 1 minute silence for John Coltrane, (transcription)
- 4.5 5" 1800' 0.5 mil tensilized Ferrodynamics OK Polyester Brand 5 Congress Transcription, Gregory Bateson July 17th, Tracks 1 & 2, Track 1 - Address (3 3/4), Track 2 - Questions, (transcribed), Broadcast tape, Use from about 1000', Master tape
- 4.6 5" 1800' Polyester New International OK Electronics RT555, 3 3/4, Transcription , Congress July 26, Ross Speck etc. Public Address, Tracks I & 2 (transcribed)
- 4.7 5" 1800' Polyester New International OK Electronics RT555 (transcribed), Julian Beck, Living Theatre, Friday 21st July, 3 3/4 "/sec, J. Beck
- 4.8 5" EMItape 811/6 OK DLR, end of someone
- 4.9 5" 1200' tensilized New Universal OK Polyester Electronics 3TD5, 3 3/4, Transcription, Congress, July 26th. 10.30 a.m., Lucien Goldmann, Questions Only - Address transcription, tape taken by Helen
- 4.10 5" 1800' 0.5 mil tensilized Ferrodynamics OK Polyester Brand 5 Congress July 18th (3 3/4), Stokeley Carmichael, Public Address & Floor Questions & Press Conference, Tracks 1 & 2, (transcription), (transcribed ASD)
- 4.11 5" 1800' Polyester New International OK Electronics RT555

	Transcription tape., Congress - Friday 21st July, 1967, Paul Sweezy, The Future of Capitalism, Tracks 1 & 2, Transcribed				
4.12	5"	1200'	tensilized	New Universal	OK
	Polyester Electronics 3TD5				
	3 3/4, Transcription, Congress, July 27th, 10.30 Public Address, G. Petrovicz - "Praxis" - (first 5 minutes lost - tape recorder breakdown), Is on Master, and ?? Hajek? (Czech), Track 1 - Addresses (with first 5? mins. lost), Track 2 - Questions (Track 2 begins some way in but is complete)				
4.13	5"	1800'	0.5 mil tensilized	Ferrodynamics	OK
	Polyester Brand 5, Congress July 19 (3 3/4), Jules Henry, Public Address & Question Time, *Transcribe only question time [because] lecture was written and read., Transcription, Track 1 Public Address & Question Time, Track 2 July 20th. John Gerassi, Public Address & Question Time ([] on Gevasonor tape), (Transcription), Transcribed				
4.14	5"			EMItape	Some spotting
	Title Goldman, Unused 8 mins, End of Question Period, French/Eng				
4.16	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	very spotty
	[Mono] 7 1/2 IPS, TAPE Y, Congress July 20th Master, John Gerassi, Public Address, Track 2 Second part - Public Address, Track 4 Second part of Questions - some speed variation part of this track is also recorded on Track 1 of Tape Box marked 2, Speed changes, see other tape				
4.17	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	very spotty
	7 1/2 IPS, MASTER, Stokley Carmichael, Sunday 23rd July, Track V, Carmichael questions began about 325 in				
4.18	7"	1800'	Polyester	Scotch 150	Spots
	Intersound Recordings Ltd., Title DL1 Side A, Duration 24mins. 30 secs., Language English, Speech Only, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 Mono				
4.19	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	Spots
4.20	7"	1800'	Polyester	Scotch 150	Spots
	Intersound, Title Anti Institution Seminar - DL20 - Side A, Duration 26 mins 40 secs, Start Yellow, (orange) scroll : 6'20"; 11'0"; 16'0"; 19'30", End Green, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track				
4.21	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	not too bad
	Tape for transcript Transcribed – ASD, R.D. Laing - 15 Jly				
4.22	7"			EMItape	dirty - Spots?
	Not used, Sweezy Discussion				
4.23	7"			Scotch	dirty
	Goodman Questions Not Used				
4.24	7"			EMItape	dirty
	Not used [Gerassi?]				
4.25	7"			EMItape	dirty
	Not Used Discussion Petrovic				
4.26	5"			EMItape	dirty
	NO LABELS				
4.27	5"			EMItape	dirty
	Cuts from []				
4.28	5"	1800'	Polyester	New International	OK
	Electronics RT555, Congress 3 3/4, Saturday July 22nd Transcription, 8 p.m., Laing/Carmichael/Ginsberg/Cooper/E. Brogan, Tracks 1 + 2, Transcribed				
4.34	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	dirty/fungal
	Mono 7 1/2 IPS, Congress July 18th, Stokeley Carmichael, Public Address, Tracks 1 & 3, Track 1 First Half of Address (white) 32 minutes, Track 3 Questions from floor (red)				
4.35	7"	1800'	Polyester	Scotch 150	spotty
	Mono 7 1/2 IPS, Carmichael, 18 July, Questions 1083, NOT USED, Bob Woolford Sound				
4.36	7"			EMItape 883/12	some fungus
	DL17 Side A, Speech, 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 track, End at 26'40"				
4.37	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	Spot
	3 3/4, Transcription, Congress, Poetry Thursday evening, 27th July 1967, Track II				
4.38	7"	1800'	Polyester	Scotch 150	spotty
	Intersound Records, Master, Title John Gerassi (Continuation) DL9 Side B, (1092') Duration 29mins 30 secs., No, Scroll, Start white leader, End orange, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track				
4.39	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	spotty
	7 1/2 ips, Master, Congress 26th July 1967, 7.30 p.m., Poetry reading & lectures, Track 1 - Lecture - C.S.R. James - Poetry - John Lerosé, Track 3 Andrew Sackey (Poetry) - Ted Jones Poetry				
4.40	7"	1200'	Polyester	Scotch 175	fungus

- 7 1/2 ips, Master, Congress July 26th 1967, 7.30 p.m., Poetry Reading & Lectures, Track 2 Elwyn
? Jones (Poetry) - Andrew Salkey (Poetry), Track 4 - Andrew Salkey (Poetry)
- 4.41 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 fungus
[Mono] 7 1/2 ips, Congress, June 27, Allen Ginsberg, Track 2 - Ginsberg & Simon Winkemer's
paper, 4 Not worth transcribing
- 4.42 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 some spot
- 4.43 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 some spots
[Mono] 7 1/2 ips, Congress July 18th Master, Stokeley Carmichael, John Gerassi, C.L.R. James,
George Rawick, David Cooper, Panel Discussion - Afternoon, Track I First Half Discussion,
Track III Last part of Discussion
- 4.44 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 spotty
[Mono] 7 1/2 ips, Congress July 18th Master, Stokeley Carmichael, Panel Discussion - Afternoon,
Track 2 Second Half of Discussion - not to the end, Track 4 blank
- 4.45 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 spotty
[Mono] 3 3/4ips, 8 pm Tues 18th July, Prof. Owen (Listen before transcription), Side I & II
- 4.46 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 spotty
Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Saturday Night DL14 Side A, 1037 Duration 27 mins 40
secs., Start yellow, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track,
- 4.47 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 OK
Intersound Recordings
Master, Title Ronald Laing - The Obvious - DL4 - Side A, Mono Speech, (1080') Duration 29
mins 20 secs, No scrolls, start white leader, end orange, DL4/CB/81, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track
- 4.48 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 some spots
Intersound, Master, Title Saturday Night - DL13 Side A, 773' Duration 20 mins 40 secs., Start
yellow, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track
- 4.49 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 spottiness
Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Stokeley Carmichael - Black Community - DL7 - Side A,
1180 Duration 31 mins 20 secs, start yellow leader, no scroll, end red, 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track
- 4.50 7" 1800' Polyester Scotch 150 spots/dirt
Intersound Recordings, Master, Title Saturday Night DL14 Side B, 1225 Duration 32 mins. 50
secs., Start yellow, no scroll, end blue , 7 1/2 ips 1/2 track
- 4.51 7" 1200' Polyester Scotch 175 spotty
[Mono] 7 1/2 ips, Congress Master, July 27th, Public Address, G. Petrovic - Editor Praxis
(Yugoslavia) and ?? Hajek (Czechoslovakia), Tracks 1&3 (transcribed),

Annex C

DOCUMENTATION:

This document was created by Natascha Naumann in 2022 from the PETT FOLDER.txt file. Changes to the original document:

Conversion from txt file to docx file; change of font and font size; the distance between the log entries was eliminated (in the original it was up to five pilcrows); the information in the original entries was separated into lines by pilcrows or tabstops, this was changed to separation by comma to save space for printing and facilitate transfer to the dataframes; the log entries used to create the column PETT_FOLDER_1 in the pandas dataframes in Natascha Naumann's research were set to lower case letters except for the first letters of names, the symbol “ was changed to the word *inch*.

TAPE TRANSFER LOG

PLAYED BACK ON SONY APR 5003 WITH MODIFIED 1/4 TRACK HEADBLOCK AND FULL TRACK MONO HEAD-BLOCK ALIGNED TO MRL CALIBRATION TAPES FOR SUITABLE SPEEDS 4.75 CM/SEC IS 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB REDUCED BY 50% AND ADJUSTED BY EAR 9.5 CM/SEC: IEC&NAB EQUALISATION 19 CM/SEC: IEC 1 EQUALISATION DAW 1 LOG (1 OF 2 LOGS CREATED USING 2 SYSTEMS)

DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST, ARCHIVE LOG NOTES, PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST

1.1.12 DAVID COOPER: BEYOND WORDS CONGRESS 1967 OPEN REEL HALF TRACK MONO OUTPUT IEC EQUALISATION 19 CM/SEC MICROPHONE CLIPPING AS SOURCE, REF: DL3/CB/4 TOTAL TIME: 00:26:08 1.1.14 CONGRESS 1967.07.20 JOHN GERASSI PUBLIC ADDRESS TRACK 1: 'DOUBLE RECORDING OF PART OF QUESTION TIME MATCHING TRACK 4 ON TAPE BOX MARKED Y' SCOTCH 175 POLYESTER 360M 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, HALF TRACK MONO SHORT PROGRAMME EXCERPT TIME: 00:20:14

1.1.15 JOHN GERASSI, PUBLIC ADDRESS 1967.07.20 CONGRESS INTRODUCTION BY PAUL SWEEZY SCOTCH OPEN REEL 1/4 INCH 19 CM/SEC IEC EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO 360M LENGTH POLYESTER ADDRESS AND Q+A SESSION

1.1.16 CONGRESS 1967.05.25 1030HRS PAUL GOODMAN, MASTER TRACKS 2 & 4, MASTER 19 CM/SEC, SCOTCH SP 175 HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL 7" BOX HAS SOME SIGN OF DECOMPOSITION, TAPE PLAYS BACK WELL. TRACK 1

1.1.17 PAUL GOODMAN DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967 5A CH1 HEX ON APR5003 IEC 1 EQ SCOTCH 175 POLYESTER 360M 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, CONTAINS TAPE NOISE, HALF TRACK MONO PAUL GOODMAN 1967.07.25 1030 HRS EXPERIMENTAL ASPECT OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

1.1.18 1967.07.21 PAUL SWEEZY: THE FUTURE OF CAPITALISM CONGRESS 1030 HRS MASTER 19 CM/SEC, SCOTCH SP 175 HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL 7" BOX HAS SOME SIGN OF DECOMPOSITION, TAPE PLAYS BACK WELL. TRACK 1

1.1.19_S1 & S2 CONGRESS 1967.07.24 DR ROSS SPECK, PUBLIC ADDRESS SCOTCH 175 POLYESTER 360M 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, CONTAINS TAPE NOISE, HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL BOTH SIDES ARE PRESENT ON THIS RECORDING COMMENTS AND REACTIONS TO STOKLEY CARMICHAEL MAN AS A DOG Q + A DR REDLER TIME: 00:49:40

1.1.20_S1 SIDE 2 STEREO 19 CM/SEC IEC EQUALISATION SCOTCH 360M OPEN REEL POLYESTER 175 SP 9MM WIDTH CONTAINS HUM AS SOURCE, 100 HZ HUM IS REMOVED PROGRAM: SPEAKER 1: DAVID COOPER PUBLIC ADDRESS SPEAKER 2: MURRAY KORNGOLD SPEAKER 3: (MC) CHILD AND TOY SPEAKER 4: JULES HENRY TIME: 00:31:56

PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST

1.2.2 PAUL SWEEZY, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.21 FRIDAY 1030 HRS, 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, QUARTER INCH 2 TRACK MONO SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER OPEN REEL, CLEANED FOR PLAYBACK WITH LEADERS ADDED, THE FUTURE OF CAPITALISM - MASTER, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT

1.2.4 DL23 SIDE B SPOKEN WORD ONLY, MONO 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ 1/2 TRACK MONO ON EMI TAPE IN RED BOX 18CM SPOOL, REEL: POETRY READING 18, IF THIS IS A COPY FROM DL23 SIDE B IT HAS BEEN DONE WRONG, WITH IMPEDENCE MIS-MATCH AS SOURCE, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT

1.2.7 ROY BATTERSBY, BBC CHALLENGE TV PROGRAMME 1967, 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, EMITAPE OPEN REEL 1/4 INCH, BOX: DL 23 SIDE A SPOKEN WORD ONLY MONO 7 1/2 IPS 1/2 TRACK 31.00, MAN'S INTERVENTIONS ON THE PLANET, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT

1.2.9 ECONOMIST PAUL SWEEZY, THE FUTURE OF CAPITALISM, EMITAPE PROFESSIONAL RED BOX, INTER-SOUND RECORDINGS PRODUCTION, DL12 SIDE A 19 CM/SEC 1/2 TRACK MONO POLYESTER 1/4 INCH OPEN REEL, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT,

1.2.12 Stokely Carmichael 1967.07.23 (Sunday) congress master 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 2 track mono scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present some writing undistinguishable in red ink on the box number 9 on plastic reel..

1.2.15 JULES HENRY, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.19, PUBLIC ADDRESS 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, QUARTER INCH 2 TRACK MONO SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER OPEN REEL, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT ON THE TAPE OUTER SURFACE, 'SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION FOR WAR', SECOND PART OF ADDRESS AND QUESTION TIME BEGINNING,

1.2.16 JULES HENRY, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.19, PUBLIC ADDRESS 19 CM/SEC IEC EQ, QUARTER INCH 2 TRACK MONO SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER OPEN REEL, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT ON THE TAPE OUTER SURFACE, 'SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION FOR WAR', THIS IS THE FIRST PART OF THE ADDRESS, WITH MOST OF THE QUESTION TIME, BUT MISSING THE BEGINNING, TOTAL TIME: 01:03:10

1.2.19 Stokely Carmichael 1967.07.23 questions ii 12.5 cm reel full track mono 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present hippies, exploitation of minority groups...

1.2.20 Stokely Carmichael, Roundhouse, Congress, London 1967.07.23 Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 2 track mono scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present the predicament coloured people are in...

1.2.25 DR BERKE, DR R D LAING RADIO BROADCAST AND COMMENT, EMITAPE IN PLAIN BOX, 14 CM REEL, HALF TRACK MONO IEC&NAB EQ 9.5 CM/SEC, DR BERKE: INTRODUCTION, DR LAING: VIOLENCE AND LOVE BROADCAST WBAI NEW YORK FOLLOWED, BY A SKETCH BY A FEMALE VOICE, PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST

1.2.26 Laing_Carmichael_Ginsberg_Cooper_E. Brogan 1967.07.22 2000 Hrs Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 1/2 track mono scotch 175 7 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present animated discussions, good audio...

1.2.29 Laing_Carmichael_Ginsberg_Cooper_E. Brogan 1967.07.22 2000 hrs Dialects of Liberation congress 1967 19 cm/sec iec eq, quarter inch 1/2 track mono scotch 175 inch polyester open reel required cleaning of mold and contaminants present 'track 5'....

1.3.1 JULIAN BECK, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.21, DL19 SIDE_B , 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO QUARTER INCH OPEN REEL ANALOGUE TAPE, EMITAPE 883/12 54194, 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVED, CONTAINS MANY REMOVED CLICKS AS SOURCE

1.3.3 LUCIAN GOLDMANN, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.26 1030 HRS, CRITICAL ATTITUDE AND DOGMATISM IN THE LITERARY, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO QUARTER INCH , SCOTCH 175 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVED

1.3.6 JOHN KAMPFNER, FAMILY SESSION IN SURGERY, DR JOSEPH BERKE, MR AND MRS KAMPFNER 1970.06.17 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, UNIVERSAL ELECTRONICS 3TL7 360M LENGTH 18CM REEL SIZE, QUARTER TRACK STEREO, PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST 1970.07.17

1.3.10 DISCUSSION ON THE FILM "CHALLENGE", 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, SCOTCH SP 175 ANALOGUE OPEN REEL TAPE 18 CM SPOOL HALF TRACK MONO, UNUSED MATERIAL WRITTEN ON BOX, AND DATED 1967.07.19 WITH BATESON, SOME EXTRAENOUS NOISES ARE CONTAINED WITH MICROPHONE PALCEMENT OFTEN OFF-AXIS. SOME AUDIBLE TAPE SLIP IS NOTICED AT TIMES WHICH APPEARS TO SETTLE DOWN AFTER ADJUSTMENT, PROBABLY BATTERY REPLACED., DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.3.13 GAYO PETROVIC, DL18 SIDE 1, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO QUARTER INCH OPEN REEL ANALOGUE TAPE, 18 CM POLYESTER REEL IN WHITE UNMARKED BOX, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVEDDUB EXCERPT FROM PETROVIC MASTER IN THE DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967 COLLECTION

1.3.16 Stokely Carmichael to Congress DL6-side A 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono quarter inch open reel analogue tape Scotch 175 18 cm polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present removed dub excerpt from Carmichael master Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967...

1.3.18 PAUL SWEEZY , FOREIGN INVESTMENT, DL12 SIDE_B HALF TRACK MONO, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO QUARTER INCH OPEN REEL ANALOGUE TAPE, EMITAPE 883/12 54194, 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVED, DUB EXCERPT FROM SWEEZY MASTER INTERSOUND RECORDINGS, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.3.22 MURRAY KORNGOLD, DL 2 SIDE 2, 1/2 TRACK MONO IEC1 EQUALISATION, EMITAPE 18CM OPEN REEL ANALOGUE QUARTER INCH, EMITAPE 883/12 BATCH 54203 18 CM REEL IN RED EMI PRODUCT BOX, CONTAINS EDITED EXTRACTS OF THE MASTER RECORDINGS FROM THE CONGRESS 1967

1.3.23, Saturday Night DL13 side B master from congress, two track stereo on quarter inch open reel, Scotch LP 150 18cm reel, iec1 equalisation (ccir) 19 cm/sec speed

1.3.25 Stokely Carmichael Black Community DL7 Side B Intersound master 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, from 1/2 track mono 1215 feet of tape Scotch LP 150 polyester Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967..

1.3.27 POETRY READING DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.27 EVENING THURSDAY

9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION CONFIGURED HALF TRACK MONO SCOTCH 175 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVED VARIOUS POETS READ

1.3.29 R D LAING INTRODUCED BY DAVID COOPER SCOTCH 175 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS 9 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO OUTPUT NOTES ON BOX: USE INTRO BY BATESON FOR DAVID - OTHERWISE CUT EXTRANEIOUS BATESON STUFF. 1ST PART - DAVID COOPER'S INTRO. TRACKS 1 & COOPER DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.15

1.3.30 ALLEN GINSBERG, ALLEN GINSBERG AND FRIENDS, SONGS (WITH COPYRIGHT APPLICABLE) 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO MASTER SCOTCH 175 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, KRISHNA CHANTS , DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.21 2000 hrs

1.3.31 GREGORY BATESON: CONCIIOUSNESS V NATURE, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.17, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION HALF TRACK MONO MASTER , SCOTCH 175 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT REMOVED, ROMAN, HEBREW, GREEK CIVILISATIONS, IMPERIALIST CIVILISATION YEASTED BY A DOWNTRODDED EXPLOITED COLONY IN PALESTINE ...

1.3.34 JULIAN BECK, MONEY, SEX AND THE THEATRE SIDE B DL 15, ROBINS BRAND FIVE OPEN REEL MYLAR QUARTER INCH RECORDED FULL TRACK MONO, IEC1 EQUALISATION, 19 CM/SEC PLAYBACK FROM SONY APR 5003 ANALOGUE OPEN REEL RECORDER., DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, EXTRA NOISE INDUCED FROM SECOND GENERATION

1.3.35 PAUL GOODMAN DL 17 SIDE B DUB, INTERSOUND RECORDINGS 20 FITZROY ST LONDON W1 , CM/SEC IEC1 EQ 1/2 TRACK MONO EMITAPE 883/12 BATCH 54203 18 CM REEL, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.3.39 DAVID HOROWITZ, NATIONALISM IN THE MIDDLE EAST 1600 HRS, 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL QUARTER INCH TAPE, SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, 2030HRS., CL LR JAMES, THE DIALECTICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PROLETERIATE OF THE ADVANCED AND THE PRESENT, OF THE UNDERDEVELOPED NATIONS

1.3.40 DAVID HOROWITZ, NATIONALISM IN THE MIDDLE EAST , CONTINUED, 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL QUARTER INCH TAPE, SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, 2030HRS., CL LR JAMES, THE DIALECTICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PROLETERIATE OF THE ADVANCED AND THE PRESENT, OF THE UNDERDEVELOPED NATIONS

1.3.42 JULES HENRY, DL10 SIDE B, EMITAPE 883/12 BATCH 54203 18 CM SPOOL NEEDING CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS, INTERSOUND RECORDINGS LTD DUB FROM MASTER, 19 CM/SEC IEC EQUALISATION FULL TRACK MONO OPEN REEL, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.3.44 PANEL., PAUL GOODMAN, HUXLEY, , DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.17 PM

1.3.43 R D LAING_PUBLIC ADDRESS, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.15, MASTER RECORDING ON SCOTCH 175 18CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES. 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO

1.4.1 HERBERT MARCUSE, PUBLIC ADDRESS, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.28, MASTER RECORDING ON SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES. TAPE SPEED 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, ON BOX: TRANSCRIPTION 1, ENDING AS SOURCE

1.4.3 JOHN GERASSI, PUBLIC ADDRESS 1967.07.20, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967 SECOND TAPE RECORDED ON GEVAERT GEVASONOR 8CM OPEN REEL AT SPEED OF 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION HALF TRACK MONO, SIDE 1: JOHN GERASSI PUBLIC ADDRESS, SIDE 2: BEGINS WITH SOME CLASSICAL MUSIC RECORDED AS MONO WITH SOME INTERFERENCE , LABEL ON REVERSE READS CONROY, BERRY MUSIC CO LTD MUSIC ALL MUSIC SOURCE COPIED FROM THIRD PROGRAMME BROADCAST

1.4.5 GREGORY BATESON, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.17, SIDE 1: ADDRESS, SIDE 2: QUESTIONS, GEVAERT GEVASONOR 8CM OPEN REEL AT SPEED OF 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION HALF TRACK MONO, BROADCAST TAPE, TRANSCRIPTION AND TRANSCRIBED. MASTER TAPE SCRIBLED ON THE BOX SPINE, REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES.STARTS AND ENDS AS SOURCE

1.4.6 DR ROSS SPECK, DR. JULES HENRY, PUBLIC ADDRESS, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.26, 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO OPEN REEL ANALOGUE AUDIO TAPE, NEW INTERNATIONAL ELECTRONICS RT 555 360M POLYESTER PURPLE BOX REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES, SINGLE FILE SRC TO 48 KHZ BECAUSE OF SIZE

1.4.9 LUCIEN GOLDMAN, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.26 1030 HRS, QUESTIONS ONLY, ADDRESS AND TRANSCRIPTION TAPE (TAKEN BY HELEN), 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO OPEN 13CM REEL, CONTAINS HUM AS SOURCE, NEW UNIVERSAL ELECTRONICS 3TD5 BLUE BOX TENSILIZED POLYESTER WITH GOOD OUTPUT. HUM HAS BEEN REMOVED FOR PROGRAMME CONTINUITY. START AS SOURCE

1.4.11 PAUL SWEEZY: THE FUTURE OF CAPITALISM, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.21 FRIDAY, 13CM NEW INTERNATIONAL ELECTRONICS RT 555 360M POLYESTER OPEN REEL TAPE RUNNING AT 9.5 CM/SEC USING IEC1 EQUALISATION CONFIGURED AS HALF TRACK MONO OUTPUT, BEGINNING AND END AS SOURCE.

1.4.14 LUCIEN GOLDMAN (FRENCH/ENGLISH DIALOGUE), END OF QUESTION PERIOD (NOT SPECIFIED), EMITAPE 12CM OPEN REEL FULL TRACK MONO POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES. EXCERPT THAT ENDS AS SOURCE, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.16 JOHN GERASSI (2/2), PUBLIC ADDRESS CONTINUED, SCOTCH SP 175 360M 18CM REEL 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION QUARTER INCH TAPE NEEDING CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS, MONO HALF TRACK MASTER RECORDING , LATIN AMERICANS - ALTERNATIVES TO EDUCATION - DIGGERS/HIPPIES AS ALLIES - MINUTE MINORITIES, BEGINS WITH 2ND PART OF THE PUBLIC ADDRESS - TAPE Y, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967.07.20, , THERE ARE NOTES ON THE BOX INDICATING SPEED FLUCTUATIONS - PART OF THIS TRACK (SIDE 2) IS ALSO RECORDED ON TR 1 OF TAPE BOX 2

1.4.18 GREGORY BATESON, DL1 SIDE A MONO FULL TRACK COPY, INTERSOUND RECORDINGS DUB, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO, SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.20 ANTI INSTITUTION SEMINAR DL20 SIDE A, INTERSOUND RECORDINGS DUB, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO COPY, SCOTCH 150 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES, THE PROVO MOVEMENT, AMSTERDAM, AMERICAN SOCIETY, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.25 RUSSIAN AND CHINESE CULT OF PERSONALITIES, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO COPY FROM MASTER NO CASE, SCOTCH 18CM OPEN REEL FULL TRACK MONO POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES. 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO COPY LEADERS ADDED BOTH ENDS, REPACKED FROM TAIL OUT

1.4.26 OPEN REEL NO CONTAINER OR NOTES, GERMAN SPEAKER IN AN EXCERPT, WEST GERMAN ENSLAVEMENT AND LIBERATION

EMITAPE 12CM OPEN REEL FULL TRACK MONO POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES. 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO COPY LEADERS ADDED BOTH ENDS, REPACKED FROM TAIL OUT, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.28 Laing, Carmichael, Ginsberg, Cooper, E Brogan Congress 1967.07.22 2000 HRS International Electronics polyester 360m open reel 8mm tape 1/2 track mono 9.5 cm/sec iec&nab equalisation required cleaning and leaders added good copy requiring editing of sides one and two together as one. required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, air sealed for 18 months with silica gel to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967....

1.4.29

LATHAM FAMILY 1966.12.18, MR AND MRS LATHAM, CHARLES, CAROLINE AND CAROLINE'S HUSBAND, QUARTER TRACK STEREO, INTERNATIONAL ELECTRONICS ACETATE OPEN REEL 8MM TAPE, PLANNED ENVIRONMENT THERAPY TRUST, SIDE 1: 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION: FAMILY DISCUSSION WITHOUT THE MEN, SIDE 2: 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION: FULL FAMILY DISCUSSION, BOTH SIDES ARE INCLUDED IN THE MASTER FILE 1.4.29

1.4.32

DR JOSEPH BERKE, , SIDE 2: 1965.07.16 GARY BRILLIANT AND DR JOSEPH BERKE IN SURGERY. GARY RELATES A STARTLING CHANGE IN HIMSELF AFTER TAKING LSD: A GREAT EXPERIENCE OF EMOTIONAL OPENING UP. , HOUSED IN AN RCA BLUE BOX 'SOUND TAPE' 360M ACETATE 704 SERIES. 9.5 CM/SEC IEC&NAB EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO

1.4.38

JOHN GERASSI (CONTINUATION) , DL9 SIDE B, INTERSOUND RECORDINGS DUB, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, FULL TRACK MONO COPY, SCOTCH 150 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, AIR SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS WITH SILICA GEL TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES, 14:00 QUESTIONS : PAUL GOODMAN , DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.40

EVAN JONES, ANDREW SALKEY, CONGRESS 1967.07.26 1930 HRS POETRY READING AND LECTURE, SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACCUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES TAIL OUT, 19 CM/SEC IEC EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO GOOD OUTPUT WITH SOME MICROPHONE CLIPPING AS SOURCE, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967

1.4.41

ALLEN GINSBERG, SIMON WINKENEUR, CONGRESS 1967.07.27 PUBLIC ADDRESS, SCOTCH 175 7" POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACCUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES TAIL OUT, 19 CM/SEC IEC EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO GOOD OUTPUT, DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, ALL ON ONE SIDE OF THE TAPE: START AND ENDS AS SOURCE

1.4.42 Stokley Carmichael Congress 1967.07.18 public address Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vaccuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques tail out 19 cm/sec iec equalisation, half track mono good output Dialects Of Liberation Congress 1967 'track 2: second half of public address and beginning of floor questions' track 4: last part of floor questions and press conference' Dialects Of Liberation Congress 1967...

1.4.44 Stokley Carmichael Congress 1967.07.18 afternoon panel discussion Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vaccuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques tail out 19 cm/sec iec equalisation, half track mono good output dialects of liberation congress 1967 violence, power and anti-power end as source this file is put into file 1.4.43 as I think it sits between the two files in there as a continuum of the programme. it does because the edit points exist Dialects Of Liberation Congress 1967

1.4.46, Saturday night DL14 side A, R D Laing, Stokley Carmichael: demystification of violence, 19 cm/sec iec equalisation half track mono , Scotch 175 7 inch polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vaccuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, excerpt from Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967

1.4.47, DR RONALD LAING_THE OBVIOUS_DL4 SIDE A, INTERSOUND RECORDING EXCERPT FROM THE DIALECTS OF LIBERATION CONGRESS 1967, 19 CM/SEC IEC1 EQUALISATION, HALF TRACK MONO SOURCE, THIS IS FULL TRACK MONO, SCOTCH 150 LP 18 CM POLYESTER REQUIRED CLEANING OF MOLD AND CONTAMINANTS PRESENT, VACCUUM SEALED FOR 18 MONTHS TO KILL OFF THE CONTAMINANTS AND VACUUMED USING GENTLE CLEANING TECHNIQUES, SOUND SUFFERS FROM DEGRADED TAPE OUTPUT MANIFESTING ITSELF IN SOME AUDIO DISTORTION AT TIMES,

1.4.48, Allen Ginsberg, Stokely Carmichael, Saturday Night DL13 side a contains chanting with accor-dian, Japanese, English, discussion 1967.07.22 Intersound recordings dub, 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono, Scotch 175 7" polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vaccuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, Stokely Carmichael, discussion: violence, cultural imposition, culture adoption, fight for cultural integrity, imposition of culture on the Third World, Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967

1.4.50, Stokely Carmichael, Allen Ginsberg, Beck open discussion on individualism, Saturday Night DL 14 side B, Intersound recordings dub, 19 cm/sec iec1 equalisation, full track mono on 18 cm reel, Scotch 175 polyester required cleaning of mold and contaminants present, vacuum sealed for 18 months to kill off the contaminants and vacuumed using gentle cleaning techniques, return to self, suppressed and oppressed culture, police, Dialects of Liberation Congress 1967

